

16-19 October 2023

EEG and MEG methods multi-hub meeting

Cutting
Gardens

cuttinggardens2023.org

Foreword

Electroencephalography (EEG) and Magnetoencephalography (MEG) are powerful tools for investigating the living human brain, making these two technologies valuable assets for both clinical and basic research worldwide. However, mastering the intricacies of a comprehensive analysis pipeline, avoiding pitfalls, and adhering to current best practice standards can be a daunting task. This challenge is particularly acute in non-central regions, particularly outside Western Europe and North America, where access to cutting-edge developments is limited.

This is why [CuttingEEG](#) was established in 2014 to bring cutting-edge methods for EEG and MEG analysis to researchers. [The CuttingEEG symposia](#) bring together scientists developing new methods for EEG/MEG data analysis with those applying these techniques to explore the human brain and its disorders.

The advent of online video conferencing at the start of the new decade opened up the possibility of accessible, inclusive, and open online meetings on a scale never before imagined, at a fraction of the ecological impact of regular in-person meetings. CuttingEEG seized this opportunity to organise a large live event called [LiveMEEG](#) on Good Scientific Practices in MEG and EEG research. This event attracted the attention of a broad scientific community of over 1200 attendees, many of

whom would not have been able to join a local event in Europe. For CuttingEEG, this event was a game-changer and inspired us to reach out to other communities worldwide.

However, as we expanded our reach, we also recognized the limitations of a traditional conference model, where a central organiser assembles a list of speakers to address a unified audience. We decided to adopt a different approach. We engaged with the broader [CuttingEEG community](#) [link to mailing list] to gather volunteers to organise local events around the world. Importantly, the new event we envisioned would not only showcase cutting-edge MEEG methods but also serve as a **springboard for empowering local communities eager to participate in the global scientific community.**

Instead of a mere multi-hub meeting for cutting-edge MEEG methods, **CuttingGardens is a unique blend of virtual and in-person engagement.** It's a virtual, open meeting that facilitates global knowledge sharing, and an approachable in-person community that fosters local expertise development.

CuttingGardens is a scientific conference that delves into cutting-edge EEG & MEG methods, but it's also an experiment in scientific communication. It unfolds in parallel across multiple locations (known as «Gardens») around the globe, with a shared global program that streams to all locations and local sessions tailored to the interests of regional research communities.

We brought together **21 Gardens** spanning Europe, the Americas, and Asia, each with independent local organising committees and participants. Each Garden could adopt a set of badges that reflected the types of activities taking place locally ([see here](#) for a description). This flexibility allowed Gardens to range from simple broadcasting hubs for the global event's plenary sessions to self-contained scientific gatherings broadcasting local lectures, workshops, and satellite events to the broader community. As a global coordinating entity, CuttingEEG provided a ready-to-use catalogue of lectures, tutorials (and tutor training), demos, and a virtual platform to host the conference.

This document is an attempt to report what transpired at CuttingGardens 2023. Our goal is to provide readers with a taste of the event's vibrant atmosphere and inspire future participants in the upcoming event—stay tuned for what's coming!

This booklet has been compiled by the Belgrade Garden, especially by Anđela Šoškić and Vojislav Jovanovic from University of Belgrade

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Speaker badge

Tutorial badge

Poster badge

Satellite badge

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** Planned but could not happen*

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Plenary lectures

Theoretical advances in cognitive neuroscience made through meeg

[Link to live capture](#)

Chair : Anne-Sophie Dubarry, Aix-Marseille Univ, CNRS, CRPN, Marseille, France

VISCERAL SIGNALS, BRAIN DYNAMICS & SUBJECTIVITY

Catherine Tallon-Baudry¹

¹ *Laboratoire de Neurosciences Cognitives, Ecole Normale Supérieure, Paris*

Abstract

Subjective experiences, the hallmark of consciousness, presupposes the existence of a subject of experience. Here, I propose and test the hypothesis that the biological mechanism to generate the subject of experience is rooted in the monitoring of visceral signals by the brain. Visceral organs such as the heart and the stomach

are constantly active and their activity is relayed up to the central nervous system. In addition to having a profound impact on resting-state brain dynamics, neural responses to visceral signals contribute to subjective perceptual experiences, subjective judgements and subjective mental life.

FOCUSING WORKING MEMORY FOR ACTION ... INSIGHTS FROM EEG

Freek van Ede¹

¹ *Proactive Brain Lab, Institute for Brain and Behavior Amsterdam, Department of Experimental and Applied Psychology, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam*

Abstract

In cognitive neuroscience, action is often considered the "endpoint" – the process that follows specific cognitive operations such as working-memory retention. Yet, anticipated action (broadly defined as our behavioural goals) often serves as the "starting point" invoking specific cognitive processes. In my talk, I will share a selection of our

EEG studies that highlight the profound bi-directional links between visual working memory and action. Using the study of visual working memory as an example, I will make the more general point how the electrophysiology of cognition should not – and even cannot – be studied without also considering action.

- Global program
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EMERGENCE OF LANGUAGE DURING EARLY DEVELOPMENT

Clément François¹

¹ *Laboratoire Parole et Langage, Institute of Language communication and the brain, CNRS, Aix-Marseille Université*

Abstract

Neural sensitivity to statistical regularities has been proposed as a fundamental biological property underlying language acquisition. In the case of speech, statistical regularities may play a crucial role in the acquisition of language by contributing to word segmentation, rule learning and word-to-picture mapping. In this talk, I present

recent results from different labs showing that Frequency tagging applied to EEG data collected during artificial language learning paradigms in newborns, infants, and children is a powerful tool to decipher the emergence of basic language learning mechanisms during development.

Challenges and opportunities in real time eeg processing and classification tools for brain computer interfaces

[Link to live capture](#)

Chair : Marie Constance Corsi, NERV team, Inria Paris,
Paris Brain Institute, France

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GEOMETRIC DEEP LEARNING MEETS BCI TO ADVANCE INTER-SESSION AND -SUBJECT TRANSFER

Reinmar Kobler^{1,2}

¹ART, Japan, ²Riken AIP, Japan

Abstract

Current brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) do not generalize well across domains (e.g., sessions and subjects) without expensive supervised re-calibration on small domain-specific data, which severely limits BCI utility and scalability. Fortunately, geometric deep learning offers a remedy via combining data-efficiency and invariances of Riemannian geometry aware methods with feature learning capabilities of neural nets. In this talk, I will present a geometric deep learning framework to perform unsupervised domain adaptation (UDA)

on the symmetric, positive definite (SPD) manifold. The framework can be readily applied to multi-source/-target and online UDA scenarios. Using oscillatory EEG BCI datasets, we demonstrate that a simple, network architecture, which we denote TSMNet, can obtain state-of-the-art performance in inter-session and -subject transfer without compromising on neurophysiological interpretability.

FACING THE SMALL DATA REALITY IN EVENT-RELATED POTENTIAL BCI PROTOCOLS

Michael Tangermann¹

¹ Data-Driven NeuroTech Lab, Donders Institute, Radboud University, Nijmegen, The Netherlands

Abstract

Machine learning methods that are capable to decode brain states in single trial play a role not only in closed-loop neurotechnological systems such as brain-computer interfaces (BCI) but also allow to obtain immediate feedback for participants who participate in studies that address fundamental research. Training up such a decoding model typically requires labeled training data from an individual participant / BCI user that is obtained at the beginning of a session. Recording this data limits the duration of the following on-

line experiment or BCI application. In my talk I will first provide an overview of mitigations of this problem, that all have in common that they try to minimize the need for individual data for a novel user or session, before zooming into three recently developed classification methods for event-related potential data, that make use of domain-specific regularization to minimize the need of training data.subjective judgements and subjective mental life.

CONDUCTING BCI PROTOCOLS WITH PATIENTS

Theresa Vaughan¹

¹ *National Center for Adaptive Neurotechnologies, Albany Stratton VA Medical Center*

Abstract

Studies have shown brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) can allow people with severe motor impairment to communicate using brain signals rather than muscles independently in their homes. However, after over three decades of research, BCIs remain unavailable to the people who need them most. The Shirley Ryan Ability Lab in Chicago, Illinois and the National Center for Adaptive Neurotechnologies (NCAN) in Albany, New York

are exploring the use of telehealth to introduce clinicians, their patients, and patient caregivers to EEG-based BCI technology in the form of a simple one-target SSVEP-based BCI called the MusicBox. We are developing methods for BCI training, use, and support. This talk will address the background and significance, current work, and the challenges, of these methods.

- Global program
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Reproducible processing pipelines and multiverses

[Link to live capture](#)

Chair : Yu-Fang Yang, Division of Experimental Psychology and Neuropsychology, Department of Education and Psychology, Freie Universität Berlin, Berlin, Germany

EEGMANYPIPELINES

Elena Cesnaite¹

¹ *Department of Neurology, Max Planck Institute for Human Cognitive and Brain Sciences, Leipzig, Germany*

Abstract

Researchers analyzing electroencephalographic (EEG) data are faced with a choice between countless alternative and plausible analysis approaches. The variability of these analytical approaches among researchers in real-life practice and the extent to which they affect the results is unknown. The EEGManyPipelines project is a community-driven many-analyst project that aims to investigate the robustness of EEG findings across different analytical approaches. With this aim, a single EEG dataset, together with a set of

8 hypotheses, was sent to more than 300 expert teams participating in the project. In total, 168 teams successfully completed the task and returned their results. In this talk, I will present the initial findings of the project, detailing how variable the analytic choices and results are. We will discuss whether a prototypical EEG analysis pipeline exists and whether analytic practices should be standardized for more robust and comparable results.

THE DATA-PROCESSING MULTIVERSE OF EVENT-RELATED POTENTIALS: OPTIMIZING PIPELINES FOR EXPERIMENTAL EFFECTS, DATA QUALITY, AND INTERNAL CONSISTENCY

Peter Clayson¹

¹ *Department of Psychology, University of South Florida, Tampa, FL, USA*

Abstract

Numerous methodological choices must be made when analyzing event-related potential (ERPs), and the same ERP can be examined using different, reasonable pipelines. Unfortunately, different pipelines can lead to different statistical conclusions. Multiverse analyses of the data-processing pipeline can shed light how different data-processing decisions impact ERP outcomes. Different pipelines might be uniquely suited for interpretations focused on experimental effects, data quality, or psychometric internal consistency. Multiverse analyses provide a rigorous bottom-up

approach for optimizing data processing and can inform top-down decisions about data processing. Routine analysis of the data-processing multiverse will hopefully serve to improve the replicability and quality of ERP effects. The proposed process of analyzing the data-processing multiverse paves the way for better refinement, identification, and selection of methodological parameters, ultimately improving the utility of ERPs in psychological research.

- Global program
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AGREED REPORTING TEMPLATE FOR EEG METHODOLOGY – INTERNATIONAL STANDARD

Andela Šoškić¹

¹ *Faculty of Education, University of Belgrade, Belgrade, Serbia*

Abstract

Even though it is widely accepted that reporting on research transparently and thoroughly is crucial both for reproducibility and confidence in science, achieving the necessary degree of transparency and detail has proven to be a challenge, especially when using complex methods like MEEG. Over decades, the standards of a good MEEG research report have become stricter and more elaborated, but, in practice, this has not been reflected in more thorough methods descriptions in publications. ARTEM-IS is an attempt

to help with this challenge from a different angle - by designing research methods questionnaires that cover methods details of EEG experiments, and allow creating methods metadata supplementary documents (human-reader-friendly PDF reports and meta-science-friendly JSONLD files). This talk will focus on the current status of the ARTEM-IS project, potential uses and benefits of this approach, as well as limitations and challenges to making a widely useful and used tool of this kind.

Deep neural network analysis of meeg data: a roadmap to using machine learning with meeg

- Global program
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Link to live capture

Chair : Maximilien Chaumon, CNRS, Paris Brain Institute (PBI),
Centre de Neuroimagerie de Recherche (CENIR), Equipe MEG-EEG, France

LEARNING M/EEG REPRESENTATIONS WITH SELF-SUPERVISION

Hubert Banville ¹

¹ FAIR, Meta AI, London, United Kingdom

Abstract

For years, deep learning advances in fields like natural language processing and computer vision relied on large annotated datasets and supervised learning approaches. However, recent breakthroughs have demonstrated the effectiveness of unsupervised approaches that use even larger "unlabeled" datasets - an idea that for instance led to the success of large language models. While collecting brain activity data is costly and time-consuming, the availability of openly

accessible M/EEG data makes unsupervised approaches such as contrastive and self-supervised learning (SSL) increasingly promising. This talk will explore how SSL can be applied to learn meaningful and useful representations of M/EEG data. Key considerations and example use cases will be discussed, shedding light on the potential of unsupervised learning for advancing M/EEG research.

CLASSIC MACHINE LEARNING VERSUS DEEP LEARNING: IS THERE A CLEAR WINNER?

Maarten De Vos ^{1,2}

¹ Department of Electrical Engineering (ESAT), STADIUS Center for Dynamical Systems, Signal Processing and Data Analytics, KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium ; ² Department of Development and Regeneration, University Hospitals Leuven, Child Neurology, KU Leuven, Leuven, Belgium

Abstract

There is a long history of machine learning approaches for the analysis of EEG (e.g. in epilepsy, sleep or BCI). With the availability of big datasets and the advances of deep learning approaches, various papers claim superiority of deep learning

for various tasks. Is deep learning achieving a clear performance gain? How do we deal with uncertainty in deep learning and interaction with the human expert? How can we expect in the future?

USING ARTIFICIAL DEEP NEURAL NETWORKS TO PREDICT AND UNDERSTAND HUMAN VISION

Radoslaw Martin Cichy¹

¹ Faculty of Education and Psychology, Freie Universität Berlin, Berlin, Germany

Abstract

Artificial deep neural networks (DNNs) are the current workhorse model of the human visual system. In this talk I will showcase how DNNs are used to predict and explain human visual brain activity recorded with M/EEG during object and scene perception. I will present shortly older foundational work that established a hierarchical correspondence between brain activity and DNNs. Then focusing on recent research, I will present a study establishing end-to-end DNN modelling of EEG

data: the model takes pixels as input and gives EEG data as output. I will then highlight several ways how DNNs are used as tools in EEG research, for example to establish feature processing hierarchies over time, to elucidate the visual coding format in the infant brain, or to model brain activity and categorization behavior. I will close with a preview of ongoing efforts such as modeling EEG data recorded during movie watching or language comprehension.

- Global program
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Belgrade

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[Local plenary lectures](#)[Link to live capture](#)

ANALYSING MEEG DATA: LESSONS FROM VISUAL EVOKED POTENTIALS

Jasna Martinović¹

¹ *University of Edinburgh, School of Philosophy, Psychology and Language Sciences, UK*

Abstract

In the last decade, many new approaches to analysing magneto and electroencephalographic (MEEG) data have emerged, supplanting more traditional event-related potential analyses (ERPs). However, interpretation of ERP results benefits from decades of existing literature. Many new methods have yet to be validated to such an extent. In this talk, I will discuss several properties of Visual Evoked Potentials (VEPs) that make them ideal for validating data analytic approaches and thus constraining interpretation of MEEG results. First, as VEPs are highly localised to occipital electrodes (i.e. easily reducible to a univariate outcome) and their amplitude and latency are so contrast-dependent, they represent an ideal

case for evaluating how amplitude and latency changes to MEEG waveforms affect decoding accuracy. Second, VEPs are useful in evaluating measures of MEEG variability. Luminance-driven P1 occurs first in the waveform and its amplitude is on the whole positive. This allows for evaluations of variability in the context of a component's amplitude, demonstrating that participants with a higher P1 mean also exhibit more variance, including during the baseline. In conclusion, new analytic approaches are still applied to the same old waveforms, and can therefore benefit from being validated on large-scale VEP datasets, whose generators and properties are very well understood. subjective judgements and subjective mental life.

Local satellite event

Link to live capture

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EXPLORING THE FRONTIER OF MOBILE EEG RESEARCH: NAVIGATING THROUGH HISTORY, PROGRESS, CHALLENGES, AND INNOVATIONS IN ECOLOGICAL STUDIES

Ivan Gligorijević¹

¹ *mBrainTrain, Serbia*

Abstract

Researchers are progressively embracing the utilization of EEG in innovative environments, stretching beyond the conventional, static laboratory settings. However, the pertinent question arises – does mobile EEG transcend being merely a trendy term and a technological prospect, and what tangible value do ecological studies contribute? We aim to trace the motivation and pro-

gress enveloping the field over the past decade and explore the accompanying challenges, especially those related to capturing research-grade EEG amidst motion and additional interferences. Through a showcase of diverse examples, we will dissect the advancement in mobile EEG research and delve into the factors propelling and fueling the future innovation within this domain.

Local symposia

Get-to-know-each-other

Link to live capture

Chair : Vanja Ković, University of Belgrade, Faculty of Philosophy, Laboratory for Neurocognition and Applied Cognition, Serbia

NEW BULGARIAN UNIVERSITY NEUROSCIENCE LABORATORY

Ivo Popivanov^{1,2}

¹ *New Bulgarian University, Department of Cognitive Science and Psychology, Neuroscience Laboratory, Bulgaria* ; ² *Medical University, Sofia, Department of Neurology, University Hospital "Alexandrovska", Bulgaria*

Abstract

The Neuroscience lab, associated with the Department of Cognitive Science and Psychology at the New Bulgarian University (NBU), was established in the early 2000 by Prof. David Popivanov, who was a renowned electrophysiologist from the Bulgarian Academy of Sciences and a part-time lecturer at the NBU. The first apparatus was a custom-built polygraph with 17 channels, which was soon replaced by a 32-channel system from the Austrian company g-Tec.

Most of the research projects between 2000 and 2010 were focused on nonlinear dynamics of EEG oscillations during cognitive tasks, as well as evoked activity during processes of translation from one language to another (Eye-to-IT EU project).

In 2021, the lab was modernised with a contemporary 64-channel system from the Iranian startup company ScienceBeam, supported by the NBU and a personal grant of Ivo Popivanov. Currently the lab is involved in several research projects on evoked and induced activity during face perception, emotion processing, language and executive function control.

- Global program
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UNIVERSITY OF BELGRADE LABORATORY FOR BIOMEDICAL ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGIES – MUBE

Milica Janković ¹

¹ *University of Belgrade, School of Electrical Engineering, Laboratory for Biomedical Engineering and Technologies, Serbia*

Abstract

The laboratory for BioMedical Instrumentation and Technology (BMIT) is located at the University of Belgrade – School of Electrical Engineering. BMIT activities include the development of diagnostic and assistive systems with a focus on neurodevelopmental and sensory-motor disorders, pre-clinical and clinical research, and the development of computer-supported decision-making systems in medicine. The laboratory is equipped with wearable systems for measuring physiological signals and movement analysis, as well as non-contact systems for measuring biometric signals such as radar systems, thermal imaging cameras, and

eye-tracking systems. In teaching and research, emphasis is placed on defining and solving real challenges, always in cooperation with medical staff, psychologists, special educators, etc. that also validate developed methods and instruments. The multimodal approach, i.e. synchronous measurement of various biometric signals in experimental conditions with the extraction of features and the application of machine learning methods for the classification of subjects' states is one of the main directions of further laboratory research.

UNIVERSITY OF BELGRADE SCIENCE AND RESEARCH CENTRE - HYBIS PROJECT PI

Andrej Savić¹

¹ *University of Belgrade, School of Electrical Engineering, Science and Research Centre, Serbia*

Abstract

Dr Andrej Savić is affiliated with Science and Research Centre of the University of Belgrade - School of Electrical Engineering (ETF) with a role of senior science associate. Main fields of his research interest are biomedical engineering, neural engineering and neuroscience, with the narrow expertise in: «Brain-Computer Interfaces (BCI)» and «closed-loop neurotechnology». He was involved in numerous public and private funded research projects on the topics: BCIs for stroke, assistive BCIs for ALS, neuroergonomics, hybrid BCIs, implantable neurotechnology etc. He is a principal investigator of a HYBIS project of Fund for Science of Republic of Serbia for excellent ideas of young researchers, leading a team of 4

researchers from 3 Science and Research institutions of University of Belgrade: ETF, Innovation Centre of ETF and Faculty of Medicine. The HYBIS project aims to develop and clinically test an innovative BCI prototype for the rehabilitation of sensory functions after stroke. The project activities involve exploration of multiple novel concepts in BCI research stroke rehabilitation generally. The project activities are in line with the most advanced and novel trends in introduction of top-down therapeutic methods in neurorehabilitation after stroke, quantitative and evidence-based approaches to therapy, and closed loop intelligent systems based on advanced machine learning algorithms.

- Global program
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UNIVERSITY OF NOVI SAD LABORATORY FOR BIOMEDICAL ENGINEERING AND INSTRUMENTATION

Dorđe Novaković¹, Sanja Mandić¹, Platon Sovilj¹

¹ *University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences, Serbia*

Abstract

In this presentation we present Laboratory of biomedical engineering and instrumentation from Department of power, electronics and communication engineering at Faculty of Technical Sciences (University of Novi Sad, Serbia). The topics of study and research in this laboratory are next: Structure and modules of biomedical instrumentation. Measuring quantities in biomedical measurements. Types and characteristics of biomedical measurement-acquisition systems: measurement quantities, intensity ranges of measurement quantities, frequency ranges of measurement quantities and standard measurement methods. Measurement transducers in biomed-

ical measurement and acquisition systems. Signal conditioning in biomedical measurement and acquisition systems. Digitization of conditioned signals in biomedical measurement and acquisition systems. The role of computer and communication technologies in biomedical measurement and acquisition systems. Data acquisition applications. Introduction to methods of measuring different physical quantities in biomedical measurements. Analog measuring instruments in biomedical engineering. Digital measuring instruments in biomedical engineering. Methods of measuring electrophysiological signals. Measurement of electrical activity of nerve cells.

Measurement of electrical muscle activity. Measurement of the electrical activity of the heart. Methods of measuring galvanic response. Displacement measurement methods in biomedical engineering. Methods of measuring force and pressure in medicine. Methods of heart rate measurement. Blood pressure measurement methods. Measurement of lung capacity and air speed during breathing. Methods of measuring chemical components of blood, tissues and organic fluids. Methods of measuring the concentration of gases in medicine. Methods of measuring the partial pressure of gases in medicine. Spectrophotometric methods of measuring components of liquids and gases in medicine. Methods of quantitative measurements of solid blood particles. Methods of measuring body temperature. Methods of measuring arterial and venous pressure. Blood flow measurement methods. Methods of measuring the volume of displaced blood. Methods of measuring blood pH factor and gastric acidity. Methods of measuring breathing rhythm. Methods of measuring respiration rate. Measurement methods in ballistocardiography. Measurement methods in magnetoencephalography. Ultrasonic measurement methods in biomedical engineering. Methods of measurement and data acquisition in thermography.

Detection of ionizing radiation in medicine. Detection of thermal radiation in medicine. Measurement methods in X-ray diagnostics. Methods of measurement in computed tomography. Scintillation detectors in medicine. Parameters of nuclear magnetic resonance important for measurements in medicine. Measurement methods in nuclear magnetic resonance systems. Holter monitoring measurement-acquisition systems. Telemetry systems for biomedical measurements. Precision, accuracy and measurement uncertainty of biomedical measurement systems. Calibration of biomedical measurement and acquisition systems. Impact of interference, noise and biological artifacts in biomedical measurements. Calculation of measurement uncertainty in biomedical measurement systems. Introduction to metrological aspects of medical devices. Introduction to national legal metrology and international OIML standards for medical devices. Introduction to safety aspects in biomedical measurements.

- Global program
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UNIVERSITY OF BELGRADE LABORATORY FOR NEUROCOGNITION AND APPLIED COGNITION

Vanja Ković¹

¹ *University of Belgrade, Faculty of Philosophy, Laboratory for Neurocognition and Applied Cognition, Serbia*

Abstract

The Laboratory for Neurocognition and Applied Cognition (LNPK), situated within the Faculty of Philosophy at the University of Belgrade, is a distinguished and recently established research facility. It has been made possible through the dedicated efforts of its founding professors: Dejan Lalović, Vasilije Gvozdenović, and Vanja Ković. Their vision and commitment have been further bolstered by the generous support of esteemed academics, including Prof Guillaume Thierry from

Bangor University, Prof Kim Plunkett from the University of Oxford, Prof Kenneth Holmqvist from Lund University, and Dr. Andrej Savić from the University of Belgrade, who have contributed second-hand equipment to facilitate the lab's operations.

The LNPK's research endeavors encompass a wide array of cognitive neuroscience domains, exploring themes such as categorization, implicit vs. explicit processing,

taxonomic vs. thematic processing, sound symbolism, as well as applied neuroscience, deception detection, and neuroergonomics. This extensive scope reflects the lab's commitment to advancing our understanding of human cognition from various angles. One of the most notable aspects of the LNPK's impact is its role in nurturing talent. Over the past decade, the lab has provided training to over 30 undergraduate, master's, and doctoral students. Many of these students have gone on to pursue doctoral or post-doctoral positions in renowned research facilities worldwide, including the Oxford Baby Lab at the University of Oxford, the Cognitive Development Lab at Ohio State, BCBL (Basque Center on Cognition, Brain, and Language) in Spain, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, the Technological University Dublin, the Phonetics and Phonology Lab, and the Lisbon Baby Lab at the University of Lisbon. Additionally, some have joined the ranks of the teaching and research staff at the University of Belgrade. The

global reach of LNPK alumni, their contributions to prestigious institutions, and their academic achievements underscore the lab's dedication to fostering exceptional talent and promoting international collaboration in the field of cognitive neuroscience. The Laboratory for Neurocognition and Applied Cognition continues to make significant contributions to neurocognitive research through the development of future scholars in the field and in the recent years through the initiation of an international ARTEM-IS project dedicated to enhancing methodological reporting standards in EEG research. This initiative underscores the lab's commitment to not only advancing scientific knowledge but also promoting transparency and rigor within the research community.

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[Local talks](#)
[Link to live capture](#)

BEHAVIOURAL AND ELECTROPHYSIOLOGICAL CORRELATES OF PROCESSING THREATENING VS. NON-THREATENING STATIC VISUAL STIMULI

Gergana Moskova¹, Metodi Simeonov¹, Vladimir Ivanov¹, Ivo D. Popivanov^{1,2}

¹ *New Bulgarian University, Department of Cognitive Science and Psychology, Neuroscience Laboratory, Bulgaria*; ² *Medical University, Sofia, University Hospital "Alexandrovska", Department of Neurology, Bulgaria*

Abstract

Following DeLaRosa et al. (2014), we designed an EEG study in order to examine the behavioural and electrophysiological correlates of processing threatening static visual stimuli. We selected 108 pictures from the IAPS and 4 from the NAPS, categorizing them into two groups: threatening and non-threatening, based on their pleasantness values on the IAPS scale. Additionally, we presented 112 scrambled stimuli as distractors. A total of 15

(11 female) students (mean age 25.87), took part in the EEG experiment. The data were recorded from 28 channels with a sampling rate of 1 kHz, placed according to the 10/20 system covering the entire scalp. The stimuli were presented for 1500 ms, followed by 1500 ms inter-stimulus interval. Participants had to indicate whether the presented item was a real or a scrambled image by pressing a button.

The behavioural results showed faster Response Times (RT) to scrambled stimuli, with no significant difference between RT to threatening vs. non-threatening stimuli. Furthermore, EEG data showed pronounced differences in the early (100-

200 ms post-stimulus) and late (300-400 ms) event-related components between the different item categories.

- Global program
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ELECTROPHYSIOLOGICAL EVIDENCE FOR THE FACE INVERSION EFFECT (FIE) WITH LOW NUMBER OF REPETITIONS

Metodi Simeonov¹, Gergana Moskova¹, Vladimir Ivanov¹, Ivo D. Popivanov^{1,2}

¹ *New Bulgarian University, Department of Cognitive Science and Psychology, Neuroscience Laboratory, Bulgaria*; ² *Medical University, Sofia, University Hospital "Alexandrovska", Department of Neurology, Bulgaria*

Abstract

Previous EEG research showed two event-related (ERP) components which correlate with visual face perception – N170 and P240, indicating two stages of processing (Bentin et al., 1996; Rossion & Gauthier, 2002). In this study we aim at replicating those findings with substantially less repetitions of the stimuli. We selected a total of 80 images divided in 4 categories with 20 items each: upright and inverted face photographs, artificial objects and pixel scrambled faces. Participants. A total of 15 (12 female) volunteers (mean age 27.1), took part in the EEG experiment. Apparatus. EEG

data were recorded from 28 channels with a sampling rate of 1KHz, placed according to the 10/20 system covering the entire scalp. Procedure. The stimuli were presented for 500 ms, followed by 1500 ms inter-stimulus interval. The participants had passively view the stimuli and count the number of scrambled stimuli. Results. Both inverted and upright faces elicit the expected ERPs – N170 and P240 with larger amplitudes than the other stimuli categories. As expected the N170 for inverted faces has a larger amplitude, while P240 has a larger amplitude for upright faces.

DEVELOPMENT OF PHONOLOGICAL AWARENESS IN SHALLOW ORTHOGRAPHY: BEHAVIORAL AND NEUROCOGNITIVE INDICATORS

Katarina Stekić¹, Vanja Ković¹

¹ *University of Belgrade, Faculty of Philosophy, Laboratory for Neurocognition and Applied Cognition, Serbia*

Abstract

The aim of this study is to examine the development of phonological awareness by testing the longitudinal effects of an early reading intervention using ERP and eye-tracking. Subjects who participated in a reading intervention study conducted in 2019 will be re-examined to see differences when compared to controls several years after the intervention. MMN and N1 components will be examined, based on a recent

review study (Stekić et al., 2023). MMN indicates phonological sensitivity and reflects phonological discrimination ability, while the N1 shows sensitivity to print recognition and print processing, with N1 lateralization being a robust predictor of reading ability. We hypothesize that a higher amplitude will be found with the intervention group in the MMN experiment when compared to controls.

We also assume a higher N1 amplitude with the intervention group. Additionally, the intervention group will show a more pronounced left lateralization of the N1 effect. We propose that there will be a significant difference between the control and intervention groups in eye-tracking patterns

as well (both saccade and fixation patterns), which will correlate with ERP effects.

- Global program
- **A - G**
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- O - Z

IMPAIRMENT OF THETA AND BETA BAND OSCILLATIONS IN MIGRAINE WITH AURA DURING INTERICTAL PHASE

Vojislav Jovanović¹, Igor Petrušić²

¹ University of Belgrade, Faculty of Philosophy, Laboratory for Neurocognition and Applied Cognition, Serbia ;

² University of Belgrade, Faculty of Physical Chemistry, Laboratory for Advanced Analysis of Neuroimages, Serbia

Abstract

Migraine stands out as one of the most widespread and disabling conditions. While it has been conclusively established that the ictal phase of migraine, often accompanied by higher cortical dysfunctions (HCD), represents the most debilitating period of the disease, our understanding of cognitive functioning during the interictal phases remains incomplete. In our study, we utilized the Oddball paradigm to examine the features of different band oscillations in individuals diagnosed with migraine with aura (MwA) during their symptom-free phase. A total of 20 subjects were involved, including 10 MwA HCD patients and 10

healthy controls (HC). Event-Related Spectral Perturbation Analysis (ERSP) indicated weaker suppression of the upper beta band (20-30Hz) in MwA compared to HC, extending bilaterally from frontocentral to parietal regions and occurring very early, persisting up to 400ms after stimulus onset. Additionally, MwA showed a decrease in theta band (4-8Hz) power at the central and frontocentral electrodes while simultaneously exhibiting an increase at centroparietal and parietal sites. No differences were found in occipital, temporal, or frontal zones between MwA and HC.

ADVANCED TOOLS IN EDUCATION RESEARCH: THE BRAIN-COMPUTER INTERFACE AND THE STROOP EFFECT

Sanja Mandić¹, Vladimir Pejanović¹, Jelena Đerić¹, Nina Evetović¹, Sara Miljuš¹, Platon Sovilj¹

¹ University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technical Sciences, Laboratory of Biomedical Engineering and Instrumentation, Serbia

Abstract

This paper provides an overview of existing research on the subject of the Stroop effect, as well as the mutual correlation of attention, learning, and the Stroop effect. Furthermore, the paper describes an experiment, which aim was to examine the Stroop effect in subjects of different genders and ages. The experiment was realized

using the EMOTIV experimental platform, which provides an experiment within the EMOTIVLabs software, whose role is to examine the Stroop effect, and which was used in this work. To collect data and the results of the experiment, a five-channel EEG device EMOTIV Insight was used.

This EEG device is compatible to work with the EMOTIV experimental platform and the corresponding software packages within it. The paper describes the experimental setting and gives the

analysis and presentation of the results of the experiment.

- Global program
- **A - G**
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DECODING COGNITIVE PROCESSES IN ARITHMETIC TASKS: AN EEG-BASED CONVOLUTIONAL NEURAL NETWORK MODEL

Nikola Petrović¹, Lemana Spahić², Sanja Mandić¹, Platon Sovilj¹

¹ University of Novi Sad ; ² Verlab Research Institute for Biomedical Engineering, Bosnia and Herzegovina

Abstract

In this study, we introduce a novel system, developed in Python, for classifying cognitive processes based on EEG signals. The system employs a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) trained on a dataset comprising 4-minute EEG recordings from 30 subjects. Each EEG sample processed for CNN input is 0.5 seconds long and is transformed into EEG power levels for each channel. The primary achievement of this research is the successful use of the CNN to classify whether a subject

is performing a cognitive task well or poorly. The system's performance has been validated by experts in cognitive neuroscience and psychology, and its results have been benchmarked against state-of-the-art studies in the field. This work represents a significant contribution to the field of EEG-based cognitive process classification, demonstrating the effective integration of machine learning techniques and neuroscience data.

Local workshops & tutorials

EEGLAB WORKSHOP

Vojislav Jovanović¹, Katarina Stekić¹

¹ University of Belgrade, Faculty of Philosophy, Laboratory for Neurocognition and Applied Cognition, Serbia

PYTHON-MNE WORKSHOP

Marija Novičić¹

¹ University of Belgrade, School of Electrical Engineering, Serbia

MULTIMODAL PSYCHOPHYSIOLOGICAL MEASUREMENTS – EXPERIMENTAL SETUP WORKSHOP

Milica Janković¹, Jelena Jovanović²

¹ University of Belgrade, School of Electrical Engineering, Laboratory for Biomedical Engineering and Technologies, Serbia ; ² mBrainTrain, Serbia

Bournemouth

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Local plenary lectures

MACHINE LEARNING IN EEG

Géza Gergely Ambrus¹

¹ *Bournemouth University, Faculty of Science and Technology, Department of Psychology, UK*

Abstract

This talk will present a series of studies that explored memory processes, investigating the spatio-temporal dynamics of neural signals of successful memory retrieval. The overarching goal of this research was to better understand the commonalities in mnemonic processes, and how their neural correlates unfold over time, using multivariate cross-classification across EEG datasets. Cross-dataset classification is a data-driven technique that involves training machine learning classifiers on data from one dataset and testing it on data from a different dataset to examine how neural representations of different cognitive processes generalize across different experimental conditions or tasks.

The first set of studies examined the neural correlates of face learning and recognition, and specifically, the role of familiarization type (perceptual, media, and personal) in the emergence of neural signals of familiarity. All three datasets yielded significant cross-classification effects, mainly in the right hemisphere between 270-630 milliseconds

after stimulus onset, suggestive of a general neural indicator of face familiarity, independent of familiarization type, participant, or stimulus used. Further analyses revealed that neural patterns for passive viewing of personally familiar and unfamiliar faces were useful in decoding familiarity in a matching task where familiarity was attained through a short perceptual task. This indicates that the visual processing of personally familiar and purely perceptually familiarized faces involves similar mechanisms, the neural correlates of which can be decoded across different experimental paradigms. Further analysis exploring the spatio-temporal properties of the shared familiarity signal for faces found that the general face familiarity signal was present for long-term personally familiar faces under passive viewing, as well as for acknowledged and concealed familiarity responses. Importantly, a differential modulation of the signal in the 200-400 ms and the 400-600 ms was observed.

The second set of studies aimed to investigate the extent to which the face-familiarity signal, observed in the previous investigations, could be generalized to non-face stimuli. When training was performed on non-face datasets, an early (around 200-300 ms) to late (post-400 ms) differentiation was found. Successful cross-classification for non-face stimuli (music and object/scene associations) was most pronounced in the late period. Additionally, a striking dissociation between familiar and remembered objects was seen, with shared signals present only in the late window for remembered objects, while cross-classification for familiar objects was successful in the early period as well. These findings suggest that late neural signals of memory retrieval generalize across sensory modalities and stimulus types, and the

dissociation between familiar and remembered objects may provide further insight into the underlying processes.

In summary, this research program demonstrated the existence of a generalizable neural signal of recognition memory that transcends variations in tasks, modalities, and stimulus types. The use of openly available data has been critical for this work, facilitating the pooling of diverse datasets across studies. These results illustrate the potential of multivariate pattern classification analysis as a robust technique for exploring the shared cognitive mechanisms underlying memory processes.

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CO-REGISTERED EYE MOVEMENTS AND EEG

Federica Degno¹

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Abstract

There is a growing interest in experiments that simultaneously record participants' eye movements and EEG signal. With this type of experiments, researchers are able to examine neural correlates of cognitive processes as they occur under natural experimental conditions. In the talk, the theoretical contributions of this type of data will be discussed, with a focus on the investigation of both

foveal and parafoveal processing in young and older skilled readers to gain insights into the nature and fine grain time-course of cognitive processes. The examples will demonstrate the importance of recording brain activity when information is presented more naturally than in traditional EEG/ERP tasks.

SOCIAL PERCEPTION IN VIRTUAL REALITY

Xun He¹

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Abstract

Traditional desk-mounted EEG research has been facing the challenge of ecological validity and believability in neuroscience research on human social behaviours. The combination of virtual rea-

lity (VR) and EEG techniques provides a solution for realistic and controlled rendering of social scenes for human neuroscience research.

This talk presents the research in progress at the Multimodal Immersive NEuro-sensing (MINE) Research Cluster at Bournemouth University. In this study, we asked the question whether planning of future social interactions is embodied in visual perception of faces and scenes. Social interactions between participants and non-player characters (NPCs) took place in VR while EEG was being recorded. Planned analysis on the N170 event-related potential component (a biomarker of face perception) and exploratory analysis were

employed. Despite no effect was found in N170, potential embodied cognition of social interactions was observed between 150 and 350 ms over frontal and parietal midline channels. This study illuminated a promising research direction and highlighted some technical considerations for immersive EEG research.

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Posters

LOOKING AND THINKING TOGETHER DURING LIVE PERFORMANCE: CHALLENGES IN MULTIMODAL HYPERSCANNING DATA SYNCHRONISATION

Albane Arthuis¹

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Abstract

This work addresses some of the significant challenges that occur when collecting eye movement and EEG data in a live performance environment. It was conducted during a series of live performances, titled "How Shall We Begin Again" and is part of the ERC-funded Neurolive project. This research aims to investigate behavioural and neurophysiological data in a live art and ecologically valid context. The performance experiment involved 50 dance solos, each lasting approximately 20 minutes. Over the two-day duration of the experiment, data from both wearable eye trackers (Pupil Labs Invisible) and mobile electroencephalogram (EEG, Ant Neuro) were simultaneously collected from 51 participants, with an additional 23 individuals exclusively providing eye tracking data, resulting in 21 hours of recordings. We captured blinking, gaze fixation, head movement, as well as 32-channel EEG signals. Behavioural data were also collected from all 165 attendees. Col-

lecting data from multiple people and sensors presents several challenges including synchronisation between people, synchronisation between different devices (eye trackers and EEG), data storage and processing. Ahead of the performance, we developed software employing LSL (Lab Streaming Layer) to facilitate synchronisation. It broadcasted wireless messages to both the eye tracking and EEG systems, including a 'heartbeat' signal transmitted every 10 seconds, songs' information facilitated through the Spotify API and performance-related comments (i.e. laughter, applause). We further aligned the systems using video and audio from the eye trackers and room cameras. Synchronising this extensive dataset provides a unique perspective and valuable insights into human perception of live experiences in social contexts.

NEURAL UNDERPINNINGS OF EMOTIONAL AROUSAL AND COGNITIVE REAPPRAISAL IN BULIMIA NERVOSA: THE LATE POSITIVE POTENTIAL

Sanjidha Hassan ¹, Dr Laura Renshaw-Vuillier ¹

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Abstract

Difficulties processing and regulating emotions is a well-known phenomenon in Bulimia Nervosa (BN). People with BN tend to experience emotions with more intensity, and often struggle to regulate them; for example under-utilising adaptive strategies such as cognitive reappraisal. However, this literature mainly relies on self-reports, which is sub-optimal due to the known difficulties in identifying and describing emotions in this population (termed alexithymia). This study used electroencephalography to investigate how people with BN process and regulate emotions, in a more objective manner. N=30 people with BN and N=32 controls viewed emotional pictures while being instructed to either reappraise or maintain their emotional reaction to them. Participants received instructions on how to reappraise, and also viewed neutral pictures. The Late positive poten-

tial (LPP) measured the intensity of their reactions. To test whether people with BN show heightened arousal, we ran a 2(BN vs control) x 2(emotion vs neutral) ANOVA, and to test if they can reduce their emotional response using reappraisal, we ran another 2(BN vs control) x 2(reappraise vs maintain) ANOVA. Preliminary findings suggest the LPP for negative pictures was greater than for neutral pictures to the same extent for both groups, suggesting no difference in emotion processing between groups. Second, there were no differences in reappraising or maintaining emotions between- or within- groups, suggesting that people with BN may be able to reappraise their emotions with support. Future detailed analyses will confirm these results and interpret them in the context of potential emotion intervention for people with BN.

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READING USING EEG AND EYETRACKING

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Abstract

Emerging evidence suggests digital reading may hinder attention control, vital for text comprehension. Addressing this, training in digital reading skills is a key educational challenge. Research questions: The primary goal is to examine how a 14-week digital reading training affects adolescents' long reading skills and their neural attention indices during reading. Additionally, the study explores the influence of question location (at the end or within the text), question type (localization,

local integration, global integration), and feedback type (none, simple, elaborated) on attentional effects. Methods. Co-registered EEG (32 electrodes) and eyetracking data will be collected in a pre-test/post-test design from 60 high school students while reading two texts. The texts are approximately 1500 words long and are divided into nine paragraphs. We created nine comprehension questions (multiple-choice), one per paragraph. Predictions.

After training, the alpha power over paragraphs of the text, as an indicator of attentional control, will differ between the experimental and the control group. Specifically, alpha power of the trained students will decrease more rapidly during the reading task than at pre-test. Additionally, the elaborated feedback will be beneficial in maintaining attention, whereas the question type and location are more exploratory inquiries. Such a design will provide pioneering evidence on the attentional

neural mechanisms of high school students during digital reading, together with a fine-grained assessment of the aspects - question type and location, and type of feedback - that may enhance such attentional mechanisms when specifically trained in a digital platform.

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EEG MEASURES OF RECURRENCE RISK IN DEPRESSION

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Abstract

With 50% of Major Depressive Disorder (MDD) cases being unremitting or recurrent, there is a need to understand the pathophysiology of MDD. An fMRI study found a self-blame selective signature that predicted MDD recurrence in remitted MDD (rMDD) patients. EEG studies have found altered processing of emotional stimuli in MDD. However, the EEG signatures of self-blaming emotions in MDD are elusive. Further, it is unknown if EEG can be used to make individualised MDD recurrence predictions. In this study, rMDD participants (n=85) and healthy controls (n=40) will undergo EEG testing while completing 1) a moral sentiment task, requiring judgement of sentences about positive and negative social behaviours, and 2) a blame/praise induction task requiring the recall of memories inducing feelings of self- and other-blame and praise. rMDD participants will complete a follow-up period until they develop a recurrent depressive episode, for up to 14 months. EEG measures of interest will be event-related

potential (ERP) amplitudes previously associated with emotional word processing (e.g. late positive potential) and theta power (4-7Hz) change for Task 1, and frontal-alpha asymmetry and signal complexity (sample entropy and Higuchi's fractal dimension) for Task 2. Principal Component Analysis factors derived from EEG measures will serve as: 1) outcome variables in a multivariate general linear model for a cross-sectional analysis comparing rMDD and HC participants, 2) predictors for time to recurrence in a cox regression, and 3) predictors in a machine and statistical model predicting MDD recurrence, to evaluate the feasibility of using EEG to make individualised predictions.

Local workshops & tutorials

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EEGLAB AND ERPLAB: AN INTRODUCTION

Andrew Hanson¹, Federica Degno¹

¹ *Bournemouth University, UK*

EEG-EYE TRACKING

Federica Degno¹, Otto Loberg¹

¹ *Bournemouth University, UK*

EEG & VIRTUAL REALITY: HARDWARE CONSIDERATIONS AND EXPERIMENTAL DESIGN

Andrew Hanson¹, Xun He²

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Local plenary lectures

AUDITORY RHYTHM PERCEPTION IN PREMATURE NEWBORNS

Sahar Moghim¹

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AN ELECTROPHYSIOLOGICAL APPROACH OF MEMORY IN AGING

Lucie Angel¹

¹ *Université de Tours (U7295), France*

EEG BIOMARKERS OF COGNITIVE DECLINE: STUDIES IN PARKINSON'S DISEASE AND DIFFERENT FORMS OF DEMENTIA

Nacin Betrouni¹

¹ *Inserm U1172, France*

Local talks

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EVOKED BRAIN RESPONSES TO PREDICTIONS IN TYPICAL AND ATYPICAL CHILDREN FROM 2 TO 6 YEARS OF AGE

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Abstract

Sensory prediction (SP) is the ability to anticipate future stimulations on the basis of previous sensory inputs. It is related to repetition suppression (RS) which is the reduction of activity in the brain when a stimulus is repeated or becomes irrelevant. Recent studies indicate these processes may be altered in children with neurodevelopmental disorders. We assessed somatosensory RS and SP of 38 typical and 12 atypical children from 2 to 6 years old to date, and recorded their brain activity is measured using 128-channel EEG. In typical children, we found a robust RS in both somatosensory and frontocentral areas, a somatosensory mismatch negativity-like activity (MMN), and a frontocentral P300 during deviance and postomission. Furthermore, we found a developmental effect on the P300 that depended on the type of deviance to be processed. Compared to typicals,

atypical children display a mismatch positivity in the somatosensory cortex during the postomission. Furthermore, they have a negative response 300ms after stimulation onset and a delayed positive response to both deviant and postomission stimulation. There is currently little information on tactile processing in children, despite studies showing the importance of this modality in understanding sensory impairments associated with NDD. Here we describe robust repetition suppression of tactile stimuli in typical and atypical children. Responses to unexpected stimulations (deviant and omissions) were inverted in polarity and delayed in atypical children, indicating different processing of this information. Further analysis will indicate if RS and SP can be used as a marker of neurodevelopmental disorders.

HOW ATYPICAL CHILDREN'S BRAIN PROCESS RHYTHM: THE CASE OF WILLIAMS SYNDROME

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Abstract

Williams syndrome (WS) is a genetic neurodevelopmental disorder characterised by hyperacusis (Levitin et al., 2005) and atypical language (Mervis, 2003). Despite a two years delay in language development, an important gain in vocabulary and great communication skills are later observed among WS children (Laing, 2002). The ability to extract rhythm patterns in auditory stimuli has been shown to support toddlers' language (Nazzi et al., 1998) and social skills acquisition (Loeb et al., 2021). The hyperacusis often found among WS individuals might explain their atypical language development. In this perspective, we aimed to compare WS children's (n = 7, aged from 11 to 15) auditory rhythms processing with a control group of typically developing children (n = 12, aged from 6 to 14) and a group of Down syndrome children (n = 5, 9 to 12) matched with chronological age

and developmental age. We investigated this via high-resolution electroencephalography (128 electrodes) to assess mismatched neural responses to either an ambiguous duple or triple metre beat. No priming was made. Stimulus patterns changed on timbre and pitch according to trials. Analysis of data is still in process. We expect higher amplitudes and atypical neural activity patterns for WS. Findings will be discussed in view of WS's atypical speech and auditory processing and may help to better understand neural networks, as previous results seem controversial with hypo- (Fagundes Silva et al., 2021) and hyperactivity of the auditory system (Zarchi et al., 2015).

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INVESTIGATING LEARNING MECHANISMS DURING STIMULUS EXPOSURE: AN EEG FREQUENCY TAGGING APPROACH

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Abstract

Visual statistical learning allows preverbal infants to organise visual stimulation in a coherent representation. Thus far, early visual statistical learning skills have been measured with post-exposure behavioural tasks that focus on the outcome of learning. These tasks may lead to ambiguous interpretations since there is no clear consensus about the directionality of the expected learning outcome in infancy. Electrophysiological measures can be acquired while learning occurs and can shed light onto the temporal course of learning. We propose an EEG frequency tagging approach to study 4- to 6-month-old infants' and adults' neural entrainment in response to visual regularities. Participants were presented with 20-second streams of shapes appearing at 6 Hz. They were randomly assigned to one of three conditions: a) standard doublet condition, inclu-

ding doublets of shapes with a translational probability (TP) of 1, b) control doublet condition, in which the TP between elements of a doublet was 0.25, and c) single condition, including randomly presented shapes. Results revealed that both infants and adults showed stimulus tracking at the base frequency of stimulation (6 Hz and its harmonics) that did not differ across conditions. On the other hand, activity at the doublet presentation frequency (3 Hz and its harmonics) varied across conditions. Infants were especially sensitive to the standard doublet condition, whereas adults were equally sensitive to the standard and the control doublet conditions. Overall, these results suggest that visual regularities can be detected early on. Frequency tagging seems a promising approach to study detection and learning during stimulus exposure.

RECORDING OF AUDITORY-EVOKED RESPONSES IN THE NEWBORN BRAIN USING OPTICALLY PUMPED MAGNETOMETERS

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Abstract

The excellent time sensitivity and good spatial resolution of Magnetoencephalography (MEG) make it a technique of choice for studying neurophysiological processes, and their evolution throughout the brain development. Traditional SQUIDS-based MEG systems have a one-size-fits-most rigid helmet, which is well suited for adults but much less for newborns, in which case one can only study a small subregion at a time. Optically pumped magnetometers (OPMs) are a novel MEG type where cryogenic-free sensors can be individually placed at will close to the scalp. They are therefore a potential prime choice for recording neural processes in newborns, which is the object of this study. Twelve healthy one-month-old newborns had OPMs placed on their head using an EEG cap with custom-made hol-

ders and were presented with two sound sequences. The first consists of a single pure tone presented at randomly varying intervals and the second sequence consists of a tone presented at 3Hz and a dishabituator presented every 4 tones. For the first sequence, the averaged evoked-response fields show a significant response at 210-260ms post-stimulus. For the second sequence, the power spectrum SNR is significantly >1 at the standard tone frequency (3Hz) and at the deviant tone frequency (0.75Hz). This study demonstrates the feasibility of recording one-month-old newborn neural activity using OPM-MEG system, both in the time domain and frequency domain, even for low presentation rates. It is an initial step that paves the way for further OPM-MEG neural recordings in newborns and in the whole lifespan.

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TIMES: EXPLORING CHANGES OF NEURAL UNDERPINNINGS OF TEMPORAL PROCESSING IN COGNITIVE AGING AND IN PRESENCE OF DEPRESSIVE SYMPTOMS

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Abstract

Objective: The present project aims at shedding light on the observed heterogeneity of cognitive decline trajectories across individuals, by investigating changes in the neural mechanisms underlying temporal processing in aging through simultaneous electroencephalography and functional magnetic resonance imaging (EEG-fMRI), while accounting for the presence of depressive symptoms. **Methods:** To this end, 50 young (20-35) and 80 healthy participants (60-85) will be enrolled to realize a temporal generalization task, with

short (1500ms) and long (3500ms) reference durations, during the simultaneous recording of the EEG-fMRI with a 128-electrode cap inside the MRI scanner (3T). Neuropsychological tests and questionnaires investigating the subjective experience of time on longer time scales will be administered at the end of the session. Depressive symptoms will be quantified by the Beck Depression Inventory and the Hospital Anxiety Depression Scale.

After source reconstruction (sLORETA) and artifacts correction, fronto-parietal theta-gamma synchrony will be correlated to the activity of the striatum and the functional connectivity of the fronto-striatal network. Results: We expect a lower precision and a more variable timing performance in the older adults group. The fronto-parietal theta-gamma coupling expected to be involved during the maintenance in memory of durations is expected to show a greater variability as well, together with a decreased activity of the stri-

tum in the older group. Conclusions: Results could expand current understanding of both the evolution of the neural bases of temporal processing with aging and the heterogeneity of aging effects across individuals by considering the intensity of depressive symptoms on temporal processing abilities.

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IMPROVING EARLY DIAGNOSIS OF NEURODEGENERATIVE DISEASES USING MEG-BASED MACHINE LEARNING IN THE BIOFIND DATASET

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Abstract

There is an ever-growing need for developing treatments for Alzheimer's disease (AD). Electrophysiological biomarkers could help achieve earlier diagnosis of AD and other dementias. In this study, we explored spectral magnetoencephalography (MEG) metrics and machine learning approaches for AD detection. We assessed the capacity of MEG to distinguish between patients with mild cognitive impairment (MCI) and healthy controls, and between stable MCI and patients who later developed AD dementia. We analyzed 323 resting-state MEG recordings from the BioFIND dataset (Vaghari et al., 2021), including 157 MCI patients and 166 healthy controls. 64 MCI patients evolved to AD dementia while 53 remained stable. We computed spectral power and covariance matrices using Morlet wavelets (Hipp et al 2012, Nat Neuro). We further analyzed classification performance of MEG metrics using models

based on Riemannian Geometry (Sabbagh et al 2020, NeuroImage). Baseline analyses of spectral power suggested a widespread increase of brain activity in lower frequencies (1-6Hz). This was most pronounced in parietal, temporal and occipital regions of the sensor array. AD converters showed a focal pattern of reduced spectral power in higher frequencies (> 12Hz) in parieto-occipital regions compared to non-converters. Effects remained significant after adjusting on confounds (site, sex, motion, education). Compared to baseline log-power features, the Riemannian features performed better to discriminate between MCI and controls when using the covariance matrices on frequencies ranging from 0.5Hz to 64 Hz (AUC = 0.82). Our results suggest that covariance-based features can bring additional value beyond classical spectral features.

APERIODIC CHARACTERISTICS OF ELECTROPHYSIOLOGICAL SIGNALS IN PARKINSON'S DISEASE DURING COGNITIVE ACTION CONTROL

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Abstract

Cognitive symptoms, including cognitive action control (CAC) alterations (suppressing an automatic behavior in favor of a controlled one), severely impair the quality of life of Parkinson's disease (PD) patients. In order to predict the risk of cognitive decline and improve patient care, a prerequisite is the identification of a signature derived from behavior and/or neuroimaging. In parallel to this, the aperiodic component of EEG (the so-called 1/f activity) has been recently linked to various pathologies and cognitive functions. Here, we aimed at describing the offset and exponent of the EEG power spectrum to test their potential relationship with PD-related behavioral changes during CAC. We recorded high-density EEG from 30 HC and 29 PD patients during a Simon task. We analyzed the task-related behavioral data in the light of the activation-suppression model and ex-

tracted aperiodic parameters using specparam at the scalp and source levels. We found behavioral alterations of CAC as well as higher offsets in PD patients in parieto-occipital brain areas but no significant difference regarding the exponent. Aperiodic parameters were related to the execution of the task shown by significant changes between resting-state, pre-stimulus and post-stimulus periods. However, no correlation between behavior and EEG aperiodic parameters was evidenced. These findings describe changes in aperiodic parameters linked to task execution and PD, but for which our results suggest there was no link with PD-related behavioral changes. Therefore, this study underlines the importance of considering aperiodic activity in ongoing efforts of identifying a signature of PD cognitive deficits.

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HOW DOES MEMORY AGE IN ASD?

Marine Bessé^{1,2}, **Shasha Morel-Kohlmeier**², **Badiâa Bouazzaoui**¹, **Laurence Taconnat**¹, **Philippe Prévost**², **Laurie Tuller**², **Emmanuelle Houy-Durand**², **Zinaïda Tamiatto**^{1,2}, **Marie Gomot**², **Lucie Angel**¹

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Abstract

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental disorder that is characterized by restricted interests and stereotyped behaviors and alterations in social adaptation and communication. The few studies to date that have explored cognitive aging in autism reported contradictory results. Different hypotheses suggest that cognitive aging could either be accelerated, equivalent or slowed compared to neurotypical aging. Furthermore, there are no studies considering the mechanisms underlying this evolution. The aim of our study is to characterize the evolution of cognitive profiles in autism during aging and to study associated brain mechanisms. Sixty autistic adults and sixty control adults divided into three age groups (18-40; 40-60; 60-80 years-old) will participate in this study. Several questionnaires and cognitive tests will make it possible to investigate the evolution of processing speed, executive

functions and memory. An electrophysiological (EEG) task examining the effect of load on working memory will allow us to explore the underlying brain activity and to characterize the evolution of cognitive capacities in autism. Moreover, we will explore the hypothesis, proposed for typical aging, that brain reorganization mechanisms can have compensatory effects (Davis et al., 2007). We will be able to determine if autistic adults present a pattern of brain activity that could also be compensatory, or on the contrary no longer sufficient, especially in the oldest autistic individuals. We will present the methodology used and the first behavioral results in 20 neurotypical adults per age group.

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FREQUENCY-TAGGING EEG REVEALS INSTRUCTION-DRIVEN MAGNITUDE INTEGRATION USING THE NUMERICAL DISTANCE EFFECT

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Abstract

While humans can readily access the common magnitude of various numerical codes, such as digits or dot sets, it is not yet clear whether this integration occurs spontaneously or only when involved in explicit magnitude processing. Here, we addressed this question by examining the neural distance effect, a robust marker of magnitude processing, with a frequency-tagging approach. By varying the instructions given to participants, we compared spontaneous processing of visually presented numerosities to explicitly oriented processing of magnitude or parity. Electrophysiological responses were recorded while participants were viewing rapid sequences of a base numerosity presented at 6 Hz (e.g., "2") in randomly mixed codes: Arabic digits, number words, canonical dot patterns and canonical finger configurations. A

deviant numerosity either close (e.g., "3") or distant (e.g., "8") from the base was inserted every five items (i.e., at 6 Hz/5 = 1.2 Hz). We observed clear discrimination responses of the deviant numerosity despite its code variation. The distance effect (larger responses when base/deviant are distant than close) was present when participants were explicitly oriented to magnitude and parity, but not in simple viewing. We thus argue that abstract magnitude processing is only partly spontaneous. It indeed requires sufficient cognitive resources to be engaged in numerical processing, but occurs whatever semantic aspect of numbers is activated.

NEUROPHYSIOLOGICAL MARKERS OF MUSICAL AND VERBAL SHORT-TERM MEMORY: A FUNCTIONAL NEAR-INFRARED SPECTROSCOPY (fNIRS) STUDY

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Abstract

Musical and verbal short-term memory (STM) are key auditory processes that have been shown to be impaired in children with learning disorders. Neuroimaging studies have revealed the involvement of fronto-temporal networks in musical and verbal STM. To our knowledge, no study has explored a putative fronto-temporal impairment during musical and verbal STM in children with learning disorders. We used a fairly new technique, functional Near-Infrared Spectroscopy (fNIRS), ideal for investigating auditory cognition in special populations. We conducted two studies in a total of 40 healthy adults to assess frontal lobe

involvement in auditory STM. In the first one, we observed the preferential recruitment of inferior frontal gyrus (IFG) and dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (dlPFC) during encoding and maintenance of musical and verbal sequences with a Delayed Matching-To-Sample Task, when compared to a low-level perception task. In the second study, we tested a specific involvement of the dlPFC for the maintenance of higher memory loads. These two studies pave the way for a final ongoing study in which we explore the impairment of the same structures in children with learning disorders and age-matched or reading-level-matched controls.

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MEMORY RETENTION STRATEGIES: UNVEILING NEUROPHYSIOLOGICAL SIGNATURES THROUGH MACHINE LEARNING

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Abstract

Congenital amusia is a lifelong disorder of music perception and production. This rare condition arises from a deficit in short-term memory (STM) for pitch whereas verbal processing remains intact. Previous studies suggest an hemisphere-specific processing of verbal and musical information in STM, even if some mechanisms might be shared across materials. Recent fMRI studies have described alterations of the right fronto-temporal network responsible for the impaired pitch STM observed in amusics. However, the neural correlates specific to each component of STM remains poorly understood. In this study we investigated STM neural correlates in Magneto-encephalogra-

phy (MEG) using sequences of words and tones separated by a retention delay for ten amusic and ten control participants in a delayed-matching-to-sample task. Using multivariate pattern analysis classifiers along time, we were able to decode in each group (control or amusic) the material (musical or verbal) heard or maintained based on brain activity patterns on 275 MEG sensors. Patterns of features used to decode between material seems to indicate that during encoding and memory retrieval of verbal and musical information the two group relies on similar neural mechanisms.

However, during the retention periods the classifier seems to rely differently on sensors above the temporal lobes depending on the groups. To the best of our knowledge this is the first-time machine learning tools are used to investigate musical STM in human. Further investigation is needed to identify the nature of these mechanisms

(whether they are oscillatory or not), their temporal dynamics, and the specific brain regions involved.

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Posters

DAILY DYNAMICS OF RESTING-STATE EEG THETA AND GAMMA FLUCTUATIONS ARE ASSOCIATED WITH HEALTHY COGNITIVE TRAJECTORIES IN AGING

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Abstract

Healthy age-related cognitive changes are highly heterogeneous across individuals. Recent imaging studies (fMRI, EEG, MEG) have shown an increase in neuronal fluctuations during aging, that could be associated with cognitive performance (Uddin et al., 2020, Waschke et al., 2021). However, neuronal activity is a biological process modulated by circadian rhythms (Smith et al., 2007), and how these fluctuations evolve throughout the day remains unknown. Using a longitudinal approach, we aimed at investigating the circadian fluctuations of synchronized neuronal activity in order to clarify their prognostic value for cognitive trajectories in healthy aging. We analyzed cognitive and electrophysiological data (5 resting EEG sessions, recorded on the same day at 10:00, 16:00, 20:00, 22:00, and 1:00) of 101 healthy participants aged 50-69 years. We calculated brain synchronization

fluctuations of distant regions (standard deviation of the Phase Lag Index) for each recording session and in the five frequency bands delta, theta, alpha, beta, and gamma, to which we correlated the participants' burden of pathological markers Tau and β -amyloid as well as their cognitive scores obtained in the initial phase and following a 2-year longitudinal follow-up. The results show that at the day level, global theta and gamma fluctuation rates correlate with Tau marker measures as well as with executive scores obtained at baseline and after two years of follow-up. Circadian structure of neural fluctuations might thus contribute to explain the heterogeneity of individual cognitive trajectories and the mechanisms of maintenance and compensation during aging.

EFFECTS OF LONG-TERM MEDITATION PRACTICE ON SLEEP AND RESTING-STATE WAKEFULNESS IN AGING

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Abstract

Background EEG changes have been described during the practice of meditation (state) and at rest (trait) in long-term meditators, mainly using spectral power analyses. Besides, meditation practice may have a beneficial effect on sleep, but objective sleep data in long-term meditators are scarce and often limited to sleep architecture. Our aim was to better understand the effects of long-term meditation practice on both resting-state wakefulness and sleep in older adults. Methods Resting-state wakefulness EEG activity and polysomnography data were collected in 27 long-term meditators (mean age \pm SD: 70.7 \pm 5.0 years, 37% of women) and compared to meditation-naïve older controls (n=76 for wakefulness, n=47 for polysomnography, mean age \pm SD: 69.3 \pm 3.8 years, 61% of women). EEG power and complexity (Kolmogorov complexity and permutation entropy (PE)) analyses were performed during wakefulness, NREM and REM sleep. Between-group differences were

assessed using ANCOVAs for sleep architecture (controlling for age and sex), and cluster-based permutation approaches with Bonferroni-correction for EEG power and complexity. Results During wakefulness, long-term meditators showed lower delta power (pcluster=0.002) and higher delta PE (pcluster=0.009) compared to controls. Regarding sleep architecture, long-term meditators exhibited a longer sleep duration (p=0.023), reduced %N1 (p<0.001) and higher %N2 (p<0.001). They also had higher alpha power (pcluster=0.012) and theta PE (pcluster=0.004) during NREM sleep, and higher theta power (pcluster=0.011) during REM sleep. Conclusions Older adults with a long-term meditation practice exhibited patterns of EEG measures suggestive of preserved brain activity during wakefulness and greater sleep quality compared to meditation-naïve older adults.

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COGNITIVE AND NEURAL CORRELATES OF DREAM RECALL: RELATION BETWEEN MEMORY/ATTENTION AND DREAM RECALL FREQUENCY

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Abstract

Working memory and attention are two cognitive processes that have been hypothesized to be involved in dream recall frequency (DRF), but experimental arguments supporting this hypothesis are weak or sparse so far. In order to better understand how working memory and attention are involved in DRF, we used the MEMAT paradigm (an auditory working memory task under auditory distraction) in persons with a low (LR) and a

high (HR) DRF while recording their brain activity with magnetoencephalography (MEG). MEMAT is a modified auditory delayed-matching-to-sample task with distracting stimuli played in one ear alternatively with to-be-attended stimuli played in the other ear. LR showed better performance than HR, and this between-group difference increased when attentional distraction increased.

At the cerebral level, the better performance of LR was associated with a larger difference in late evoked activity between targets and distractors in LR compared to HR. In the challenging conditions of the MEMAT paradigm, LR are better at differentially processing relevant and irrelevant stimuli than HR, leading to better resistance to distraction. These results confirm an association

between attentional processes and DRF while working memory difficulty did not impact performance differently in the two groups.

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MEASURING RESIDUAL CAPACITIES IN THE BLIND FIELD OF POST STROKE PATIENTS WITH CORTICAL BLINDNESS: A NOVEL METACOGNITIVE AND EEG APPROACH

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Abstract

Blindsight refers to the ability of some post-stroke patients to discriminate visual stimuli in cortically blind areas of their visual field despite having no associated awareness. This dissociation between perception and awareness exists along a spectrum (Derrien et al. 2022), whose nature and mechanisms remain unclear. To shed light on the neural underpinnings of such residual capacities, we developed a protocol which both assesses objective and subjective capacities in the cortically blinded field, and measures electrophysiological activity of subjects. In the passive condition, we record EEG activity during a closed-eye resting-state sequence and during passive observation of motion stimuli. The active condition is a motion detection and discrimination paradigm, in which objective capacities and level of subjective awareness are measured by gold-standard psychophysical measures (d' and m -ratio), thanks to our novel metacognitive scale. These data allow us to draw patients' full perceptual and neurophysiological profile. Furthermore, we explore the different neurophy-

siological signatures associated with our sample's different behavioural profiles. We compare these measures to the patients' intact field performance and that of age-matched controls, with stimulus difficulties ranging from consciousness threshold to completely salient. This study provides a comprehensive neurophysiological and behavioural assessment of the dissociation between capacities and conscious perception in cortical blindness. Its impact is two-fold; (1) a better understanding of the nature of the perceptual experience of cortically blind patients, notably to improve rehabilitation strategies and (2) a contribution to the neuroscience of consciousness by investigating neural mechanisms of visual capacities that operate independently of conscious access.

PREDICTING FMEG MANIFESTATIONS OF FETAL SPONTANEOUS NEURAL ACTIVITY USING PREMATURE EEG

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Abstract

Evaluation of normal and pathological fetal brain development is a very challenging task. Fetal magnetoencephalography (fMEG) has been developed to investigate brain activity at the earliest stage of development. The study of spontaneous activity remains challenging due to the complexity of the extraction and of the analysis of fetal brain signals. However, a large body of electroencephalography (EEG) studies has characterized the spontaneous neural activity in premature neonates at different gestational ages. In this study, 10 EEG recordings in preterm at 28 to 31 weeks gestational age (wGA) and 10 fMEG recordings at 34 to 37 wGA have been used with signal-to-signal translation (SST) to propose a transfer function for prediction of spontaneous neural activity in fMEG, based on our knowledge in premature EEG. Toward

this, fMEG data were filtered (0.5-25 Hz) and preprocessed using orthogonal projections to remove the cardiac activity of the mother and the fetus. Then, the bursts of spontaneous activity in fMEG and premature EEG were detected using the non-linear energy operator (NLEO) algorithm. Unpaired matrices consisting of 5s windows of bursts of activity in fMEG and EEG, pooled over all subjects, were used to train the SST. The detection for the premature EEG were accurate as confirmed through visual inspection by one clinician (FW). The performance of NLEO on fMEG was enhanced by modifying the parameters (notably the threshold) with the objective to have the minimum inter-burst intervals for SST. The results of SST in realizing the data transformation (EEG to fMEG) was visually inspected.

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SPECIFICATION OF ATTENTIONAL DEFICIT IN ATTENTION DEFICIT/HYPERACTIVITY DISORDER (ADHD)

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Abstract

Attention deficit/hyperactivity disorder (ADHD) is considered as one of the most common developmental disorders diagnosed in childhood. As the name implies, children and adolescents with ADHD are known to have attentional deficits, but what is less clear is what type of attentional processes are particularly affected. Indeed, attention is not a unitary phenomenon, but it is a multifaceted construct supported by multiple brain processes such as voluntary and involuntary attention. However, the different facets of attention

have been rarely simultaneously investigated in ADHD. The Competitive Attention Test developed by Bidet-Caulet and collaborators (2015) allows to study the balance between voluntary and involuntary attentional processes, and to simultaneously measure different facets of attention, such as sustained attention, voluntary attention orienting, distraction, attentional lapses, and impulsivity. This study aimed to specify the attentional deficits in children and adolescents with ADHD using the Competitive Attention Test.

The performance of children and adolescents with ADHD obtained during the competitive attention test are compared with those of healthy peers previously tested and included in a normative database. The comparison is performed both at the individual and group levels to highlight the atten-

tional specificities of each patient, as well as the common deficits among the group that could be used as behavioral markers of ADHD.

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A DEVELOPMENTAL PERSPECTIVE ON THE INFLUENCE OF AROUSAL ON AUDITORY ATTENTION

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Abstract

The control of attention requires a good balance between voluntary and involuntary attention. Especially during childhood, the ability to select relevant information in the environment and to resist irrelevant distraction is essential to ensure a proper learning. While we know that young children are more prone to distraction and present more difficulties to sustain attention over a long period, the developmental trajectories of those attentional components remain largely unknown. Distraction by unexpected auditory events often occurs in daily life of both children and adults. Although it has been shown that unexpected salient sounds impair task-performance, an increasing number of studies demonstrated that unexpected stimuli can be beneficial for the performance. Current theories attribute this beneficial effect to a transient increase in the arousal level, under the

control of the Locus Coeruleus – Norepinephrine (LC-NE) system. Animal studies suggest that an optimal performance would be reached for an intermediate level of tonic arousal, accompanied by high phasic bursts. Previous work in adults suggest that modulating the arousal level using music could impact attentional processes during a behavioral auditory task. The objective of the study was to investigate the impact of arousal on voluntary and involuntary attention in children and adults, using a 3-tone oddball paradigm. We modulated the tonic arousal by using calm and exciting music extracts, and exciting videos. We recorded behavioral responses (reaction times, response rates) and physiological parameters (skin conductance, pupil dilation, heart rate) in order to get insight into the effect of arousal on attention during childhood and adulthood.

NEURAL OSCILLATIONS AND SPEECH PROCESSING DURING THE FIRST MONTHS OF LIFE

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Abstract

Neural oscillations correspond to the synchronous activity generated by neuronal assemblies, which can be naturally coupled, or coupled by a common stimulus. In adults, delta (1-3 Hz), theta

(4-8 Hz), and low-gamma (25-35 Hz) oscillations support the simultaneous processing of phrasal, syllabic, and phonemic units in the speech signal, respectively.

However, it is unknown whether neural oscillations are biologically endowed building blocks of the neural architecture for speech processing from birth, or whether they require experience to emerge? Using electroencephalography, we investigate neural oscillations and their relationship with speech processing at the very beginning of life. To do so, we assessed neural oscillations in the newborn brain, when experience with the (extrauterine) speech signal is limited, and in the brain of 6-month-olds, once infants have gained (postnatal) experience with spoken language. We

revealed that delta and theta oscillations differ for rhythmically different languages, suggesting that these bands underlie newborns' universal ability to discriminate languages on the basis of rhythm. Additionally, higher theta activity during post-stimulus as compared to pre-stimulus rest suggests that stimulation after-effects are present from birth.

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ELECTROPHYSIOLOGICAL STUDY OF VISUAL STATISTICAL LEARNING IN PRE-SCHOOL ASD CHILDREN

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Abstract

There is a growing research interest in tracking individual performance in statistical learning tasks, primarily as a predictor of linguistic abilities. This is of particular importance in the field of autism, as approximately 30% of individuals with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) will not develop language over the course of their development. Indeed, individuals with autism spectrum disorder (ASD) have diagnostic impairments in domains, such as language, that are associated with ISL. However, it is not clear whether ASD individuals show specific ISL deficits. In this study, we investigated the electrophysiological correlates of visual statistical learning in young children with ASD using an event-related potential sequence learning paradigm. The experimental paradigm is a modified version of the task developed by Jeste et al. (2015) in which children view a centrally presented sequence of little monsters composed of

the random presentation of three pairs of items. On 10% of the trials, the predicted little monster is replaced by another to constitute the oddball condition. We will compare 50 children with ASD and 50 typically developing children. Based on Jeste et al. (2015), (1) we expect an increased in the N1 component: we should find a larger response in the « expected » condition compared to the oddball condition. (2) We expect a larger P300 component in the oddball condition. (3) We should find a larger Nc component in the « expected » condition than in the oddball condition.

SLEEP-DEPENDANT MEMORY CONSOLIDATION AND SLOW-WAVE SPINDLE COUPLING IN BREAST CANCER PATIENTS

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Abstract

Sleep is crucial for memory consolidation, involving the coupling between slow waves and sleep spindles. Breast cancer (BC) is associated with sleep difficulties, potentially impacting sleep-dependant memory consolidation through modifications of slow waves and spindles. BC is also associated with cortical modifications in frontal regions, that may impact slow wave generation. However, the relationship between memory consolidation during sleep and slow wave-spindle coupling in BC patients remains unclear. This study investigated the association between sleep-dependent memory consolidation and the sleep spindles/slow waves coupling in 35 BC patients not treated with chemotherapy (18 treated with radiotherapy and endocrine therapy (ET+), 17 treated with radiotherapy only (ET-) compared to 21 healthy controls (HC). Participants were matched in age and education levels. ANCOVA analyses revealed

lower slow wave density in frontal electrodes during sleep stage 3 for both patients' groups compared to HC (main group effects: $p < 0.05$ for F3, F4, F7, F8, $p < 0.01$ for FP1, FP2 and Fz). Moreover, multiple linear regression analyses showed a significant interaction between cancer status, but not endocrine therapy ($p = 0.90$), and the slow wave-spindle coupling index during sleep stage 2 ($p = 0.049$). Especially, higher coupling index was associated with lower memory scores in BC patients, suggesting disrupted memory consolidation during sleep. These findings emphasize the importance of considering the effects of BC on sleep architecture and its potential consequences on memory. Further research is needed to develop targeted interventions that optimize memory consolidation and cognitive outcomes in BC patients.

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ERPs TO SIMPLE, COMPLEX AND SOCIAL TACTILE STIMULATIONS

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Abstract

Research in tactile electrophysiology mostly relies on electrical or robots-delivered stimulations which prevent the investigation of the neurophysiological response to social aspect of touch despite its crucial role through lifetime. Therefore, this study aimed to compare event-related potentials (ERPs) generated by different tactile stimulations of the radial nerve. Three distinct protocols were designed, each depending on a different type of tactile stimulation of the hairy forearm: a tactor (10ms, Protocol 1), a brief touch with a finger or an object (10ms, Protocol 2), and a gentle stroke

(3cm/s) with a finger or an object (Protocol 3). Somatosensory ERPs on six adults were analyzed over C3 and Fz channels. The results revealed that Protocol 1 and 2 elicited comparable responses: distinctive P50, N70, P100, N130 and P200 components. Components up to P200 seem to be influenced by the stimulation type. In Protocol 3, an ultra-late potential occurring around 2 seconds after stimulation onset was sensitive to the nature of the stimulation: it peaked earlier for the stimulation by the finger than the object.

Overall, these findings suggest that brief tactile stimulations reliably evoke similar ERP, regardless of their type (simple, complex, social). Continuous stimulation (Protocol 3) evoked an ultra-late potential sensitive to the type of stimulation. These findings provide valuable insights into the reproducibility and differential effects of the nature of

the tactile stimulation, contributing to the development of accessible and user-friendly tools for tactile research.

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EARLY MATURATION OF THE NEURAL RESPONSE TO AUDITORY RHYTHM BEFORE THE AGE OF TERM: AN EEG STUDY IN PREMATURE NEWBORNS

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Abstract

The ability to extract the underlying steady beat from auditory rhythms and synchronization to periodicity in auditory streams is important for the development of language, and musical skills. While previous studies show neural responses to the hierarchical structures of rhythm and its selective enhancement to both beat and meter, the evolution of the neural response to rhythm remains unclear, notably during early development. We used high-resolution electroencephalography while sleeping premature newborns (n = 45, age range: 28–36 wGA) were exposed to an ambiguous duple/triple auditory rhythm in the incubator. We examined developmental changes of the neural tracking of rhythm in the form of steady-state evoked potentials (SSEPs), which reflect the neural energy at frequencies of interest. The amplitude of the spectra at meter related frequencies, and the spatial correlation distance (1- Pearson correlation coefficient) between individual

topographies and the grand-average topography were considered as the features of interest to be examined for correlation with age.

We replicated previous studies with significant neural responses at the beat and meter related frequencies. We found a significant positive correlation between the amplitude of the spectra at beat/duple meter frequencies and the gestational age at the time of the recording. We also observed a significant negative correlation between the spatial correlation distance and gestational age at both beat and duple meter frequencies.

This finding suggests that the neural tracking of rhythm becomes more refined and aligned to the rhythmic cues of the auditory stream in the course of the third trimester of gestation.

THE EFFECT OF AGEING ON THE ELECTROPHYSIOLOGICAL CORRELATES OF FAMILIARITY, RECOLLECTION AND MONITORING WHEN MENTAL TIME TRAVELLING TO THE DISTANT PAST AND FUTURE

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Abstract

The ability to mentally travel in time calls on both episodic and semantic memory. Previous studies have shown an episodic memory deficit with ageing, with a relatively intact autobiographical semantic memory (Abram et al., 2014). In this study, we focus on the effects of normal ageing on general semantic (GS), personal semantic (PS) and autobiographical episodic (EPI) representations of the distant past or future (more than 10 years away from the present moment). Twenty young (M_{age}=31.8 years, SD_{age}=3.8) and 22 elderly (M_{age}=67.9 years, SD_{age}=5.9) participants were asked to respond to positive personality traits being presented on a screen while their brain electrical activity was being recorded. Depending on the experimental condition, participants responded whether each trait was (or will be) valued by society (GS); it characterized (or

will characterize) them (PS); or whether it could evoke a specific event from their past (or future) (EPI). We assessed three event-related potentials to evaluate the impact of ageing (young vs old), temporal direction (past vs future) and type of representation (GS, PS, and EPI) in the old/new memory effects associated with familiarity (FN400), recollection (LPC) and post-retrieval/simulation monitoring (LFE). Younger participants showed a larger familiarity marker for personal semantics in comparison to general semantics, as well as greater recollection marker for past as opposed to future events in the episodic condition. Elderly participants, by contrast, only showed a modulation of the type of memory representation for the post-retrieval/simulation monitoring potential. The interpretations and implications of these results will be discussed.

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Local talks

BEYOND BRAIN WAVES: EMBRACING GOOD SCIENTIFIC PRACTICE IN MEG AND EEG

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Abstract

Good scientific practice in magnetoencephalography (MEG) and electroencephalography (EEG) is essential for ensuring reliable neuroscientific knowledge. This talk will provide an overview of good scientific practice in M/EEG research, emphasizing collaboration, openness, and reproducibility in neuroimaging. We will delve into community-developed resources and tools that support these practices throughout the research cycle. Covering study inception and planning, data acquisition, research data management with the importance of standards, data processing and analysis, and research dissemination going beyond

publication, this talk will address the multifaceted dimensions of M/EEG research. We will also reflect on more intangible aspects, including ethical implications and the responsibility scientists have in engaging with societal challenges. We believe this talk will prove beneficial for the CuttingEEG audience, encouraging a commitment to collaborative, open, and reproducible M/EEG research embracing good practice. Adhering to these principles can facilitate researchers to generate high-quality results, significantly contributing to advancing our understanding of the brain.

BRAIN OSCILLATIONS DURING RESTING STATE

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Abstract

Understanding neural oscillations is considered to be a critical step in deciphering the brain's communication code. However, despite their relevance, some basic questions have barely been addressed. For instance, it is unclear how much time different brain regions actually spend in oscillatory mode and what their characteristic frequencies are. To answer these questions, we used a large sample of resting-state magnetoencephalography recordings obtained from The Open MEG Archive (OMEGA). After reconstructing the signal in source space, we applied an unsupervised machine learning algorithm (k-means clustering) to extract typical spectral patterns in the signal. Our results show that different brain regions have

characteristic oscillatory frequencies, which are organized according to both a medial-to-lateral and a posterior-to-anterior gradient. We additionally applied a modification of the best oscillation detection method (fBOSC) on a voxel-by-voxel basis to identify moments of rhythmic activity over time. Interestingly, we show that the brain is far from being oscillating all the time, although there are marked differences between brain regions and rhythms. These findings open up new possibilities for extracting meaningful information from ongoing brain oscillatory activity.

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NEURAL TRACKING OF ENVIRONMENTAL TIME

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Abstract

Contemporary research in cognitive electrophysiology is predominantly centered on the phenomenon of «tracking»—the dynamic modulation of human brain activity while monitoring the temporal structure of events across various time scales. However, distinguishing this phenomenon from the conventional understanding of the brain «responding» to external stimuli remains ambiguous. In my presentation, I will delve into the methodological advancements offered by cutting-edge techniques designed to assess neural tracking. Firstly, I will elucidate the methodological and electrophysiological assumptions inherent in

each approach. Subsequently, I will demonstrate that these diverse methods possess the potential to offer complementary insights into the brain's sensitivity to external stimuli. Crucially, this may unveil evidence of qualitatively distinct neurocognitive mechanisms traditionally categorized under the overarching concept of tracking. In essence, these innovative methodologies herald a new era in the exploration of the neural foundations of human cognition.

NOVEL MULTIVARIATE METHODS TO TRACK FREQUENCY SHIFTS

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Abstract

Instantaneous and peak frequency changes in neural oscillations have been linked to many perceptual, motor, and cognitive processes. Yet, the majority of such studies have been performed in sensor space. Furthermore, both terms have been used interchangeably in the literature, although they do not reflect the same aspect of neural oscillations. In this talk, I discuss the rela-

tion between instantaneous frequency, peak frequency, and local frequency, the latter also known as spectral centroid. Furthermore, I propose and validate three different methods to extract source signals from multichannel data whose (instantaneous, local, or peak) frequency estimate is maximally correlated to an experimental variable of interest.

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CORTICAL TRACKING OF SPEECH IN YOUNG INFANTS AND ITS RELATION TO LANGUAGE DEVELOPMENT IN THE FIRST YEARS OF LIFE

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Abstract

During their first year of life, infants' capacity to process speech and extract meaningful linguistic information from the speech signal undergoes significant development. In recent years, cortical tracking of speech, which refers to the synchronisation between oscillatory cortical activity at different timescales and the information conveyed in the speech signal, has received attention in the field of infant language acquisition as a neural mechanism that plays a significant role in this development. In this talk, I will present an overview of this evidence and the methodological consi-

derations of studying cortical tracking of speech in young infant populations. I will argue that the study of cortical tracking of speech in young infants can lead to a better understanding of the influence that the complex interaction between neural maturation and growing language experience has on early speech processing, and to the identification of early neural indices of later individual language outcomes.

NEURAL OSCILLATIONS IN READING DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

The acquisition of reading relies on the development phonological representations learned from continuous speech. Accordingly, it has been proposed that atypical reading development such as dyslexia, stems from difficulties to disengage the attentional focus fast enough from critical events in speech, leading to poor phonological representations. In this talk, I will offer my view on how neural oscillations can inform such attentional theory of reading development. I will present four studies that support the importance of slow brain rhythms

generated in the right hemisphere in response to speech to develop adequate phonological and reading skills. In particular, our data suggest that these brain oscillations support the development of efficient attentional shifting abilities over speech, that will determine the quality of the information falling under the focus of attention and in turn, the quality of the phonological representations used when converting letters into sounds.

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PROTRACK: CORTICAL TRACKING OF PROSODY IN THE TYPICAL BRAIN AND AFTER STROKE

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Abstract

Rationale

Prosody is the complex of suprasegmental phenomena in speech and conveys both linguistic (linguistic prosody, LP) and affective (emotional prosody, EP) meanings. Cortical tracking of speech (CTS)-i.e., the degree of coherence between spoken language and neural signal-seems to be maximal in delta (0.5-4Hz) and theta (4-7Hz) bands over frontotemporal areas. Aphasia and aging populations have shown reduced CTS in the delta band (Kries et al., 2023; Gillis et al., 2023). We ask whether brain damaged and aging people (1) show altered CT of (differential) emotional and linguistic prosody, and, if so, (2) if this hinders the interpretation, (3) and correlates with other cogni-

tive/linguistic measures.

We will record magnetoencephalography signal while RH damaged, LH damaged, young (range 18-30) neurotypical, and patient-matched neurotypical people listen to 240 sentences spoken with 6 different intonations and match them to a facial expression in a forced-choice task. All subjects will also undergo cognitive/linguistic screenings and an MRI scan beforehand.

We will estimate CT using the mTRF function approach (Crosse et al., 2016) and fit linear mixed-effects models to evaluate the effect of the independent variables on the mTRF performance scores and accuracy in the experimental task.

Detailed material and methods

Participants

We will recruit 30 neurotypical young adults (age 18-30, YT), 30 people with post-stroke LH damage (LD), 30 people with post-stroke RH damage (RD), 30 neurotypical adults (OT) matched in age range and education with the clinical groups. All participants will undergo a linguistic and cognitive screen before the MEG experiment. An MRI scan will be also acquired for subsequent source reconstruction. All participants speak Castilian Spanish as their first language. The sample size was determined drawing on previous literature. In addition, we ran a power analysis using an online tool based on linear mixed models (https://jakewestfall.shinyapps.io/two_factor_power/), that is, the statistical approach we are planning to employ. We ran two separate analyses for the OT-Patients and the YT-OT comparisons. In the first case, we set the effect size $d=0.29$ (following Tomasello et al., 2022), number of participants=90, number of stimuli=160. Note that the actual number of stimuli is higher but since this model was designed for two conditions, we had to adapt our case (80 items X 3 conditions) to that scenario. We chose the fully crossed design option (CCC), in which all participants see all items in all conditions. The combination of these parameters returned a power of 0.932. In the second case, we applied the same parameters, except that the number of participants was now 60, obtaining a power estimate of 0.849. Imagining to consider each group of participants separately, and, thus, setting the number of participants to 30, we would obtain a power of 0.611.

Stimuli

240 pre-recorded Spanish sentences, equally distributed across 6 intonations: happy and angry (EP condition), question and request (LP condition), neutral and flat (baseline condition). All participants will listen to the same sentences although in a different randomized order. We also created a set of 6 facial expression pictures, expressing each of the aforementioned intonations. After each sentence the subject will have to choose which out of three pictures best represents the attitude of the speaker via button press.

Statistical analysis

Cortical tracking. In order to model the relationship between continuous auditory input and brain signals, we will employ Multivariate Temporal Response Function (mTRF) (Crosse et al., 2016).

For each participant, we will fit several models: acoustic models, including acoustic features (pitch, envelope) as predictors; linguistic models, taking (sub)word level information (e.g., phoneme onset, word surprisal, etc...) as independent variables; and a functional model, in which condition is the main factor. We will then compare the average mTRF prediction accuracy across groups (YT vs OT; OT vs RD/LD). Factor-response modelling. To model the relationship between independent and dependent variables (task accuracy and mTRF prediction accuracy) we will use linear mixed effect models (lmer package, R Core Team 2022). Our independent variables will be screening scores (cognitive and linguistic), acoustic features (pitch, envelope), experimental conditions, age, lesion location and size (for patients), and group, as fixed factors, and subjects and stimuli as random factors. In the OT vs YT comparison, we will also consider education as a predictor. We may also employ a Bayesian approach for further analyses.

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RHYTHM IN SPEECH: A BRIDGE TO MORPHO-SYNTAX ACQUISITION

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Abstract

Rationale

During language acquisition, infants display the remarkable ability to unravel which linguistic units are related to each other. However, infants' capacity to detect dependencies across units that are distant in time, e.g., UNbelieveABLE, remains poorly understood.

Speech constitutes an inherently rhythmic entity and evidence has consistently shown a link between language processing efficiency and language rhythm in both adults (Assaneo et al., 2019) and infants (Martinez-Alvarez et al., 2023). In humans, exposure to periodic acoustic stimuli induces beat perception (Povel & Essens, 1985). Underpinned by the phenomenon of neural entrainment (Large, 2008), beat perception enables organized processing of temporal events, fostering the detection of stimuli unfolding at specific long-distanced moments in time (Jones, 1976), as evidenced by its effect in improving perception and memory (Hilton & Goldwater, 2021).

The present study aims to investigate if beat perception in speech may play a crucial role in helping infants extract non-adjacent dependencies. To test this hypothesis, we designed rhythmic artificial languages (ALs) with syllable dependencies (AxC: A always predicts occurrence of C) positioned on the rhythmic beat (B+) or without beat-convergent dependencies (B-). A group of healthy adults (HA) and a group of 24-month-old children (CH) will be exposed to ALs as their brain activity will be recorded by means of EEG. After the exposure, the HA group will undergo an implicit learning test of the ALs. Applying the frequency-tagging approach, steady-state evoked potentials (SSEPs) relative to the frequency spectrum of the ALs will be extracted. Using a two-way, repeated measure ANOVA, we will test if amplitude of SSEPs at frequencies of interest (e.g., beat fre-

quency) is affected by presence/absence of rules (B+ vs B-) and if differences between groups (HA vs CH) are present. The learning performance of the HA group will be correlated with SSEPs amplitudes.

Detailed material and methods

ALs were built based on rhythmic acoustic stimuli used in Nozaradan et al., (2011, 2017), which are shown to consistently induce neural entrainment at their beat rate. Nozaradan's stimuli consist of repeating chains of twelve tone sounds and silences (e.g., "xxx s xxx s xx ss" – where 'x' is a tone and 's' a silence) at a rate of 5 Hz. If continuously listened for at least 30s, these patterns induce the automatic organization of events by groups of four (e.g., Xxx s Xxx s Xx ss – where X is a group-border tone), resulting into listener's perception of a beat on these boundaries.

To address the role of exogenous and endogenous attention in language processing, two of Nozaradan's rhythms will be used: (i) an *unsyncopated rhythm* (UnR: Xxx s Xxx s Xx ss), where tones occur on beat; (ii) a *syncopated rhythm*, (SynR: Xxxx S xxx S x ss) where beat mostly falls on silence events. In fact, while in UnR the presence of tones marks beat-moments generating exogenous cues, in SynR, beat perception is likely to occur endogenously since on-beat moments occur at silence positions.

Tone sounds from Nozaradan's stimuli were replaced with syllables (i.e., xxx s xxx s xx ss *gino-li s finoto s lino ss*). For both UnR and SynR two ALs were obtained. In the beat-rule condition (B+), non-adjacent contingencies (e.g., syllable PU-always predicts syllable KI) were placed on rhythmic beats (e.g., UnR: *PUlifo KI-gona fonu* / SynR: *PUGinoKI limiso fo*);

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Conversely, in only beat condition (B-) syllables were displaced without respecting any specific rule structure. This resulted into four ALs conditions: UnRB+, UnRB-, SynRB+, SynRB-. Each condition was built with different syllables to avoid carry over effects.

Syllables were obtained from Amazon Polly (AWS) voice synthesizer. Each syllable was stretched for a duration of 222ms and normalized for pitch (200Hz) and intensity (65dB) using Praat. ALs were then built through Python's Pydub library in Spyder environment to result into a 2.5 min stream of rhythmic language.

Sample size of HA and HC groups (N=25) is set following previous SSEP literature in similar populations (see Cantiani et al., 2022). Both groups will undergo passive exposure of each AL condition (RunB+, RunB-, RsynB+, RsynB-) while their brain activity is recorded using EEG. After exposure to each AL, only the HA group will undergo an implicit and explicit learning test for that specific AL. This constitutes a paradigm we have recently validated behaviorally. In the implicit test participants are asked to detect four alternating target syllables during a further 6.4 min exposure to the AL. Two of the targets are rule syllables, two are no-rule syllables. Response reaction times (RTs) will be measured. In the explicit test participants need to overtly recognize rule and rule-violation sequences of the AL. D-prime indexes will be ex-

tracted. Finally, the HA group will again undergo a 2.5 min passive exposure to the AL.

Using MatLab MIRtoolbox, EEG frequency-locked responses to the envelope of

ALs will be evaluated by analyzing SSEP amplitudes elicited at beat frequency and at non-beat specific frequencies. Using a two-way, repeated measure ANOVA, we will test if amplitude of SSEPs at frequencies of interest is affected by rhythm type (UnR vs SynR) and by presence/absence of rules (B+ vs B-). Possible differences between groups (HA vs CH) will be addressed, especially in regard to SSEPs patterns across UnR and SynR.

Concerning the HA behavioral data, a repeated measure ANOVA will compare RTs for the four target syllables. We will test different progressive decrease in the reaction times across syllables reflecting implicit learning. In the same way, d-prime indexes will be compared across conditions to assess presence of explicit learning of rules. Finally, we will correlate learning performance indexes of the subjects with their SSEP amplitudes during the first and second phase of ALs' exposure to determine the link between learning and these signals.

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EXAMINING MULTI-TALKER AND MULTI-ACCENT SWITCHING COSTS WITH CONCURRENT EEG AND PUPILLOMETRY

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Abstract

Rationale

BACKGROUND

Prior evidence indicates that the unique qualities of individual talkers' productions can complicate speech processing. For example, experiment blocks with multiple speakers (changing from trial-to-trial) tend to increase processing costs as compared to blocks with a single speaker (Choi et

al., 2018). Pupillometric evidence from McLaughlin and colleagues (2023) further indicates that the processing costs associated with accommodating talker variation are exacerbated when switching from a speaker with first language (L1) accent to a speaker with second language (L2) accent.

The processing costs associated with switching between multiple talkers (of L1 accent) have previously been examined with concurrent pupillometry and electroencephalography (EEG; Lim et al., 2021). Results of the EEG data indicated an increased P3a-like neural response in multi-talker blocks.

METHODS

Fifty L1 Spanish speakers will be recruited to participate. Stimuli will include 60 unique two-syllable items produced by six L1 Spanish talkers and six L2 English-accented talkers. Each trial will present six of the items (e.g., "balsa pavo dulce termo gorrón causar") in pseudorandom order.

The experiment will include 180 trials across five conditions (36 trials/condition): single-talker L1 accent, single-talker L2 accent, multi-talker L1 accent, multi-talker L2 accent, and multi-talker multi-accent.

ANALYSIS

The event-related potential (ERP) analysis will take time-locked data from presentation onset of each item. Curve-fitting linear mixed-effects regression (LMER) will be used to compare evoked responses across conditions. Alpha band power will be examined separately for the encoding and retention intervals with LMER. Pupil data will be examined with LMER.

Detailed material and methods

METHOD

1- Participants

Young adult (ages 18-35) L1 Spanish speakers will be recruited to participate. Selection criteria will recruit subjects with no known auditory or neurological impairments. We aim to collect data from 50. This sample size was selected based on sufficient power in prior work.

2- Materials

Sixty unique two-syllable items will be used in the task. Each trial will present six of the items (e.g., "balsa pavo dulce termo gorrón causar") in pseudorandom order. Words will never reoccur within

the same trial. The 60 items selected for use in the task all contain one of the six Spanish plosives (/b/, /p/, /d/, /t/, /g/, /k/) at onset, and do not have plosives elsewhere in the word. This characteristic leverages a difference in native-accented Spanish and English-accented Spanish. Voiced plosives (/b/, /d/, /g/) in Spanish are typically pre-voiced whereas in English-accented Spanish they have short voice onset times (VOTs); voiceless plosives (/p/, /t/, /k/) are also shifted more positively. Thus, the items used in the multi-accent block of the word span task should force listeners to actively accommodate accent differences. Six native (three female, three male) and six American English-accented (three female, three male) speakers will be recorded producing all 60 items. Stimuli will be processed with Adobe Audition to match in duration across talkers.

3- Procedure

Participants will complete an EEG session lasting approximately one hour and then complete a brief task to assess individual differences in working memory capacity. The experiment will include 180 trials across five conditions (36 trials/condition): single-talker L1 accent, single-talker L2 accent, multi-talker L1 accent, multi-talker L2 accent, and multi-talker multi-accent. In every trial, one word from each phonemic onset category will be re-presented. In the single-talker conditions, one of the 12 talkers will present all six words in a given trial; this results in six trials per individual talker. In the multi-talker conditions, each word will be presented by a different talker of a given accent. In the multi-accent condition, there will always be three words presented by three L1-accented talkers, and three words presented by three L2-accented talkers. Multi-accent trials will always present alternating L1 and L2 accent; half will begin with L1 accent, and half with L2 accent. Trials from each condition will be presented in random order.

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Matching the design of Lim et al. (2021), after the six items are presented (the "encoding" phase) there will be a five second "retention" phase. Participants will be instructed to rehearse the items internally without moving their lips or speaking aloud (to prevent artifacts in the EEG recordings). Next, a visual prompt will appear asking the participant what position one of the six items appeared in. For example, following the trial "balsa pavo dulce termo gorrón causar" the participant may be asked what position termo appeared in, to which the answer would be fourth.

During the encoding and retention phases, a fixation cross will be present on the screen. Participants will be instructed to reduce their blinking whenever the cross is present, to reduce artifacts in the EEG and loss of pupil data.

DATA ANALYSIS

The event-related potential (ERP) analysis will take time-locked data from presentation onset of each item. The first item of each trial will be excluded, because it contains no prior context (Lim et al., 2021). Curve-fitting linear mixed-effects regression will be used to compare evoked responses across conditions. Random intercepts of subjects and item (i.e., word), as well as random slopes of condition, will be included.

Alpha band power will be examined separately for the encoding and retention intervals with linear mixed-effects regression. Random intercepts of subjects and item (i.e., six word combination), as well as random slopes of condition, will be included.

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BRAIN SYNCHRONISATION DURING (GUIDED) COMMUNICATION IN BILINGUAL SITUATION

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Abstract

Rationale

The study explores brain synchronisation during communication between native speakers (monolingual situation) and between native and second language (L2) speakers (bilingual situation) to get a better picture of multilingual communication using an ecologically valid approach. Studies that have investigated neural mechanisms underlying human communication in natural situations suggest that fluent communication depends on the level of between-brain coupling (synchronisation) between interlocutors. In other words, communication is facilitated when the neural activity in the brain area(s) of the person who is speaking correlates with the activity in the same brain area(s) of the person who

is listening. Importantly, the between-brain coupling does not occur when the listener has difficulties extracting the meaning or structure of what is being said. Given that language processing in L2 is costlier than in first language (L1) and that native speakers have difficulty processing foreign-accented speech, we hypothesize that between-brain coupling may be reduced during conversation involving a native and an L2 speaker (bilingual situation). To investigate neural synchronisation between two brains, we will use electroencephalography (EEG) hyperscanning, a technique that allows recording the brain activity of two participants simultaneously.

Pairs of native-native speakers (monolingual situation) and of native-L2 speakers (bilingual situation) will alternate the roles of speaker and listener while interchanging their opinions about common topics (e.g., music, food). After pre-processing the EEG data, a nonparametric bootstrap-based t-test method will be used to compare interbrain synchronisation between the two communication situations. We will examine the level of synchronisation at the different frequency bands to detect the correlation of temporal and spatial patterns of inter-individual neural processes.

Detailed material and methods

The study has two main objectives:

- 1- To replicate and extend the few results available in the literature regarding the neural mechanisms underlying natural communication in monolingual situation;
- 2- To explore neural mechanisms underlying natural communication in bilingual situation.

To fulfil these objectives, we will use EEG hyperscanning to record L1 and L2 users' brain activity simultaneously during (guided) communication.

First, we will test a group of native-native pairs of speakers (thereafter, L1-L1 group) to 1) replicate Pérez and colleagues' (2017) experiment and 2) to obtain a basis to then compare native-L2 pairs of speakers (thereafter, L1-L2 group). We will follow the same experimental design, that is, participants will be seated in the same room but separated by a board (to avoid extra-linguistic, multimodal sensory communication, such as gestures, frowns, etc.). The experiment will start with a resting phase in which participants will remain silent to be included as a baseline. Then, the (guided) conversation will start with participants having to talk about 5 different common topics: sports, movies, animals, music and travel. Each topic will be prompted on a screen along with 6 questions provided as a guide. Participants will alternate the speaker and listener role (divided in 2 phases of 90 seconds for each 180 second trial). When playing the speaker's role, they will be asked to answer the questions as precisely as possible since they will be used at the end to assess

the degree of attention paid to the partner. After the EEG recording session, participants will be asked to complete a paper and pencil evaluation about the information provide by their partner about each topic. Each experiment will last approximately 2 hours.

Participants: In the L1-L1 group, we will test pairs of participants whose native language is Spanish. In the L1-L2 group, we will test pairs of native speakers of Spanish and L2 speakers who are high-proficient in Spanish (C1 in the European language framework). A power analysis with an $\alpha = .05$ and power = 0.80 determined a required sample size of 27 participants, hence, we will test 60 participants in each group (i.e., 30 pairs in each language situation). Participants will be between 18 and 35 years, and they will be matched for gender, handedness, linguistic and socio-economic background. The study has been approved by the ethical committee of Nebrija University (UNNE-2021-016).

Data analysis: We will examine the level of synchronisation in the following frequency bands: delta (1–4 Hz), theta (4–8 Hz), alpha (7.5–12.5 Hz) and beta (13–30 Hz). EEG preprocessing and speech processing (computing amplitude of speech envelope) will follow the same stages as in Perez et al. (2019). A nonparametric bootstrap-based t-test method will be used to compare interbrain synchronization and brain to speech synchronization in the monolingual situation (objective 1) and between language situations (objective 2).

Expected results: In the L1-L1 group, we expect to replicate Perez et al.'s (2017) results, i.e., enhanced synchronization between the EEG oscillatory activity of listeners and speakers in delta, theta, alpha and beta frequency bands. In the L1-L2 group, based on Pérez et al.'s results with native speakers set either in their L1 context (high proficient context; Pérez et al., 2017) or L2 context (low proficient context; Pérez et al., 2019), we can expect differences in the alpha band.

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THE IMPACT OF DUAL-LANGUAGE CONTEXT EXPOSURE ON INTERHEMISPHERIC CONNECTIVITY AND READING DEVELOPMENT IN BILINGUAL BASQUE-SPANISH CHILDREN

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Abstract

Rationale

Despite increasing numbers of children learning two languages from early on, research on the effects of bilingualism on reading development is scarce. The present study aims to determine whether learning two languages before learning to read could have an impact on interhemispheric connectivity, and in turn on reading development. We hypothesize that in some cases of early bilingualism, where the two languages are used in the same contexts (i.e., dual-language contexts), cooperative interhemispheric connectivity is boosted through the corpus callosum, which is a major determinant of reading acquisition. 96 Basque-Spanish bilingual children aged between 6 – 11 years will be recruited. Participants will present a large range of exposure to Basque and Spanish (i.e., dual-language versus single-language exposure). A passive version of the non-forced dichotic listening task will be administered under electroencephalography recording to measure functional interhemispheric connectivity.

In dichotic listening, smaller N1 latency differences have been related to increased left ear reports and higher microstructural integrity of the splenium. The N450 is usually observed at longer latencies in response to left ear compared to right ear reports. Therefore, smaller N1 and N450 latency differences are expected in bilinguals with a high degree of dual-language context exposure, compared to bilinguals exposed predominantly to single-language contexts. We further predict that interhemispheric connectivity efficiency, measured through ERPs latency differences, will be related to reading development. Finally, effective causal directional interhemispheric connectivity of gamma-band responses originating from left hemisphere and right hemisphere regions of interest (temporo-parietal and frontal regions) will be computed, as they have been previously shown to predict left ear reports in dichotic listening and the integrity of the corpus callosum.

DEVELOPMENTAL TRAJECTORY OF CORTICAL TRACKING OF NATIVE AND NON-NATIVE SPEECH STIMULI IN MONOLINGUAL AND BILINGUAL INFANTS

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Abstract

Rationale

Infants rely on prosodic information to differentiate the language or languages present in their environment from other unfamiliar languages and to start segmenting native speech. This study investigates cortical tracking of speech - a neural mechanism potentially underlying this early ability. Cortical tracking refers to the synchronization between neural oscillations and the temporal structure of the speech envelope. We are specifically interested in cortical tracking of low-frequency prosodic information (at the delta, <3 Hz, and the theta, 4-8 Hz, bands). These frequency bands have been related to different levels of speech processing: delta corresponds to processing of rhythm and prosody at the phrasal and word levels, while theta has been related to finer-grain linguistic analysis, involving processing of syllable-level information in speech. Hence, we predict that infants will show efficient cortical tracking of speech at the delta band in the first months of life, reflecting early sensitivity to the rhythmic and prosodic structure of native and non-native speech. On the other hand, we expect cortical tracking at the theta band to increase throughout infants' first year of life, particularly in response to native speech, as infants accumulate greater language exposure and develop the ability to encode fine-grain prosodic and phonetic detail in their native language(s).

Material and methods

We are conducting a large-scale longitudinal study that assesses language development from 4 months to 7 years of age in 180 infants acquiring Spanish and/or Basque in a bilingual community. Here, we will report preliminary results (40 infants) for 4- and 7-month-assessments of infants' cortical tracking of speech. In this task, infants are presented with three prerecorded stories in Spanish and Basque (both syl-

lable-timed languages familiar to infants) and English (unfamiliar stress-timed language), while their neural activity is recorded using continuous electroencephalography (EEG). For each participant, information about the level of exposure to each language is collected using a parental questionnaire.

We will calculate coherence between the neural oscillatory activity and the speech envelope. The specific frequency ranges for each band will be determined by the rates at which stressed (delta band) and unstressed syllables (theta band) occur in the stimuli from each language (Spanish, Basque, and English).

Results and conclusion

At 4 months, we expect that infants will show cortical tracking of speech in response to all three languages, demonstrating language-general sensitivity to prosodic information in the speech signal. It is possible that higher coherence will be observed for the two familiar syllable-timed languages (Spanish and Basque) than the unfamiliar stress-timed language (English) as evidence for infants' growing familiarity with the prosodic patterns of the language(s) present in their environment. At 7 months, however, we expect an increase in theta, but not delta coherence, specifically for the language that infants encounter more often in their environment (familiar dominant language), followed by the familiar but non-dominant language, and followed by the unfamiliar non-native language. This results pattern will evidence the complex relation between the effects of neural maturation and accumulating language-specific experience on infants' developing ability to encode linguistic information from the auditory speech signal.

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EXPLORING THE OSCILLATORY PATTERNS OF EXOGENOUS ATTENTIONAL SELECTION AND PRIORITIZATION OF NOVEL STIMULUS-RESPONSE MAPPINGS HELD IN WM

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Abstract

Rationale

A previous set of behavioral studies from our lab – by using exogenous retro-cue paradigms that capitalize on complex working memory (WM) contents (stimulus-response (S-R) associations) – have provided compelling evidence that exogenous non-predictive retro-cues can select not only space, as it was traditionally considered, but also, associated complex and novel S-R bindings held in WM. Hence, the current aim (https://aspredicted.org/see_one.php) is to disentangle the neural and ocular patterns related to attentional orientation, and those related to the exogenous selection of WM contents to better understand the possible mechanisms through which exogenous attention selects and prioritizes WM contents. Here, we expect to replicate the previously found behavioral effect (faster reaction times (RTs) for cued vs. neutral), and we also expect to find a benefit from cued to neutral trials. Based on previous physiological data (Formica et al., 2021; Balestrieri et al., 2022; Beste et al., 2023), by performing time-frequency analyses, we expect to find alpha lateralization after cue presentation, for cued and uncued trials, since it should represent attentional orientation (backed by the microsaccades pattern). Also, central alpha should increase with the neutral cues, which appear in the fixation point and don't select any mappings (both S-R associations should be held in WM), compared to cued or uncued trials, implying a higher WM load. Last, an increase in theta is expected during lateralized cue presentation vs. when it is a centralized neutral cue, representing exogenous reactivation and retrieval of a specific event file. Further, theta should positively correlate with the behavioral pattern of benefits while alpha power should be independent of RTs. In fact, during target presentation, theta should be higher for uncued vs. cued trials, re-

presenting conflict between the reactivated event file and the target, and for neutral vs. cued trials, representing a higher load.

Material and methods

Participants performed a choice-reaction task embedded in an exogenous retro-cueing paradigm that capitalized on complex WM contents (S-R associations) while electrophysiological data as well as eye movements were being recorded. The task was composed of a total of 792 trials with breaks every 198 trials. The experimental design consisted of a within-subject factor with 3 levels: object cueing (target is the cued object vs. uncued object vs. non-selected target -neutral cue-, changes trial-by-trial). The collected sample was composed by 18 participants since we established to collect participants according to a sequential Bayes Factor approach (BF₁₀=.269) (see https://aspredicted.org/see_one.php). Nevertheless, after performing the accuracy filtering (error rate < 40%) the final sample for analyzing the behavioral data was of 17 participants (3 male, mean of age=24, SD=2.76). Up to date, only the behavioral analyses have been performed, the preprocessing and analyses of both EEG and eye tracking data are being currently run. The behavioral analyses included an analysis of deviance within a Generalized Linear Mixed Model (glmm) approach.

Results and conclusion

After performing the glmm model comparison, the best suited model was selected which included the random slope of cueing on the random factors of participant and trial. Within this model, the analyses of deviance revealed that the effect of cueing on RTs was not statistically significant [$X^2(2, N=17) = 1.401, p = 0.496$].

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Nevertheless, the planned eye movement and time-frequency analyses will still be carried out to see if they can provide some additional information. In that line, the time frequency analyses of encephalographic data for one participant provide some preliminary evidence of posterior alpha power during the cue presentation in all the conditions, and posterior theta during the presentation of the target. Nevertheless, it remains to be determined if there are any statistically significant

power differences between conditions in both alpha and theta. Since this data comes from only one participant and neither alpha lateralization analyses nor statistical cluster permutation tests have been performed, conclusions cannot be drawn until the pertinent analyses have been carried out.

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NEURAL CORRELATES OF BEHAVIORAL HABIT FORMATION, WITH REAL FOOD AS THE REWARD

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Abstract

Rationale

The way our brain reacts to food stimuli can lead to different dysregulated consummatory behaviors. The brain's reward circuit, which activates when we consume tasty, high-calorie foods, can lead to uncontrollable cravings and overeating, resembling the addictive behaviors associated with substance abuse. Therefore, understanding how our brains respond to highly palatable foods is crucial in addressing food addiction in obesity. In this context, behaviors aimed at obtaining rewards are believed to be initiated by motivation and reinforced through learning experiences. Once these behaviors are established, the anticipated outcome becomes the reinforcer. While numerous studies with non-human animals support these hypotheses, research involving human populations has been relatively scarce, especially when using real food as a reinforcer.

In the present study, we adapted the well-established Pavlovian-Instrumental Transfer (PIT) paradigm, typically used with rats, to investigate whether participants demonstrate increased motivation towards food stimuli that have been previously conditioned (CS+). Within the framework of Event-Related Potentials (ERPs), one of the com-

ponents most closely associated with reward anticipation is the Stimulus Preceding Negativity (SPN). Consequently, we examined this component throughout the two consecutive phases of the learning process, with a focus on the crucial third phase of the paradigm (the transfer phase), during which the reward is no longer presented, and extinction is expected to occur. Additionally, we collected behavioral data to determine whether they align with the psychophysiological findings. In summary, our primary objective in this preliminary study was to adapt a well-known paradigm used predominantly with rats for use with a group of healthy human subjects. Our aim was to explore the potential of this paradigm and methodology for use in a target group of individuals dealing with obesity.

Material and methods

Our PIT experiment had three phases. Firstly, participants underwent classical (Pavlovian) conditioning, where they learned associations between stimuli and food rewards (crispy snacks). This phase featured 2 images and 4 tones (2 tones per image). Each trial presented an image followed by a tone, creating 4 image-tone pairs.

Only one pair led to a fixed reward of «»snacks»» (1 unit), given in 70% of correct associations. This challenge aimed to engage participants. The phase included 40 trials per block (7 rewarded trials) across 5 blocks.

The second phase involved instrumental conditioning. Participants learned to respond to specific stimuli, receiving variable snack rewards (1 or 2 units) based on a baseline from a training task. It used a variant of the Go/NoGo task. Participants pressed a button as many times as possible within a 4-second window when a designated stimulus appeared (Go condition) and refrained from responding to the other stimulus (NoGo condition). The assignment of Go or NoGo stimuli (square or diamond shape) was randomized and balanced among participants. This phase comprised 40 trials per block and 5 blocks.

The final phase combined both conditioning tasks in a transfer task. Each trial began with the Pavlovian image and tone, followed by one of the instrumental figures superimposed. Participants, as in the instrumental phase, pressed a button as many times as possible within a 4-second window while the figure (square or diamond) was on the screen. We expected increased button presses when preceded by the Pavlovian conditioned pair (Cs+) compared to Cs-, akin to the classical PIT paradigm. Reward-related feedback was absent in this phase. This allowed us to study declining reward anticipation through blocks and the extinction process for CS+ versus CS- stimuli behaviorally (response rates and reaction times) and psychophysiological (SPN analysis). The transfer task featured 40 trials per block, across 5 blocks.

Results and conclusion

The preliminary data we have obtained confirm the successful adaptation of the typical paradigm used with rodents for use in the human population. As a result, we observed a larger Stimulus Preceding Negativity (SPN) during both the Pavlovian and instrumental learning phases in anticipation of rewarding feedback.

Specifically, a significantly extended SPN was observed between CS+ association stimuli and the presentation of reward feedback during the Pavlovian phase. Similarly, an equally prolonged SPN was observed in

anticipation of reward when participants responded correctly to a Go stimulus in the instrumental phase. Notably, we found a significant interaction between stimulus type (CS+/CS-) and block during the Pavlovian phase, indicating the progressive nature of the learning process associated with the motivation to obtain rewards. Additionally, a main effect of block emerged in the instrumental phase, further supporting the development of reward-related learning over time.

The results obtained in the transfer phase were equally noteworthy. Despite the absence of feedback or reinforcers, we observed a decrease in reward anticipation and a rapid devaluation of CS+ stimuli. Upon detailed analysis, significant differences between CS+ and CS- were primarily observed during the first block of this phase and within an early time window of the SPN component. These findings may be attributed to the rapid devaluation of conditioned stimuli, likely as a consequence of feedback suppression. Further in-depth analysis and data collection may shed light on other potential contributing factors.

The behavioral data, including reaction times (RT) and response rates, obtained in both the instrumental and transfer phases were consistent with the findings from the psychophysiological data. Participants exhibited faster responses and a higher number of responses when facing rewarded (or previously rewarded) trials, and their performance significantly improved as they progressed through blocks.

In summary, we conclude that the manipulation of stimuli and task conditions in the different phases was executed successfully. ERP data indicate that participants acquired knowledge of stimulus contingencies during the Pavlovian phase, with reward anticipation steadily increasing for these stimuli across blocks, mirroring the trends observed during the instrumental phase. The observed reward devaluation effect in the critical transfer phase lays the foundation for future investigations in populations of interest, such as individuals with obesity.

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MODULATION OF SUBCORTICAL CODING OF PERIODIC SOUNDS BY THE DEGREE OF CONTROL OVER SOUND PITCH PRODUCTION

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Abstract

Rationale

Humans exert exquisite control over the pitch of produced sounds. Pitch is deemed as the perceptual attribute of the repetition rate of a sound waveform which allows to differentiate between high and low sounds. Neural representation of pitch entails phase-locked neural firing to sound periodicity (temporal coding), as extensively supported by electro- and magneto-encephalography studies (M/EEG) showing that synchronized neural activity to perceived sound waveforms occurs at multiple temporal rates across the auditory domain (e.g., Frequency-Following Response, a sustained periodic event-related potential). Concurrently, a well-known brain feature is the ability to predict the sensory outcome of one's own action through the generation of forward models (e.g., corollary discharge), mainly observed as attenuated neural responses to self-generated stimuli. We here sought to reveal whether temporal coding of periodic sounds is affected by the degree of control over pitch modulation following sensory-motor learning. We collected EEG data from young participants during an audio-motor task consisting in matching target pitched-vowel sounds by controlling pitch-vowel production through a touchpad in two experimental conditions: 1) Constant (predictable, fixed touchpad's X/Y axes mapping for pitch/vowel); and 2) Random (unpredictable mapping variation). Behavioral performance was obtained by cross-correlating the target and the self-generated pitched-vowel sounds. Similarly, brain responses to sound periodicity were analyzed by cross-correlating EEG data and the envelope of the self-generated pitched-vowel sounds, an already established methodological approach. By means of behavioral and brain activity measures, we expected to observe that sensory-motor learning enhances task performance through increased predictability, and that this parallels a diminished re-

sources recruitment for the processing of auditory stimuli, specifically in regard to their temporal information

Material and methods

Data were collected from 11 subjects (7 females, between 18 and 38 y.o.). The paradigm design consisted of 16 trials (8 for each condition, alternated every 4 trials and counterbalanced across subjects) of 6 minutes each (1h40m total). In each trial, participants had to match target pitched-vowel sounds (changing every 3s) delivered in one ear, with the pitched-vowel sounds they were generating by moving the finger in a mapped touchpad, delivered on the opposite ear (counterbalanced across conditions). Target and self-generated sounds were delivered alternately every 300ms, avoiding overlaps of neural responses. The stimuli (80 ± 5 dB) were generated with a modular synthesizer (VcV Rack®) connected to a touchpad. Both pitch (120-220Hz) and vowels (A-O) ranges were continuous. A total of 8 mappings were used. In Constant trials, participants had one fixed X/Y axes mapping for pitch/vowel (randomly assigned), which they learned in a 10-minute practice before the experiment. In Random trials, mappings changed every 18s. EEG data were collected with 68 channels caps, 5kHz sr. Audio data was recorded through Ableton (44100Hz sr). Data processing included extraction of pitch information from audio data (Praat®), synchronization audio-EEG, resampling EEG to 2kHz and filtering 1-300Hz; computing audio envelope, filtering 100-300Hz and resampling to match EEG data length; data epoching (250ms), re-referencing to average and bad epochs rejection; running ICA, cross-correlating ICs and audio envelope and keeping only ICs with significant xcorr values (permutation test).

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Finally, high-pass filtering (100Hz) and equating pitch variation across conditions. Xcorr values between target and produced sounds were used to assess performance. Xcorr values between EEG and self-generated audio envelope were calculated at each subject's Lmax (lag with maximum xcorr value in Cz), for all electrodes. Statistical testing included Shapiro Wilk, Paired T or Wilcoxon signed-ranked tests.

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SCIENCE, ART, AND TECHNOLOGY: INTEGRATING A PORTABLE EEG SYSTEM PROTOTYPE INTO AN ART EXHIBITION

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Abstract

Rationale

During the event SummerLab2023 held in Tabakalera, a centre for artistic and cultural creation in Donostia/San Sebastián, from August 29th to September 2nd, we undertook a project intending to integrate a portable 4-channels EEG prototype into an upcoming art exhibition scheduled for November 2023 within the Creative Impact Research Centre Europe (CIRCE) programme.

Our collaborative working group comprised four teams: (1) the neuroscientific team, responsible for framing the scientific and theoretical background; (2) the artistic team, dedicated to crafting creative and artistic details; (3) the design team, tasked with developing the EEG prototype helmet's design and aesthetics; (4) the hacking team, dedicated to the creation of the EEG signal recording system, including both hardware and software.

Our primary goals encompassed (i) the testing and refinement of the EEG system prototype to ensure reliable data collection; (ii) the definition of the key characteristics of the art exhibition, and the establishment of the EEG prototype's role within this context. Our goal is to carry out a proper experiment during the art exhibition to collect data in a real-life environment. Our scientific hypothesis challenges the prevailing notion that cognitive conflict is inherently

negative and aversive (Botvinick, 2007; Botvinick et al., 2001; Dreisbach & Fischer, 2012, 2015; Inzlicht et al., 2015) by positing the existence of a "sweet spot" where cognitive conflict is preferred and appreciated (Berlyne, 1957, 1960; La Pietra & Ruzzoli, 2023).

Material and methods

Each team successfully achieved the expected outcomes. The neuroscientific and artistic teams collaborated closely to customize and enhance the exhibition's specificities. Simultaneously, the EEG prototype helmet was designed and 3D-printed, while the hardware and software of the EEG system were developed using the Rust Programming Language (Nichols & Klabnik, 2019). The system was thereafter debugged, refined, and tested through a 5-minute eyes-closed resting state assessment to ensure enough reliability in EEG recordings in naturalistic settings.

Results and conclusion

This project highlights the feasibility and significance of fostering collaboration between the scientific, artistic, and technological communities. Such collaboration can prove advantageous in engaging the public, disseminating scientific knowledge, and perpetuating a virtuous cycle of testing and refining scientific hypotheses.

A NEURAL MARKER OF TOPOGRAPHICAL DISORIENTATION DURING REALISTIC SPATIAL NAVIGATION TASKS

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Abstract

Rationale

Topographical Disorientation (TD), the inability to find one's way in the surroundings, can become a serious problem, impairing autonomy, self-confidence, social life and physical activity. Indeed, TD tends to become a problem at older age, and is a functional signature at early stages of pathologies like Mild Cognitive Impairment or Alzheimer's Disease. Therapeutic interventions on patients severely affected by TD focus on training spatial navigation (SN) skills using several approaches. However, none of them has aimed at characterizing the dynamic aspect of SN: moment-to-moment variations in personal experience and brain activity. This precisely, is the aim of current project: to obtain a neural marker that can be used as a time-resolved signature of TD.

In order to obtain the neural marker of TD, we will focus on brain oscillatory activity, in particular power. Recent neurocognitive theories and experimental results highlight the relevance of the endogenous Theta rhythm in brain activity for memory and SN tasks in humans. In addition, Theta activity in medial-frontal cortex structures (e.g. the anterior cingulate cortex) has proven to be a good marker for conflict detection, cognitive control, and valuation of potential reward associated to control. We hypothesize that Theta activity can be used as a biomarker to flag for TD episodes during realistic, though controlled, navigation in Virtual Reality (VR) environments.

Material and methods

The experiment consists of one session in which subjects learn and then are tested on T-junction mazes (10 consecutive left/right turns each) in a virtual city. Behavioural and EEG data (64 electrodes, standard 10-20 positioning) are collected. The experimental session is divided in three stages: Path encoding, Distractor task and Path evaluation. In the Encoding stage, for

each maze subjects navigate once with visual orienting cues (indicating the correct path) and then they must complete the same maze without visual cues using a maximum of three attempts (runs). This will be repeated for 5 different mazes. Next, subjects perform a distractor task of approximately 15 minutes that consists on playing a card game (Timeline) with the experimenter. Finally, in the Evaluation stage, subjects navigate the 5 mazes again, without visual cues, until correct completion with a maximum of 5 attempts.

VR T-mazes have been generated using a custom-made maze generation tool based on Unity-3D that allows to render and display series of T-mazes with varying lengths, trajectories, and designs. Each of the mazes used in the experiment has a different sequence of left/right turns and, in addition, distinctive decorations and wall and pavement colours and materials.

The behavioural data collected are reaction time (time to decision at turns), the decision (right/left), and accuracy (correct/incorrect). We expect that slower decisions and errors will be representative of episodes of topographical disorientation. Therefore, we will compare the oscillatory activity (time resolved power) preceding slow decisions with the activity previous to fast decisions using two approaches: first a hypothesis driven approach focusing on Theta power in frontocentral channels, next using a data driven approach exploring the power at different frequency bands and across all the scalp.

Results and conclusion

Up to date, we have collected the data from 18 subjects (from 25 planned), therefore the results are preliminary and no interpretation will be provided until the sample is completed.

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USING VISUAL SENSORY ENTRAINMENT FOR MODULATING SPATIAL NAVIGATION IN VIRTUAL REALITY ENVIRONMENTS

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Abstract

Rationale

Spatial Navigation (SN) skills integrate several basic cognitive processes such as working and episodic memory, spatial positioning, sensorimotor coordination and, executive control, among others. SN abilities have huge inter-individual variability, although they often decline in elderly populations, especially in association to other age-related clinical conditions (MCI, AD) having a negative impact in the quality of life.

A number of studies in rodents and in humans have highlighted the relevance of oscillatory neural activity in the Theta range (4 to 7 Hz) for SN. Interestingly, Theta oscillations also correlate with the ability of maintaining and retrieving sequences of elements in working memory. Different theories relate Theta, SN and memory. For instance, Theta-Gamma Neural Code theory proposes that Theta cycle duration determines the number of items that can be held in working memory. This result is backed up by causal evidence from studies using brain stimulation and sensory entrainment. According to this theory the effect of Theta in working memory could impact SN. The aim of current study is to try and modulate human SN skills during navigation in realistic Virtual Reality (VR) environments (T-junction mazes) using sensory (visual) stimulation to entrain Theta oscillatory activity and evaluate the effects of rhythmic sensory stimulation both at short and long-term memory for navigation paths.

Material and methods

The experiment consists of two sessions. The first session is divided in two stages: Encoding and Short Term evaluation. In the Encoding stage, for each of

6 different mazes (8 T-junctions each) subjects will navigate the maze once with visual cues indicating the correct direction. Next, they will navigate the same maze without visual cues. In the Short-term evaluation stage, subjects will navigate the six encoded mazes again, without visual cues. The design includes mazes presented in 3 conditions (2 mazes per condition): Baseline, Theta (rhythmic modulations of the ambient illumination) and Control (arrhythmic modulations of the ambient illumination) in a randomized order. During this first session, EEG will be recorded concurrent to the task. In the second session, one day later, participants will navigate the 6 mazes learned in session 1 without visual cues interleaved with 3 filler new mazes, all presented in random order. Only behavioural data will be acquired in session 2. In all stages, subjects will navigate the mazes without visual cues until correct completion to a maximum of 3 attempts.

The analysis pipeline was registered previous to data analysis and includes behavioural analysis to assess the effect of Theta entrainment on SN, and EEG analysis to evaluate the effectiveness of sensory entrainment on neural responses. We will evaluate the effect of Theta entrainment on the number of correct decisions by means of two repeated measured ANOVAS (one of them comparing Theta entrainment with Baseline condition and the other one comparing Theta entrainment and Control stimulation) with factors Condition (Theta entrainment and Baseline or Theta entrainment and Control stimulation) and Attempt (first, second or third).

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In the EEG analysis, entrainment will be assessed in an occipital ROI by two methods: cross-coherence between entraining signal and EEG activity and inter-trial coherence between signals aligned to sensory stimulation.

Results and conclusion

We expect that subjects will have a better performance (more correct decisions) in the Theta entrainment condition compared both to Control stimulation and Baseline.

For the EEG data, we expect that the cross-coherence for Theta condition to be significant and si-

gnificantly larger than the cross-coherence for the Control condition. Also, we expect that the inter-trial coherence will be significantly higher in Theta condition than in Control condition.

Up to date, we have collected data from 27 of 30 planned subjects and therefore the results are preliminary and no interpretation will be provided until the sample is completed.

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AUDITORY, PUPILLARY, AND MOTOR RESPONSES TOWARDS HIGH TEMPORALLY MODULATED THREATENING SOUNDS SUGGEST THE EXISTENCE OF A FAST AUDITORY PATHWAY FOR EMOTION

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Abstract

Rationale

Neural models for emotional processing in vision suggest the existence of an ultrafast route to the amygdala, a critical structure for threat processing, which allows for fast detection of threat and subsequent adaptive behavior in humans. This fast route is known to involve magnocellular neurons mediating coarse visual processing, and to elicit response to threat, in amygdala and visual cortices, at earlier latencies than other slower, more fine-grained, pathways. In the auditory domain, animal evidence suggests the existence of a similar ultrafast route for threat detection, but it still remains unknown in humans. In this study, we investigated whether a similar fast, magnocellular pathway to the amygdala mediates responses to threat in the auditory system, based on evidence that magnocellular auditory neurons are particularly sensitive to high temporally modulated sounds. We used a fear conditioning task, which depends on amygdala response, while recording and analyzing pupillometry and electroencephalography (EEG) of 29 healthy participants.

Material and methods

Subjects had to behaviorally detect human voices, which were either paired (conditioned stimuli, CS+) or unpaired (non-conditioned stimuli, CS-) with an unpleasant loud white noise (unconditioned stimulus, US). Thus, CS+ voices acquired threatening significance, whereas CS- voices, or the same CS+ voices before conditioning, remained emotionally neutral. All voices were amplitude modulated at either high (40 Hz) or low (10 Hz) rates, aiming at differentially activating a fast (magnocellular) versus a slower (parvocellular) auditory pathway, respectively. We analyzed behavior (e.g. stimulus ratings, response time, stimulus detection), pupillary size, as well as electroencephalographic activity (middle latency auditory and oscillatory motor responses) for the conditions of interest. This allowed us to dissociate neural activity potentially elicited by each of the hypothesized auditory pathways.

Results and conclusion

Behavioral and pupillary results suggest that fear conditioning was effective, as participants were aware of the pairing (contingency) between the CS+ and the US, they rated CS+ as more negative and arousing than CS-, and their pupil dilations and response times at CS+ stimuli were also different than those to CS- stimuli. Moreover, threatening stimuli at high amplitude modulation rates (AM rates) elicited earlier auditory and pupil dilation responses than low AM rates. Finally, high versus low modulated conditioned (threatening) voices elicited stronger alpha power decrease, prior to the motor response, which correlated with response times to the voices. Taken together,

these results suggest that threatening stimuli presented at high AM rates elicit increased pupil and auditory cortical responses that are compatible with an ultrafast amygdala response, and subsequent fast modulatory inputs from the amygdala to the auditory cortex, as opposed to overall slower responses to threat at low AM rates. Thus, high amplitude modulated sounds may be an optimal tool to differentially activate and investigate a putative fast auditory route to the amygdala, similar to that in the visual system.

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NEURAL MARKERS OF FEEDBACK PROCESSING DURING THE TRANSITION TOWARDS SLEEP

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Abstract

Rationale

Fluctuations in arousal and alertness occur constantly and non-linearly across the day but are exacerbated during transitions toward strained states such as sleep or physical extenuation. These changes in arousal levels influence task performance, either enhancing or impeding specific cognitive processes. In a previous study, Ciria et al. (2021) presented a Probabilistic Reversal Learning (PRL) task to participants while they fell asleep, and showed that reduced arousal levels (i.e., drowsiness, compared to a state of attentive wakefulness) lead to diminished behavioural performance through increased decision volatility, suggesting that individuals may process negative feedback information differently based on their level of arousal. Here, we reanalyse the database of Ciria et al. (2021) at the behavioural (post-error slowing [higher reaction time after committing an error] and error rate) and neural (electroencepha-

lography [EEG] univariate time-frequency analysis) levels, to study whether reduced alertness modulates the processing of negative feedback.

Material and methods

In this study, a total of 50 easy-sleepers who were transitioning to sleep in a natural, non-linear fashion responded to the PRL task for 2 hours. In this task, participants learned to choose between two tones based on feedback. When they reached 90% accuracy, the rules switched, and occasionally (20% of the time) they received misleading feedback. Subsequently, each trial of each participant was classified as «wakefulness» or «drowsiness» by computing the theta:alpha ratio of the EEG signal from the pre-trial period, and behavioural (i.e., reaction times [RT] and errors) and EEG analysis (i.e., time-frequency) were conducted.

Results and conclusion

Here, we show how drowsiness results in heightened post-error slowing (i.e., extended reaction times following an error) and a higher error rate (i.e., reduced accuracy) when compared to a baseline state of wakefulness, indicating that feedback processing turns suboptimal while reward-seeking behaviour remains preserved during the wake-sleep transition. In line with behavioural results, time-frequency analyses of the EEG data show that the neural marker traditionally associated with the processing of contradictory information (e.g., unexpected negative feedback), increased power in the theta band at frontal-me-

dial electrodes, seems to disappear during drowsiness. Altogether, these findings suggest reduced alertness would be associated with a poorer processing of negative feedback, thereby resulting in maladaptive decision-making patterns that affect the ability to generate stable evidence-based strategies.

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READY, SET, GO! HOW DO NOVEL VERBAL INSTRUCTIONS INDUCE TASK-SPECIFIC NEURAL PATTERNS?

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Abstract

Rationale

There are multiple instances in everyday life where humans have to adapt and execute novel tasks, reaching optimal performance rapidly. This ability has been linked to cognitive control mechanisms that can generate and maintain task sets, with theoretical models separating proactive preparation from reactive implementation of control. Nonetheless, most of the previous literature characterizing these control mechanisms has focused on highly practiced tasks. Hence, the chain of processes mediating task set generation in more novel settings, like verbally instructed behavior, remains elusive to date. Furthermore, previous research with novel tasks has mainly focused on neuroimaging techniques that provide data with high spatial resolution, leaving the temporal domain behind task generation unexplored. To address this, the present study aimed to explore the temporal dynamics occurring during novel instructions encoding, preparation, and execution. We employed an instruction-following task,

with unique combinations of instructions for each trial, while recording electroencephalography data (EEG). First, we wanted to test whether the congruency of the targets affected performance on tasks with novel instructions, due to interference. We expected slower responses and higher error rates for incongruent trials after executing a repeated-measures ANOVA. Specifically for the electrophysiological data, our goal was to explore if novel instructions could activate content-specific neural patterns before and after target presentation. We performed machine learning classifiers (MVPA) to decode different dimensions relevant to the instructed task from brain activity and analyzed the stability of the neural patterns. We expected to find segregable activity patterns encoding for the relevant task dimensions, as well as their generalization across different stages of the trial, suggesting a common neural code between proactive and reactive control.

Material and methods

Behavioral and EEG data was collected from a total of 39 participants (mean age = 21.85; 26 women). The experiment consisted of two different tasks: a main instruction-following task and an additional 1-back localizer task (whose results are not included in this work). The design of the main task was a 2x2x2 within-subject design, where we manipulated: Task Demand (integration or selection of the information), Target Category (animate or inanimate images), and Target Relevant Feature (color or shape of the frame surrounding the targets). We generated a total of 512 novel verbal instructions with the three independent variables fully crossed. Instructions consisted of an "if... then" statement that indicated a condition about specific features of the two upcoming targets. After target presentation, participants had to indicate if the information given by the instructions was fulfilled or not by the targets. Experimental conditions were randomized through trials. To analyze the behavioral effect of target congruency on novel instructed tasks, we carried out two 2x2x2x2 repeated-measures ANOVA, one for Accuracy rates and another for Reaction Times, with our three task-relevant dimensions (Task Demand, Target Category, Target Relevant Feature) and Congruency. Next, for the electrophysiological analyses, we performed time-resolved Multivariate Pattern Analyses to address whether brain activity patterns encoded the three task dimensions manipulated by our variables. In every time point recorded, a classifier was used to distinguish between the two levels of each independent variable separately. Finally, we employed Temporal Generalization Analysis to examine the stability of the activity patterns coding the task dimensions through time. Separately for each independent variable, the classifier was trained on a given time point and tested on all time points of the epoch of interest, and this was repeated for the whole trial.

Results

and conclusion

The current study has provided evidence that novel, complex verbal instructions induce decodable task representations, both in a proactive and a reactive fashion.

First, regarding our behavioral hypothesis, incongruent trials had slower responses with higher error rates. This congruency effect was significantly larger in trials where stimuli information had to be integrated than in those where specific targets had to be selected. Regarding our MVPA analysis, the results show that neural patterns were sensitive to the content of the task-related dimensions, both proactively and reactively, with varying strengths and temporal dynamics according to the variable studied. Task demands, the most abstract dimension, generated sustained, generalizable patterns during the whole trial epoch. In opposition, the target category and the relevant feature, both more concrete dimensions, were coded more transiently and had a greater impact on activity patterns reactively, during target processing. Furthermore, we found a generalization of activity patterns within instruction encoding and preparation, and within task execution. Nonetheless, transfer between the two trial stages was scarcely observed, leaving uncertain the presence of a common neural code shared by proactive and reactive mechanisms. Overall, our findings suggest the presence of a hierarchy during novel task coding, with differences between abstract and more concrete task dimensions. Although its interaction with bottom-up processes remains an open question. Altogether, our findings highlight the flexibility of cognitive control in novel environments.

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Local workshops & tutorials

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INTRODUCTION TO MNE-PYTHON

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¹ *Instituto Cajal, CSIC, Spain*

INTRODUCTION TO FIELDTRIP

Jose Pérez-Navarro¹

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HEART EVOKED POTENTIALS

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CORTICAL TRACKING OF SPEECH

Mikel Lizarazu¹

¹ *Basque Center on Cognition Brain and Language, Spain*

TEMPORAL RESPONSE FUNCTIONS [cancelled]

Suhail Matar¹

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Dundee

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[Local symposia](#)[Link to live capture](#)

SCONe SYMPOSIUM

Symposium abstract

The Scottish-EU Critical Oscillations Network (SCONe) has invited local speakers who present their research on how stimulus-driven and endogenous brain rhythms, measured with EEG and MEG, advance our understanding of Human cognitive function.

FREQUENCY-SPECIFIC EEG ACTIVITY UNDERLIES BOTH STATIC AND DYNAMIC MEASURES OF METACOGNITION

Martina Kopcanova

University of Dundee, Scotland

Abstract

Metacognition allows us to introspect on our behaviour and decisions. To date, a clear understanding of the neurocomputational mechanisms underlying metacognition remains elusive. Previous studies have identified electroencephalography (EEG) signatures that predict model-free subjective performance, such as confidence ratings. However, it is currently unclear whether EEG activity relates to model-based measures of metacognition that offer additional insights into the latent processes underlying self-evaluation. Here, 40 participants performed a two-alternative forced-

choice visual discrimination task with confidence while their EEG was recorded. 1st-order and metacognitive performance were modelled with an extended signal detection theory framework as well as with a recently proposed dynamic evidence accumulation framework. Single-trial regression analyses revealed that stimulus-locked alpha/beta (8-30Hz) desynchronisation and low-frequency EEG activity predicted confidence ratings independently of accuracy and reaction times, extending previous work.

Confidence ratings were also linked to the aperiodic EEG component, which may represent a novel marker of subjective evaluation. Importantly, we found that the strength of the single-trial EEG-confidence relationship predicted participants' level of metacognitive efficiency, measured with two model-based measures (stationary: M-ratio, and dynamic: V-ratio). This effect was independent of first-order performance, including type-1 sensitivity and drift rate. These findings provide new insights into the neural mechanisms

of metacognition, suggesting it is underpinned by separable neural processes likely linked to excitability modulations in wide-spread neural networks. The signatures of these modulations can thus be considered candidate markers of suboptimal metacognitive insight in general and clinical populations.

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SSVEPS OF REAL-WORLD ENVIRONMENTS WITH LCD GLASSES

James Dowsett

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Abstract

The overall goal of my research is to develop a method for studying the brain during natural exploration of real-world environments and during real social interaction. We have developed a method using modified LCD glasses to provide high frequency visual flicker to create SSVEPs. The high signal to noise ratio allows a clean signal to be recovered despite movement artefacts. Participants do not need to be seated looking at a screen as the actual visual scene is the visual input. This method allows real world neuroscience in naturalistic settings with a minimal setup. Here we present data from a selection of experiments where we demonstrate this method with participants walk-

ing and standing in real world environments and making eye movements during naturalistic social interaction combined with eye-tracking. Different visual scenes can be accurately distinguished with SSVEPs from a short amount of data (approx. 5 seconds), demonstrating that this method has greater decoding accuracy than traditional resting EEG or ERP approaches. Decoding accuracy is frequency specific with certain flicker frequencies, for example the alpha band, resulting in greater information about the visual scene. This is potentially due to an interaction with the preferred frequency of endogenous neural oscillations.

THETA AND GAMMA ENTRAINMENT MODULATES MEMORY VIA AFFECTING THETA-PHASE-DEPENDENT AND SPIKE-TIMING-DEPENDENT PLASTICITY

Danying Wang

University of Glasgow, Scotland; University College London, UK

Abstract

Brain oscillations at theta and gamma frequencies have been linked with memory formation, which are dominant signals in the hippocampus synchronising the spike timing of neurons. Using rhythmic sensory stimulation (RSS), we show that exter-

nally synchronised auditory and visual inputs at 4 Hz leads to better memory than desynchronised inputs. A computational model that implements theta-phase-dependent and spike-timing-dependent plasticity (STDP)

mechanisms suggests that the effects are due to precise synchronisation which induces stronger synaptic modification. Further, we show that driving visual and auditory cortices at 37.5 Hz, cued recall with one modality is better when the corresponding modality leads the shortest delay (6.67 ms). This is consistent with STDP, which suggests that synaptic modification depends on spike timing between pre- and post-synaptic

neurons on the order of tens of milliseconds. Together, our findings provide evidence for theta-phase-dependent plasticity and STDP in human memory, which bridges the gap between in-vitro studies in animals and human memory behaviour.

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Posters

HEMISPHERIC BRAIN-RHYTHM ASYMMETRIES IN SPEECH IN-NOISE COMPREHENSION

Tanja Atanasova, Anne Keitel¹

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Abstract

Resting-state brain activity has the potential to index intrinsic features that might be related to behavioural performance. In this proof-of-concept study, we analysed intrinsic rhythmic region-specific brain activity in magnetoencephalography data and linked this to the performance of 20 participants in a speech-in-noise word comprehension task. All participants showed prominent theta and beta rhythms in the left and right Heschl gyrus. Participants with higher theta amplitudes in the left Heschl gyrus tended to understand speech-in-noise better than those with lower theta amplitudes. This could be linked to theta's role as a temporal reference to segment from the syllable unit to the consonant and vowel unit. Conversely, participants with lower individual beta amplitudes in the right Heschl Gyrus also showed

better speech comprehension. This effect could index how beta-band rhythms increase with task-related engagement. Both theta and beta effects were specific to the respective hemisphere. Our results suggest specific functional hemispheric asymmetries correlated to speech perception. Importantly, we show that individual differences in the rhythmic make-up of the brain are linked to differences in speech-in-noise comprehension.

IMPROVING COGNITION AND BRAIN FUNCTIONING IN OLD ADULTS USING A WORKING MEMORY (WM) TRAINING PAIRED WITH TRANSCRANIAL DIRECT CURRENT STIMULATION (TDCS): AN EEG STUDY

Esteban Leon-Correa, Stergios Makris, Alex Balani, Adam Qureshi, Dorothy Tse¹

¹ Edge Hill University, UK

Abstract

Ageing comes with many challenges such as significant depletion in physical and cognitive capacities, progressive neurodegeneration, and reduction of neuroplastic capacity. Consequently, elderly people are more liable to experience mild cognitive impairments (MCI) and neurodegenerative diseases such as dementias. While some studies have tried to address these problems by combining transcranial direct current stimulation (tDCS), a non-invasive method that delivers tiny electrical currents to the brain, with working memory (WM) training, these have not found consistent results. In the current study we employ a combination of multiple sessions of frontoparietal tDCS paired with WM training with

the objective of identifying whether tDCS causes significant improvements in memory and neural functioning in healthy elderly populations. This study explores learning effects, transfer (near- and far-) effects and long-lasting effects. Furthermore, we will analyse changes in spectral power and connectivity patterns resulting from the tDCS in the different stages of the memory process to explain behavioural outcomes. Finally, we will also investigate the role of individual differences in initial cognitive levels and in neural activity during task performance and resting state as potential predictors of the benefits of tDCS. The findings of this study will contribute to the optimization of tDCS protocols in elderly populations.

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EVALUATING FACTORS THAT DRIVE INFORMATION DECODING FROM EEG DATA

Lars Werne, Jasna Martinovic, Arno Onken¹

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Abstract

We simulate EEG recordings using the SEREE-GA framework, emulating different experimental conditions via specific parameter changes. Our overarching aim is to gain insight into the ability of commonly used EEG classifiers to decode specific differences in brain signals, which could aid the choice of classifiers or the interpretation of their performance in future experimental studies.

We assess the ability of a selection of models to distinguish between conditions that differ solely in terms of the peak amplitude of the stationary

P300 Event-Related Potential (ERP) component. EEGNet, a convolutional neural network (CNN) with a compact parameter set, is initially prone to overfitting, especially when recordings from a large number of electrodes are provided. Crucially, we find that this changes drastically when we - informed by ERP CORE, a non-synthetic EEG dataset - adjust our representation of background noise to affect different electrodes less independently, highlighting an aspect of noise plausibility that past simulation studies have not validated.

We further discover that adding another temporal convolution layer with a wide kernel to its architecture makes EEGNet less reliant on mixing information across electrodes, yielding a potential pointer for CNN design in scenarios when few electrodes are available.

Lastly, we demonstrate that condition-dependent latency shifts of a unique signal component may entail a characteristic bimodal increase in deco-

dability in the context of time-resolved multivariate pattern analysis, highlighting that spatial differences in activation pattern are not a necessary prerequisite for decodable EEG differences - relevant in light of specific conclusions of past work.

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AROUND THE CLOCK: PHYSIOLOGICAL MARKERS OF LAPSES IN ATTENTION DURING SUSTAINED TASK PERFORMANCE

Emily K Cunningham, Christian Keitel, Magdalena Ietswaart ¹

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Abstract

Too often still, people lose their lives or livelihoods in tragic accidents that have their root causes in lapses of attention. With the technology available today, the development of assistance systems which can detect attentional lapses and prevent such accidents should be viable. One way to achieve this is to use objective, physiological signals in which sudden changes may indicate an imminent lapse. Our study aims at identifying physiological markers that are maximally diagnostic and reliable. We simultaneously record electroencephalographic (EEG) activity and changes in pupil size as 60 participants partake in two modified versions of commonly used sustained attention tasks (the Mackworth Clock Task and the Sustained Attention to Response Task). In both versions, participants are required to sustain their attention to

the (monotonous) task and remain vigilant to (infrequent) target events which they should respond to. We predict that in the seconds preceding a miss – that is, when we assume that participants were not paying attention – we will observe an increase in activity in the alpha frequency band (8-14 Hz) and a decrease in pupil diameter, two markers previously associated with attentional focus and neuromodulatory arousal. We also expect to see these effects occur with increasing frequency over time as participants generally become fatigued. Additional analyses will target other measures such as the spectral slope of the EEG power spectrum that indexes excitability fluctuations, and how different measures can be combined to increase reliability. This lab-based experiment will inform future studies in more ecologically valid real-world settings.

THE COUPLING BETWEEN EYE ACTIVITY AND EMOTIONAL SPEECH

Sümeyye Şen Alpaly, Christian Keitel, Anne Keitel ¹

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Abstract

Speech tracking refers to the coupling between an internal rhythm and temporal regularities of speech acoustics. While speech tracking has often been studied in

relation to brain activity, recent evidence suggests that listeners' eye activity can also be attuned to tracking these regularities.

Importantly, ocular speech tracking has been found to be more robust for attended speech, suggesting that the process is modulated by attentional mechanisms. Here, we analysed simultaneously recorded eye tracking and electrooculogram (EOG) data to investigate eye responses during listening to affective naturalistic speech. Mutual information (MI) analysis reveals that the acoustic speech signal is tracked by eye movements in different frequency bands. When linking the strength of ocular speech tracking to arousal and valence ratings of speech material, we show

that MI values were modulated by higher arousal ratings. This finding is consistent with previous studies suggesting that emotionally salient stimuli are prioritised in attention and perception. Taken together, our results highlight the engagement of motor activity in auditory speech processing and reveal differential ocular speech tracking patterns in response to affective speech.

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INVESTIGATING GAZE DIFFERENCES BETWEEN AUTISTIC AND NEUROTYPICAL DURING EMOTION RECOGNITION OF ANTHROPOMORPHISED HUMAN-ANIMAL AND HUMAN FACIAL EXPRESSIONS

Teodora Mustanova, Bryony Buck¹

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Abstract

Neurotypical individuals use intuitive, implicit matching strategies in simple and complex facial emotion recognition tasks (FER). Research shows that people with Autistic Spectrum Disorder (ASD) often experience problems in simple emotion recognition but even greater difficulty with complex emotions due to their employed atypical, explicit strategies. This is due to the proposal that autistic individuals (AI) often demonstrate abnormal gaze patterns by spending less time attending to the eye region and more time on the mouth region on human faces compared to neurotypicals. However, emotion comprehension significantly improved when AI judge the mental states of animal or cartoon-like stimuli.

Therefore, this experiment measured how high-functioning people with autism recognize simple and complex facial emotions displayed on human versus anthropomorphic faces compared

to a control group. Participant's verbal IQ was matched, and their gaze fixations were recorded with a Tobii TX300 eye tracker. Both experimental and control groups saw pictures of six simple and six complex emotions displayed on both human and anthropomorphic agents and chose the appropriate emotion label. The data collection of this research is still in progress.

The outcomes from this paper are expected to demonstrate atypical gaze patterns i.e., decreased gaze to the eyes for AI when observing human faces compared to controls and improved emotion recognition when facial expressions are displayed on anthropomorphic faces.

With these findings, we would better understand the mechanisms underpinning facial expressions in ASD and whether interventions with regard to anthropomorphic agents could positively transform social interaction with such stimuli for AI.

THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN READING ABILITY AND NEURAL TRACKING OF SPEECH AND MUSIC

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Abstract

Music, speech, and how these relate to reading ability have so far been studied solely in the context of cognitive development of children. The purpose of this study was to analyse the relationship between neural tracking of speech and music with reading ability in adults. It was hypothesised that those who showed more accurate neural synchronisation to the envelope of the auditory stimuli (i.e., tracking) would also obtain more accurate scores in a word recognition task. Using a within-subjects design, participants (N=16; 19-26 years) completed an online word recognition task as a proxy for reading ability. This was followed by an electroencephalography (EEG) session to collect data on neural tracking ability. EEG was carried out to collect neural activity while participants listened to a short story and music track. Mutual information

was used to analyse the correspondence between the EEG signal and the envelope of the speech and music stimuli. Neural tracking to music specifically in the delta frequency band was found to predict word recognition performance. Tracking of speech was also associated with word recognition performance in various frequency bands and brain regions. The results of this study suggest a relationship between neural tracking of speech and music with reading ability. As the ability to track music is influenced by musical training and experience, it establishes a connection between these and reading ability. The implications of this are numerous, first and foremost musical training could be beneficial to the development of reading skills in adults.

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THE EFFECTS OF INTRINSIC NEURAL OSCILLATION FREQUENCY ON MUSIC TEMPO PREFERENCE

Efstratios Koukouvini¹, Saara M. Varjopuro, Sarah C. Allen², Anne Keitel²

¹ *University of Glasgow, Scotland*; ² *University of Dundee, Scotland*

Abstract

Tempo preference has been widely documented in individual motor and perceptual functions. However, the mechanisms that guide music tempo preference remain undocumented. The current study investigates if biological factors in the form of intrinsic neuronal oscillations affect musical tempo preference. We hypothesise that the oscillatory peak in the beta band will be correlated to the individual tempo preference. Further exploratory analyses are carried out in the alpha and theta bands. Sixteen participants completed a 5-minute resting state EEG session to record the intrinsic neural oscillatory activity. To sample the individual tempo

preferences, participants completed 20 trials of a musical tempo selection task. The results showed that participants' individual theta rhythm peak positively predicted their preferred tempo. We also found that older participants preferred faster tempo. No relationship with intrinsic beta activity was found. The current study suggests that intrinsic neural theta activity might affect musical tempo preferences. A limitation of the current and past studies is a restricted sample size, calling for larger scale studies to be conducted for more robust effects.

SUPERIOR DISCRIMINATION OF IMAGE DISPLACEMENT DIRECTION ALONG THE HORIZONTAL MERIDIAN VERSUS VERTICAL MERIDIAN

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¹ University of Dundee, Scotland ; ² University of Glasgow, Scotland

Abstract

During steady gaze fixation, visual perception is not homogeneous throughout the visual field. Performance is better along the horizontal meridian compared to the vertical meridian, and in the lower compared to the upper visual field. Thus, visual perception is directionally dependent (anisotropic). These findings are coupled with cortical magnification anisotropies in primary visual cortex. However, in real life, eye movements occur continuously, with visual perception resulting from a tight interplay between the visual as well as the oculomotor systems. The superior colliculus in the human midbrain is responsible for the planning and execution of eye movements, and interestingly, shows opposite cortical magnification anisotropies along the vertical meridian compared to primary visual cortex.

In the current study, we have measured performance across visual fields using a task that re-

quires the involvement of both visual and oculomotor systems - saccadic suppression of image displacement. Given the different cortical anisotropies observed between the visual and oculomotor systems, we were interested in the behavioural performance across visual fields in saccadic suppression of image displacement, especially along the upper-lower visual fields. Performance on the displacement task was better in the horizontal versus vertical meridian, however, we did not observe a difference between the lower and upper visual field. Despite the opposite cortical magnification anisotropies between the visual and oculomotor systems, this did not translate into observing opposite behavioural anisotropies along the vertical meridian. We speculate that the results might reflect a compensatory mechanism to counteract otherwise opposing trends induced by the different cortical magnification anisotropies.

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AN ELECTROPHYSIOLOGICAL INVESTIGATION OF THE NEURAL PATHWAYS OF EMOTION RECOGNITION

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Abstract

The literature on face processing describes the existence of two neural pathways involved in the recognition of different facial components (i.e., a dorsal pathway focused on changeable aspects of the face, such as facial movements produced during the display of emotional expressions; and a ventral pathway focused on non-changeable aspects of the face related to personal identity - Duchaine & Yovel, 2015). Since the identification of these neu-

roanatomical structures, a large number of studies have primarily focused on researching the individual functional characteristics of each processing pathway, but little is still known about the way these two interact or interfere amongst themselves.

By creating a paradigm designed to incorporate elements of both personal identity and emotion processing during the presentation of morphed facial stimuli, we aim to pinpoint

the time course and source localisation of the early event-related potentials (P100, N170) associated with both holistic and individual recognition of facial components using electroencephalography. Furthermore, the design of this study allows us to provide novel theoretical considerations for the field of face processing, as we can observe the extent to which the use of high-valence emotional expressions presented as primers for personal identity features can impact the successful recognition of faces. If conclusive, this research

will allow us to further explore the circumstances in which late event-related potentials can also be modulated by high-intensity emotional expressions and could provide a useful step towards advancing our understanding of face processing conditions such as prosopagnosia or alexithymia.

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COUPLING TACS, EEG AND EYE TRACKING TO FACILITATE ALPHA NEUROFEEDBACK

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University of Glasgow, Scotland

Abstract

The goal of neurofeedback is to establish self-control of brain activity by providing an ongoing reading of individual brain waves. However, it is often difficult for participants to achieve control over their own neural activity, presenting a major problem for transferring experimental results into therapeutic interventions.

One factor that may contribute to successful EEG neurofeedback control is the brain state prior to neurofeedback. Here we used Transcranial Alternating Current Stimulation (tACS) to modulate a participant's brain state prior to neurofeedback, whilst controlling for overt eye movements.

Twenty-six adults completed three sessions of tACS/neurofeedback training in a single blinded within-subjects design. Sessions were counterbalanced, with a combination of active/sham neurofeedback, and alpha (individual frequency) /40Hz tACS. We administered stimulation in a 15-minute block preceding four six-minute blocks of neuro-

feedback, and recorded reaction times in a typical Posner task at the beginning and end of each session.

We targeted the lateralised occipital-parietal alpha signal from a covert visual-spatial attention paradigm during both stimulation and neurofeedback. Eye tracking was used to ensure fixation was maintained during the covert attention task.

Behaviourally, we observe the classic validity effect, as well as an overall decrease and response time along sessions. Behavioural measures were neither modulated by stimulation protocol nor neurofeedback type. While there are no significant behavioural results from our preliminary analysis, this study is the first to integrate tACS with alpha EEG neurofeedback and eye tracking. It provides a foundation for future research to investigate the integration of these technologies and opens the possibility of studying the concurrent interactions between brain activity, oculo-motor planning and behaviour.

MUSIC'S HARMONIOUS IMPACT ON NEURAL ENTRAINMENT, WORKING MEMORY, SPEECH PROCESSING, AND READING SKILLS IN YOUNG CHILDREN

Maria del Carmen Garcia de Soria Bazan ¹, Brian Mathias ¹, Anne Keitel ², Anastasia Klimovich-Gray ¹

¹ University of Aberdeen, Scotland ; ² University of Dundee, Scotland

Abstract

Working memory and phonological awareness are key components in a child's reading fluency and academic success. Both components can be facilitated by musical training, yet the cognitive mechanisms of such facilitation are unclear. This research aims to unravel the relationship between musical training and neural entrainment in shaping the cognitive abilities that facilitate memory and phonological skill relevant for reading in young children.

The project involves two cohorts of 6- to 8-year-old children: music learners actively engaged in music classes and non-music learners participating in alternative extracurricular activities. Three core research questions will be addressed:

First, I investigate whether music training enhances cortical synchrony to speech and music, thereby potentially improving speech segmentation and phonological awareness and subsequent reading skills. Second, I study whether musically-trained children outperform their non-music peers on a working me-

memory maintenance task and where these improvements are linked to specific oscillatory activity during resting-state connectivity.

In controlled lab sessions, I conduct language and reading assessments, working memory maintenance and tapping-to-metronome tasks, and EEG and ECG measurements. Online sessions include follow-up assessments for dyslexia and parent-reported questionnaires covering demographics, musical experiences at home, executive functions, and familial risk of dyslexia.

Through this series of studies, I aim to shed light on the complex interconnections between music training, working memory, speech processing, and neural entrainment in young children. Ultimately, these findings may contribute to the development of new and more effective early interventions and educational strategies, enriching the lives of young learners and promoting academic success.

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HOW PERCEPTUAL ANTICIPATIONS AFFECT MOVEMENT PERCEPTION: THE NEURAL CORRELATES OF ACTION PERCEPTION IN A SOCIAL CONTEXT

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Abstract

Recent proposals argue that our understanding of other people's behaviour emerges from a predictive process that "paints" expectations about others' future behaviour onto ones' own perceptual system, in a process of Bayesian-like hypothesis testing revision. We will report data from an experimental paradigm in which people's perception of others' behaviour is guided by perceptual anticipa-

tions of their forthcoming actions. Participants saw hands reaching and withdrawing from objects, after hearing the actors state their intention to either "take" or "leave" this object. When people reported the perceived disappearance points of the hands, these judgments were biased towards the induced expectations. By performing single trial EEG analysis, we identified

pre-stimulus alpha activity over the occipital lobe as the selective carrier of the perceptual anticipations. We found that, on a trial-by-trial level, alpha activity over the occipital lobe is positively related to the effect perceptual anticipations have on action perception. We also found that the post-stimulus P2 and P3b ERP components were mediated by the mismatch of the visual input with the perceptual anticipations on a trial-by-trial level, with larger P3b amplitudes for incongruent trials. P3b was the only ERP component affected by the likelihood of

those mismatches and was also found to mediate the size of the perceptual judgment biases. P3b therefore reflects the updating of one's prior expectation by the sensory input. These findings argue for a framework in which prior expectations – and their revision through stimulus processing – shape social perception.

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SYSTEMATIC NON-STATIONARITIES IN EEG SPECTRAL MEASURES AND THEIR RELATIONSHIP TO VISUAL DISCRIMINATION PERFORMANCE

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Abstract

Rhythmic neural activity has been functionally linked to various cognitive processes. During task performance, frequency-specific EEG activity fluctuates spontaneously during baseline periods, and in a state- and stimulus-dependent manner. Recently, larger time-scale fluctuations (across >1h sessions) have been found, with alpha (8-13Hz) power and peak frequency changing with time-on-task. However, it is unclear to what extent time-on-task changes in EEG activity are limited to activity in the alpha band and whether they influence task performance. Thirty-six participants performed 900 trials of a two-alternative forced choice visual discrimination task with confidence ratings while their EEG was recorded. Pre- and post-stimulus spectral power (1-40Hz) and aperiodic (i.e., non-rhythmic) components were compared across blocks of the experimental session. Single-trial multiple regression analyses were used to investigate relationships with behavioural measures.

We found that time-on-task effects on rhythmic EEG activity were primarily localised to the alpha (and beta) band, with alpha power increasing and alpha frequency decreasing over time. These changes were driven by periodic and not aperiodic alterations. Importantly, alpha-band time-on-task effects mediated relationships between alpha activity and single-trial reaction times. However, time-on-task effects were dissociated from other EEG signatures of behavioural performance, including predictors of single-trial decision confidence. Our results provide evidence for the presence of separable time-varying and performance-related EEG signatures primarily in the alpha band. Hence, distinct functional properties exist for the same EEG signatures during task-performance, potentially underpinned by different neural networks.

M-RATIO OR METACOGNITIVE NOISE? COMPARING SIGNAL DETECTION THEORY AND THE HIERARCHICAL PROCESS MODEL AS MEASURES OF METACOGNITION

Lucas Gappmayr¹, Christopher Benwell¹

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Abstract

The accurate quantification of metacognitive processes is of high importance to progressing understanding of the mechanisms underlying every-day decision-making, learning, and psychiatric symptoms. Long hailed as the standard framework for quantifying metacognitive processes, the Signal-Detection Theory (SDT) approach has been shown to be problematic, particularly due to its lack of a direct, unbiased measure of under-/over-confidence (UOC) and for its failure to account for factors that have been found to distort its measure of metacognitive efficiency. Recently, howe-

ver, a process model purporting to improve on many of the problems with the SDT approach has been developed (Guggenmos, 2022). This study, then, aims to provide a rudimentary adjudication between the two frameworks by (A) correlating theoretically related parameters across models, and (B) comparing their ability to predict variables previously found or hypothesised to be affected by metacognitive processes. Analyses will be conducted across two secondary datasets to investigate whether results are consistent across different groups of participants.

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EXPLORING NON-VERBAL COMMUNICATION AND HEARING LOSS THROUGH FACIAL-ACTION UNITS IN FREE-FLOWING CONVERSATIONS

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Abstract

Everyday we participate in social interactions, adapting and adjusting to the situations and people we are communicating with and in. We do this often without discussion, altering our behaviour based on non-verbal cues that signal understanding or experiences of difficulty. For people with hearing impairment (PHI), communicating in social situations, such as in small-groups, can be difficult, causing PHI to rely more heavily on non-verbal communication (e.g., facial expressions) than their normal-hearing counterparts (PNH). Facial expressions comprise facial action units (fAUs), identifying specific groupings of muscle movements, such as raising of the eyebrows. Developments in computer-vision now allow fAUs to be extracted from 2D recordings of

the face, enabling non-invasive examination of facial expressions during free-flowing conversations.

To compare the type and frequency of fAUs made by PHI compared to PNH in small-group conversations, 18 groups of four participants (2PHI, 2PNH -age matched) were recorded holding six conversations in differing audio environments. fAUs were examined in relation to listening ability and noise environment. Preliminary analyses suggest that PHI generate more fAUs than PNH, especially during 'difficult' conversations, generating more frequent fAUs relating to difficulty (lowering of the inner eyebrows, narrowing of the eyes). This investigation is the first of its kind to investigate the generation of facial

expressions as a function of hearing ability during small-group conversations. Findings will further theoretical understanding surrounding facial expressions and hearing ability during conversation, with potential to inform patient care, clinical intervention and improved hearing-aid interventions.

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CONSUMER NEUROSCIENCE: SOUND BRANDING AND SUSCEPTIBILITY TO GLOBAL CONSUMER CULTURE

Ruta Cinite¹, Anne Keitel¹

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Abstract

Traditional marketing research focuses on behavioural data, while consumer neuroscience has the potential to uncover hidden and emotional processes. Previous research in this area is based on visual, not auditory stimuli, presenting a research gap. The present study proposes to investigate brain activity correlates associated with sound branding and susceptibility to global consumer culture using electroencephalography (EEG). The participants will be presented with auditory stimuli – jingles – while their EEG is recorded. Ad-

ditionally, they will be asked to rate their familiarity of the jingle on how much they like it, as well as asked to fill out a Susceptibility to Global Consumer Culture Questionnaire. We expect that distinct brain rhythms will differentiate between familiar/unfamiliar and liked/unliked jingles, and that consumer susceptibility might be reflected in brain rhythms. This study has the potential to provide insights into the cognitive processes underlying consumer behaviour in a globalised world.

IS MUSICIANS' NEURAL TRACKING OF SPEECH LINKED TO THEIR ENHANCED SPEECH IN NOISE PERCEPTION?

Zillah Broadman¹, Anne Keitel¹

¹ *University of Dundee, Scotland*

Abstract

Many studies have revealed a "Musicians' Benefit" in cognitive function (Benz et al., 2016) one of which being auditory processing (Braz et al., 2021). Consequently, musicians have been found to have a greater capacity to understand speech in noise (SIN) (Hennessy et al., 2022). One of the neural mechanisms behind (SIN) comprehension is the synchronisation of the brain's activity (cortical tracking) to the auditory signal, in this case the speech envelope (Riecke et al., 2018). There is mixed evidence suggesting musicians may cor-

rectly track speech better than non-musicians (Harding et al., 2019; Puschmann et al., 2021). No known attempts to explicitly investigate a link between musicians' enhanced performance on SIN tasks and cortical tracking of the speech envelope have been identified. This is important to establish as there is some debate as to which areas of auditory processing is improved in musicians. The current study aims to fill this gap and form a greater understanding of the mechanisms behind speech comprehension.

Local workshops & tutorials

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FIELDTRIP

Dr Philipp Ruhnau¹

¹ *University of Central Lancashire, UK*

MNE_PYTHON

Dr Anastasia Klimovich-Gray¹

¹ *University of Aberdeen, Scotland*

BAYESIAN PREVALENCE

Dr Robin Ince¹

¹ *University of Glasgow, Scotland*

MICROSTATE ANALYSIS

Dr Tanja Atanasova¹

¹ *University of Dundee, Scotland*

Frankfurt

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Local talks

DECODING BRAIN STATES WITH RHYTHMIC AND NON-RHYTHMIC FEATURES OF BRAIN SIGNALS

Joachim Gross

University of Münster

Abstract

Rhythms are a prominent feature of brain activity and they are known to change across brain states. However, traditional approaches typically rely on an assumption that is probably universally violated in real data - namely that underlying signals are stationary sinusoidal waveforms. In addition, the importance of aperiodic activity and waveform shape is becoming increasingly clear. Therefore, it seems advantageous to characterise

brain activity along many dimensions. Here, I report first results of a new project where we employ large-scale time-series phenotyping of MEG data. We use a large set of features to characterise source-localised MEG data and identify features that are informative for predicting age, changes in brain state or that follow cortical gradients. In all cases, these non-standard features outperformed traditional spectral measures.

SIGNAL AND NOISE IN NEURAL VARIABILITY

Julian Kosciessa

Radboud University, Nijmegen

Abstract

The brain is a dynamic system that is characterized by remarkably variable activity. Increasing evidence from neuroimaging experiments indicates that such variability is a key feature of human computational and behavioral flexibility. However, discriminating between parts of complex time series that are an informative sign of a latent neural

process, an instrumental signal within the brain, or uninformative "noise" remains a long-standing challenge in neuroscience. Historically, this has inspired algorithms that (over-)emphasize specific features such as periodic rhythms in EEG/MEG research. In contrast, emerging perspectives envision neuro-computational

noise as a signal of interest in its own right, calling for a more comprehensive appreciation of recorded fluctuations. In this talk, I will use research examples to highlight current perspectives with a focus on EEG/MEG research, illustrate principled approaches to practically decompose human brain variability, and point out ongoing theoretical and methodological challenges.

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DOING EVERYTHING YOUR MEG MANUFACTURER ADVISES YOU NOT TO DO – CLEANING MEG/EEG DATA FROM STIMULATION ARTIFACTS

Esther Florin

University of Düsseldorf

Abstract

Deep Brain Stimulation (DBS) is an invasive treatment option for neurological and psychiatric disorders which can improve the patient's quality of life to a great extent. Despite its clinically established use for e.g. Parkinson's disease, its underlying mechanism is still unclear. In order to better understand the mechanisms of DBS, its influence on whole brain activity needs to be investigated.

However, DBS produces large artifacts due to the applied current and the electrode itself in MEG and EEG data. To complicate things, these artifacts seem to differ between MEG and DBS systems. In this talk, I will present approaches to mitigate these artifacts to achieve insights into the mechanisms of deep brain stimulation.

DECODING SPEECH FROM INTRACRANIAL EEG

Christian Herff

Maastricht University

Abstract

Speech is our most natural way of communication and the loss of the ability to speak is therefore devastating to patients. A speech neuroprosthesis that directly reconstructs speech processes from neural activity could provide a new means of communications to these severely affected patients. In this presentation, I will present some approaches to reconstruct different representations of speech from intracranial recordings and highlight how they can be used to build a speech neuroprosthesis. The decoding of speech processes is particularly challenging, as not only the

neural, but also the target signal has complex, nonlinear dynamics. I will stress the use of interpretable machine learning models for this task to ensure that meaningful activity is decoded and scientific insights might be generated as a side product.

ENCODING MODELS AND HOW TO USE THEM - DECIPHERING THE CORTICAL REPRESENTATION OF CONTINUOUS SPEECH.

Yulia Oganian

University of Tübingen

Abstract

As speech evolves in time, auditory cortices track and respond to salient acoustic and linguistic features in the speech signal, a phenomenon known as speech tracking. Speech tracking is a prerequisite for successful mapping between the acoustic signal and linguistic categories. In my talk I will first discuss recent work using encoding models to characterize local cortical encoding of the spectro-temporal, phonemic and syllabic content of naturalistic speech throughout the entire hu-

man speech cortex. The results of this work show that speech representation in primary areas is dominated by spectro-temporal representations, whereas representations in associative speech cortex are geared towards the phonemic and syllabic structure of speech. I will then present a recent study where we used encoding models to dissociate between tracking of syllabic content and oscillatory entrainment to it, with no evidence of the latter.

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INFERRING CAUSALITY FROM NON-INVASIVE BRAIN STIMULATION IN COGNITIVE NEUROSCIENCE

Gesa Hartwigsen

University of Leipzig

Max Planck Institute for Human Cognitive and Brain Sciences Leipzig, Germany

Abstract

Across the last decades, there is increasing interest in the application of non-invasive brain stimulation (NIBS) to probe causality in cognitive neuroscience. NIBS techniques provide powerful tools to experimentally manipulate brain function and study the consequences at the behavioral and neural network level, thereby complementing correlative neuroimaging.

Many NIBS studies follow the simple logic of asking "is region X causally involved in task Y?" While this approach has made significant contributions to cognitive neuroscience, response modulation by NIBS appears to be more complex. I will provide examples for common approaches and pitfalls in the study of cognition with diffe-

rent NIBS protocols. Example studies suggest that many influencing factors which are usually ignored should be considered when explaining NIBS effects. Considering the interaction of internal and external factors will increase the current understanding of NIBS-induced modulation of brain function. Multimethod approaches provide insight into distributed network effects and the modulation beyond single brain areas.

Local workshops & tutorials

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INFERRING CIRCUIT MECHANISMS FROM NEURAL POWER SPECTRA: PARAMETERIZATION, SIMULATION, AND PROBABILISTIC MACHINE LEARNING

Richard Gao

University of Tübingen

Abstract

Brain signals are measurements from a messy bio-electro-chemical dynamical system and are often useful as correlates of behavior and cognition. But to further take advantage of them, we can leverage other experimental data and computational tools to decode physiological mechanisms underlying their fluctuations. This requires 3 ingredients—data analysis methods (parameterization), mechanistic models (simulation), and a way to link models to data (inference)—combined in a process known as inverse modeling or data assimilation.

Here, we will first cover the basics of Fourier(-based) analysis. Then, we will discuss spectral parameterization, i.e., FOOOF, as a data ana-

lysis tool to infer circuit properties from periodic and aperiodic components of neural power spectra, such as cellular and network timescales and excitation-inhibition balance. Lastly, following the same philosophy, we will discuss mechanistic circuit models with many more parameters, and explore how to use simulation-based inference (sbi) and probabilistic deep learning to perform model inference using real experimental data. Hands-on coding sessions with the associated python toolboxes is a central focus to facilitate analysis of your own data using spectral parameterization (with guidance on hyperparameter choices), as well as fitting your own models with sbi.

DEEP LEARNING FOR INTERPRETABLE EEG DECODING WITH BRAINDECODE

Robin Schirrmeister

University of Freiburg

Abstract

Deep neural networks are nowadays widely used for EEG decoding, reaching good decoding performance on a broad variety of decoding tasks. In this workshop, we will first show how to use the open-source EEG deep-learning toolbox Braindecode to train well-performing deep networks on EEG data. After such training, one challenge of gaining scientific knowledge from EEG-trained deep

networks is to understand their internal computations: What EEG features do they learn and how do they relate to the decoding targets? Therefore, in this workshop, we will also use interpretability methods for peeking into the learned functions of the trained networks to see what insights we can gain about the EEG signal from them.

EXTRACTING INTERPRETABLE PATTERNS FROM MULTIVARIATE TIME SERIES DATA USING GED

Rasa Gulbinaite

Netherlands Institute for Neuroscience

Abstract

Electrophysiological signals recorded at any spatial scale represent a mix of activity from different neural sources. This tutorial will focus on a supervised, as opposed to blind, source separation using generalized eigenvalue decomposition (GED). GED method extracts statistical (rather than anatomical) sources, which are expressed as linear weighted combinations of electrode time series (spatial filters). Supervision step involves data selection for implementing GED, as the method relies on the covariance matrices derived from different features of the data (e.g. narrow-band vs. broad-band activity; pre-sti-

mulus vs. post-stimulus period; two experimental conditions).

To build an intuition regarding the strengths (increased SNR, dimensionality reduction) and limitations of the method, we will apply it to several empirical EEG datasets (visual and tactile steady-state evoked potentials, cognitive control task). We will focus on practical aspects: The effects of noise, the amount of data used, covariance matrices derived from single vs. concatenated trials, matrix regularization, overfitting, and interpretation of GED results.

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MANAGE YOUR DATA WITH DATALAD: FROM LOCAL VERSION CONTROL TO DATA PUBLICATION

Julian Kosciessa ¹ & Adina Wagner ²

¹ *University, Nijmegen* ; ² *Jülich Research Center*

Abstract

Many open source software tools assist with the complex task of data management. This workshop introduces one of them, the data management and data publication tool DataLad (<https://www.data-lad.org>). If you have always wanted to get going with version control, are curious to find out how to use DataLad, or want to see simple workflows for data management routines, this workshop is

for you. You will learn about core concepts of research data management and how to implement them - from local version control for all parts of your research to data publication. With a focus on technical and conceptual aspects alike, the workshop aims to equip you with skills you could transfer to real-world data, with a mix of theoretical input and interactive hands-on applications.

NET2BRAIN: UNRAVELING COGNITIVE FUNCTIONALITY AS CAPTURED BY EEG USING PRE-TRAINED ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS

Saba Sadiya, Domenic Bersch, & Gemma Roig

Goethe University Frankfurt

Abstract

This workshop will introduce Net2Brain, an innovative toolbox that enables researchers to harness the power of deep learning for neuroimaging data

analysis. Unlike conventional toolboxes that offer limited functionalities focusing predominantly on supervised

image classification models, Net2Brain stands out with its comprehensive capability to extract activations from a remarkable variety of over 1000 ANNs trained for diverse vision-centric tasks across image and video datasets. Moreover, Net2Brain also includes multimodal, and language models. The toolbox also has a built in in-depth comparative analysis pipeline that employs advanced techniques such as representational similarity analysis (RSA), weighted RSA and encoding models. Facilitating in-depth brain-model comparison, both within specified regions of interest and across entire temporal and / or spatial spaces using searchlight searches and temporal neural pattern dynamics analysis. The user-friendly platform is open-source, complemented with brain data and end-to-end analysis examples

for immediate exploration. It also ensures streamlined incorporation of datasets and new models for evaluation. During the workshop, we will elucidate the capabilities of Net2Brain by presenting its application in recent studies. One of such studies utilizes EEG to explore how the human brain processes visual information to facilitate navigation planning in indoor scenes. The workshop will include a hands-on section during which you will be provided with interactive notebooks that run in your browser. Join us as we unravel the potential of Net2Brain in advancing cognitive computational neuroscience.

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LINEAR MIXED MODELING FOR M/EEG DATA

Benedikt Ehinger

University of Stuttgart

Abstract

Linear mixed models are versatile and increasingly popular in cognitive psychology to analyze behavioural datasets with within-subject trial-repetitions. Some brave researchers have already applied these hierarchical models to EEG data, typically on averaged space/time region of interest. In this 2 h tutorial, I will revisit some of the basics and intuitions behind mixed models and extend them to the mass-univariate EEG case: fitting mixed models to all time-point and channels using the `Unfold.jl` & `MixedModels.jl` toolboxes in JuliaLang. You will be provided with interactive notebooks that run in your browser.

We will explore together some implications and challenges of running such mass univariate LMMs: baseline periods, identifiability of random and item effects, and «usefulness».

I want to warn you though, I cannot provide a satisfactory answer to many of the issues that we will discuss in the workshop. My goal is rather to leave you with a sense of scientific curiosity, and the simulation- and analysis-tools to explore some of those issues yourself.

A DIFFERENT PERSPECTIVE ON OSCILLATIONS WITH EMPIRICAL MODE DECOMPOSITION

Andrew Quinn

University of Birmingham

Abstract

Neuronal oscillations (and any other kind...) can be split into separate components using the data-drive sifting algorithm to perform an Empirical Mode Decomposition. The resulting modes contain mono-component oscillations that retain much of the non-linear and dynamic properties of the original signal. We can then represent the spectral content of these modes using instantaneous frequency as an alternative to the Fourier transform. This alternative framework avoids some of the common pitfalls of Fourier analyses, such as time-frequency trade-off, and provi-

des a window onto challenging features such as rapid dynamics and waveform shape. Like all analyses the EMD algorithms are not perfect, but I argue that they provide a powerful complement to traditional approaches that is better optimised for approaching non-linear and non-stationary signals. I will illustrate these methods with an interactive demo using resting state EEG recordings from the LEMON dataset, MNE-Python and the EMD toolbox (<http://emd.rtfid.io/>).

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Posters

INVESTIGATING THE INFLUENCE OF SALIENCY ON FIXATION-RELATED POTENTIALS (FRPS)

Schepers J¹, Ehinger BV^{1,2}

¹ *University of Stuttgart, Institute for Visualisation and Interactive Systems, Stuttgart, Germany*; ² *University of Stuttgart, Stuttgart Center for Simulation Science, Stuttgart, Germany*

Abstract

To explore their environment, humans move their eyes to compensate for the drop in visual acuity from the fovea towards the periphery. This sequential sampling of fixation locations is not random but structured, i.e. some regions attract more fixations than others, which can be captured in so-called saliency maps and scanpath models. It is currently debated where, when, and if at all, saliency maps are computed and represented in the human brain. To add to this debate, we use coregistered EEG and Eye-tracking, to investigate whether there is a neural correlate of saliency. More specifically, we explore whether we can recover any effects of saliency on fixation-related

potentials (FRPs). We make use of a preexisting dataset with unrestricted viewing of natural scenes (Gert et al. 2022). Instead of a static saliency map, we use DeepGaze III (Kümmerer et al., 2022), a state-of-the-art saliency prediction model which combines traditional static saliency maps with the scanpath over previous fixations. This results in conditional saliency predictions for each fixation in a scanpath, and consequentially a saliency map which changes throughout the exploration of an image. To adjust for overlap in the EEG signal, we use linear deconvolution and regression-based FRP analysis via the Unfold.jl toolbox (Ehinger & Dimigen, 2019).

To account for non-linear confounds, we statistically adjust for several eye movement properties including fixation duration, position, and rank, as well as incoming saccade amplitude using generalized additive modelling (GAM). We mainly investigate three features of saliency: the probability of the current fixation, the probability of the next fixation, and the entropy of the fixation-wise saliency distribution. In future analyses, we are also interested in the change of entropy during the exploration of an image, as a measure of in-

formation uptake or surprisal. We want to highlight that our current analyses are explicitly exploratory in nature and have the purpose to give a first description of potential saliency effects in coregistered EEG/Eye-tracking, and to generate more specific hypotheses which can then be tested using a different data set.

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DEVIANCE DETECTION IN HUMAN AUDITORY BRAINSTEM RESPONSES

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¹ *Institute of Cell Biology and Neuroscience, Goethe University Frankfurt*

Abstract

Auditory deviance detection is the ability to detect unexpected sounds in a repetitive acoustic environment and is of major importance for survival. In the last decades, the investigation of this ability has grown more and more impactful and comprises multiple species, including humans. Although studies with human subjects are numerous, the main effects of human deviance detection focus on cortical activity with relatively long latencies compared to the stimulus onset. On the

contrary, studies with animals could show much earlier effects of deviance detection at several subcortical levels, including the brainstem. Here, we present data that demonstrates that very early, subthalamic effects of deviance detection are also present in the human brain, measurable by noninvasively recorded auditory brainstem responses (ABRs). The effects modify the ABRs in complex, stimulus-dependent ways.

PERCEPTUAL SENSITIVITY TO DEVIATIONS FROM ISOCHRONY IN COMPLEX SOUND SEQUENCES

Mock, C. M.^{1,2,3}, Oganian, Y.¹

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Abstract

Regularities in the temporal structure of a sequence of events can aid sensory processing by providing predictions about upcoming inputs. This hinges on the ability to perceive the onset timing of single events. Individuals' perception of event onsets is therefore a bottleneck for the predictive power of temporal structures. In auditory perception, previous studies found a mismatch between

acoustic onsets and perceptual onsets (P-Centers) for speech and non-speech complex sounds. P-Centers occur after the acoustic onset and are consistent across individual listeners, even though they do not align to any simple acoustic landmark within sounds. What remains unknown is how precisely P-Centers and their timing relative to a carrier

sequence are perceived by listeners, and whether this sensitivity depends on the acoustic complexity of the sound. To address this, we used an iterative perceptual adjustment paradigm (IAP). Participants ($n=9$) heard isochronous 4-beat sequences, followed by a target word (speech condition) or a fifth metronome beat (non-speech condition). Target word P-Centers were based on recordings of the targets, which were produced in-sync to a metronome. Target P-Centers were either aligned on-beat or offset by up to ± 120 ms. On each trial, participants first heard the sequence and then indicated on a slider by how much the target needed to be shifted to fall on beat. They then listened to the adjusted sequence and were offered to re-adjust the target position. This was repeated until the sequence sounded isochronous. We hypothesize that perceptual sensitivity to P-Center deviations is stable within sound conditions, i.e., independent of initial offset. Beyond that, we

make no assumptions about the direction of potential differences across conditions. Planned analyses will focus on the final distance of target P-Center to the beat, size and number of adjustments.

Preliminary results suggest that perceptual sensitivity to P-Center deviation is enhanced for simple non-speech sounds compared to speech, and that final distances depend on the initial offset. Interestingly, adjustment dynamics suggest that listeners incrementally approximate an internal P-Center representation. Planned follow-up studies will (1) validate sensitivity thresholds for P-Centers in the IAP as compared to a classical staircase approach and (2) elucidate the source of sensitivity differences for speech and non-speech sounds.

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THE ART OF BRAINWAVES: A SURVEY ON EVENT-RELATED POTENTIAL VISUALIZATION PRACTICES

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Abstract

The field of EEG research has witnessed significant advances, such as the integration of virtual reality and the emergence of mobile EEG setups. Virtual reality setups provide more naturalistic environments, and mobile EEG systems enable data collection in real-world settings. However, this paradigm shift adds new levels of complexity to the ERP visualization. Both technologies increase the dimensions of data and make visualization more complicated. In this context, the present study undertakes the exploration of ERP visualization practices in the face of these challenges. This study explores the user experience of a typical EEG practitioner attempting to visualize event-related potentials. We conducted a conditional online survey of approximately 200 respondents, including both novices and experts in the field of EEG.

The results shed light on the most used tools for ERP visualization, preferred tool features, most common visualization challenges, and awareness of issues related to color and error bars in graphs. Survey results indicated that Matlab-based tools such as EEGLAB, FieldTrip, and ERPLAB were most used, along with Python-based MNE and Brain Vision Analyzer. We found that several common problems were faced by practitioners while generating different ERP visualizations: adding uncertainty to line plots, styling and color in butterfly plots, channel highlighting in topoplots, and legibility and scaling in topographic arrays were among the common challenges. Researchers valued features such as publishable plots, reproducibility, and speed, and were skeptical of interactive data selection.

In addition, most respondents (82%) preferred positive voltages to be displayed up on the Cartesian coordinate system, contrary to the established standard. Many were unaware of color map issues, and 40% omitted error bars in published ERP plots. These findings underscore the need for awareness and education about visualization best practices. This study provides a comprehensive view of the current state of ERP visualization in the EEG community. By uncovering prevalent tools, elucidating preferred features, addressing

controversies, and assessing awareness of visualization issues, the study contributes to the advancement of ERP visualization practices. The findings of this study provide valuable guidance for the development of effective visualization tools and improved research practices.

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STATE-DEPENDENT EFFECTIVE CONNECTIVITY IN THE SPEECH PRODUCTION NETWORK – AN MEG STUDY

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Abstract

Neural oscillations shape functional networks. The speech production network synchronizes across theta, beta, and gamma bands. However, how this synchronization evolves from intention to speech stages remains unclear. To investigate the speech production network's coupling dynamics, we employed magnetoencephalography (MEG) during delayed sentence repetition. Our focus encompassed network dynamics due to task instructions, sentence listening, and short-term memory maintenance. MEG was acquired in 20 right-handed participants. Using a cue-target sentence repetition paradigm, to separate preparation from listening, memory maintenance and execution. With 600 pseudo-randomized trials, each featuring 100 three-word German sentences (~0.91s), we performed time-frequency analyses using Slepian multitapers (1–90 Hz), 1 Hz frequency resolution, and adaptive spectral smoothing (0.4 per frequency). Employing cluster-based permutation analyses ($p < 0.05$, cluster corrected) on sensor data, we assessed session and condition differences. A DICS beamformer was used to detect underlying sources. Non-parametric tests yielded consistent MEG sources ($p < 0.05$) in the inferior frontal gyrus (IFG), superior temporal sulcus (STS), and dorsal premotor cortex (dPMC).

Time courses were extracted (2–150 Hz) using a LCMV beamformer. Temporal resolved partial directed connectivity (TPDC, Muthuraman 2018) was computed between sources. Cluster-based permutation analyses between conditions, surrogate datasets (time information shuffled), and the four time-phases (baseline, preparation, listening, maintenance) were conducted ($p < 0.05$, cluster corrected). Alpha/beta power increased during motor preparation in the right IFG (receiver region in TPDC). This could reflect action suppression until the Go-cue. The speech production network was strongly coupled throughout all trial phases. During set-up and listening, connectivity between the SMA and the left STS increased relative to baseline in all bands. However, during memory maintenance, the direction of information flow changed from a top-down regime to a bottom-up information flow. This underscores the role of the SMA in the dynamic control of speech reproduction. During network set-up and sentence listening, the connectivity from right to left STS was suppressed relative to baseline. This supports a more relevant role of the left STS for speech reproduction as the connectivity from left to right STS was not suppressed.

DECOMPOSING NEUROPHYSIOLOGICAL UNDERPINNINGS OF AGE-RELATED COGNITIVE DECLINE IN VISUAL WORKING MEMORY

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Abstract

Understanding the neural mechanisms underlying age-related cognitive decline in working memory (WM) is crucial, given the present demographic change towards an aging society. The lateralized change detection paradigm is commonly used to study the neurophysiological basis of visual WM (VWM). Previous electroencephalographic (EEG) studies suggested that the largely investigated contralateral delay activity (CDA), a measure of lateralized slow wave potentials, may be insensitive to the age-related cognitive decline. Instead, recent evidence indicated that task-induced alpha power lateralization decreases in old age. Despite this, the relationship between alpha power lateralization and age-related VWM decline remains unknown, and recent studies have questioned the validity of findings on alpha power lateralization due to confounding factors of aperiodic signal components. Here, using a sample of 134 subjects, we have replicated a task-induced periodic alpha

power lateralization that declines with age after adjusting for the aperiodic signal component. We further found that the diminished alpha power lateralization causally mediated the age-related decline in VWM. Importantly, this missing link between task performance and alpha power lateralization could only be found when adjusting for biases of the aperiodic signal. Functionally, these findings suggest that age-related declines in VWM performance are driven by failures during active maintenance of VWM contents, particularly by the loss of the ability to prioritize relevant stimuli and suppress irrelevant distracting information throughout VWM retention. Concurrently, the CDA amplitudes remained stable across age groups, indicating a neural mechanism that is distinct from alpha power lateralization, and may functionally be related to preserved encoding or early WM maintenance processes.

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EFFECTS OF CARDIAC SIGNALS ON CORTICAL DYNAMICS AND VISUAL PERCEPTION: TOWARDS A MECHANISTIC THEORY

Online version

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Abstract

Heartbeat-evoked potential (HEP) is a specific type of event-related potential (ERP), arising in response to ventricular contractions of the heart. Corresponding neural signals arrive at the Central Autonomous Network (CAN) of the brain through visceral ascending pathways. Both the phase of the cardiac cycle and the HEP amplitude in the brain have been shown to modulate visual detection and discrimination thresholds. However, neurophysiological mechanisms to account for such effects are unknown. How do cardiac signals that arise in frontal and central brain regions exert effects on visual processing, which mainly takes place at distant locations from frontal and central brain regions? To answer this question, we will conduct concurrent ECG-EEG recordings while the subjects perform a visual detection or a binocular rivalry task. We will specifically test the hypothesis that electrical and/or mechanical signals which originate due to cardiac events (and are temporally marked by HEP) propagate towards visual cortex in the form of an electrophysiological traveling wave, eventually resetting the phase of alpha oscillations at the visual cortex to modulate our visual processing abilities. Since the signal-to-noise ratio is too low for us to measure absolute HEP amplitudes, relative HEP amplitudes will be compared between trials where the stimulus reaches and does not reach awareness during

the visual detection task. We will then look at the brain regions in which there are significant amplitude and/or phase differences at subsequent time windows to understand the propagation dynamics of neural signals induced by cardiac events. With the binocular rivalry paradigm, we will also test whether the cardiac cycle and HEP amplitudes modulate perceptual switches between two monocular stimuli. Such an effect would imply that cardiac signals also modulate the dynamics of interocular and pattern competition at the low- and high- level visual processing areas, respectively, which together account for the emergence of binocular rivalry. Lastly, we will include experimental blocks with desk-cycling and cold pressor challenges to increase the heart rate while subjects perform the aforementioned visual perception tasks. We will thus investigate whether the phase of the cardiac cycle and HEP amplitude still modulate visual perception in a similar fashion, accumulating further evidence towards a causal effect of cardiac signals on visual perception.

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NEURAL POPULATION DYNAMICS DURING OBJECT VISION REVEAL TWO TYPES OF REPRESENTATIONAL ECHOES ACROSS THE VISUAL SYSTEM

Online version

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² *Mortimer B. Zuckerman Mind Brain Behavior Institute, Columbia University, New York, USA*

Abstract

The human visual system enables us to recognize objects in our visual environment. For this, it relies on bottom-up, as well as intricate lateral and feedback connections that dynamically alter its neural population responses over time. Here we explore such dynamics while participants view natural objects in the MEG. We use time-resolved representational similarity analysis (RSA) on source-reconstructed regions across the whole brain and compute cross-temporal representational similarities. This enables us to investigate how the neural geometries change as they unfold in time. We observe two distinct oscillatory patterns that are prevalent across the visual hierarchy. First, we observe representational dynamics that repeat at an alpha rhythm (approx. 10Hz), reminiscent of echoes. These are in line with stimulus-unrelated traveling alpha waves across the cortex and indicate alpha's ongoing effects on cortical information processing in stimulus-evoked res-

ponses. Second, when excluding non-stimulus locked neural dynamics using cross-validation techniques, we observe repetitive representational patterns in the alpha and beta band (approx. 7-30 Hz) in which visual responses observed during stimulus presentation reverberate throughout the system. These findings illustrate two modes with which recurrent connectivity can impact ongoing visual computations. Once via ongoing oscillatory responses that add to the stimulus-related computations. Second via stimulus-locked representational echoes that are in line with a system that repetitively falls back to stimulus-related information, long after the bottom-up signals via stimulus input have disappeared.

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THE DEVELOPMENT OF EXCITATION-INHIBITION BALANCE RELATES TO SPEECH PROCESSING: EVIDENCE FROM EEG

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Abstract

Sensory processing relies on the collective interactions of billions of neurons, which communicate by sending either excitatory or inhibitory signals (Wu et al., 2011). In healthy brains, excitation and inhibition are in check (E/I balance; Rubenstein & Merzenich, 2003), meaning that cortical excitation in response to a stimulus is followed by proportional inhibition, allowing for the effective encoding and interpretation of sensory information (Oswald et al., 2006). Here, we test the relevance of E/I balance for auditory processing of speech. To include a maximal range of E/I balance, we analyze electroencephalography (EEG) data from both healthy children and a group of children with autism, where prior work, including our own (Plueckebaum et al., 2023), has observed E/I imbalance (Sohal &

Rubenstein, 2019). We examined the relationship between E/I balance and auditory processing of naturalistic speech for a final sample of 58 autistic children between 6 and 17 years of age and 64 non-autistic children matched by age, sex, and nonverbal-IQ. We employed a recently introduced functional measure of E/I balance based on the amplitude and temporal autocorrelation of alpha oscillations in resting-state EEG recordings (Bruining et al., 2020). Auditory speech processing was quantified through EEG encoding models (temporal response functions, TRFs; Crosse et al., 2016) using the speech spectrogram as predictor. In addition to the neural measures, individual differences in general autism symptoms were assessed for all children using

the Autism Spectrum Screening Questionnaire (ASSQ). We observed significant prediction accuracies to the spectral TRF model for both autistic and non-autistic groups (both $p < .001$), indicating speech processing for both groups. We also found a significant relationship between the developmental trajectory of E/I balance and spectral processing ($p = .048$). Specifically, we observed that better neural processing of speech was related to balanced E/I across childhood. In contrast, lower spectral processing responses were linked to an increase in relative excitation and thus E/I imba-

lance in older children. Critically, we find that the relationship between speech processing and E/I balance was significantly related to individual differences in general autism symptoms ($p = .03$). Children with more pronounced autism symptoms displayed a stronger relationship between E/I imbalances and speech processing than children with less pronoun.

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EXPLORING AFFECTIVE EXPERIENCES EVOKED BY MUSIC: A STUDY PLAN FOR NEUROPHYSIOLOGICAL DEEP DATASET MANYMUSIC 🎵

Seung-Goo Kim¹, **Pablo Alonso-Jiménez**², **Xavier Serra**², **Daniela Sammler**^{1,3}

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Abstract

Music can evoke strong emotions. But what in the music does evoke such emotions, and how does the brain transform musical sounds into emotional experiences? Previous theoretical and behavioral work identified both structural (Huron, 2005; Meyer, 1956; Gold et al., 2019) and expressive features in natural Western music (Juslin, 2013) to evoke emotions. Neuroimaging research, in turn, often presented artificially manipulated music, e.g., dissonant versions of short (~10 sec) music clips (Blood et al., 2001; Kim et al., 2017), or neglected the role of musical features overall (Salimpoor et al., 2011). The present study plans to leverage novel machine learning approaches to understand how structural and expressive features in natural music are represented in the brain and how they interact in evoking emotions. Therefore, we aim to simultaneously collect continuous ratings of emotional experiences and neuro-/psycho-physiological recordings (i.e., EEG, facial EMG, ECG, respiration, EGG, EDA) while participants are listening to natural music. To fully exploit the benefits of the machine learning approach, we aim to present a massive

number (>1,000) of musical pieces across various musical styles to a small number of subjects who will participate in repeated sessions ("within-subject" sampling). This approach follows novel trends in human neuroscience ("deep neuroimaging") that exploit the natural covariance of events in pictures or speech and the benefits of an extensive sampling of a limited number of subjects ("Narrative fMRI dataset" Naselaris et al., 2021; "Natural Scenes Dataset", Allen et al., 2022; "THINGS-data", Hebart et al., 2023) to establish predictive models of human experience with high ecological validity and replicability. Here, we initiate an open-access dataset for music-evoked emotions, entitled "ManyMusic 🎵". The project aims to establish a predictive model of musical emotions that explains how structural and expressive features in natural music turn from auditory representations into subjective affective experiences in the brain. The neuro-/psycho-physiological experiment described in the current abstract is part of a bigger project that further incorporates online behavioral ratings and fMRI.

THE FUNCTIONAL EXCITATION-INHIBITION BALANCE AND ITS RELATION TO LANGUAGE ABILITIES IN A DEVELOPMENTAL AUTISTIC AND ALLISTIC SAMPLE

Online version

- Global program
- A - G
- H - N
- O - Z

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Abstract

Imbalances between the brain's excitatory (E) and inhibitory (I) systems can lead to structural and functional cortical deviances in the brain which ultimately can alter information processing. These EI imbalances have been associated with various developmental conditions including autism. However, the developmental trajectory of these EI imbalances across childhood and adolescence and its relationship to autism traits is not well understood yet. In this study, we determined a functional measure of the EI balance (f-EIB) from resting-state electroencephalogram (EEG) recordings for 92 autistic children (6 to 17 years of age) and 100 age-, sex-, and nonverbal-IQ-matched allistic children. We related the developmental trajectory of f-EIB to behavioral assessments of autism traits and language ability. Our results revealed differential EI trajectories for the autistic compared to the allistic children. Importantly, the developmental trajectory of the f-EIB values related to individual language ability. In particular, elevated excitability in late childhood and early

adolescence was linked to decreased listening comprehension. Our findings therefore provide evidence against a general EI imbalance in autistic children when correcting for nonverbal IQ. Instead, we show that the developmental trajectory of the EI balance shares variance with autism trait development which is consistent with the proposal that the late development of inhibitory brain activity is a key substrate of autism traits.

DISTINCT FREQUENCY CHANNELS FOR MOTOR AND SENSORY PROCESSING IN SPEECH PRODUCTION

Online version

- Global program
- A - G
- H - N
- O - Z

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Abstract

Speech production involves the interaction between action and perception. The successful integration between motor output and sensory input ensures the fluency that we typically experience during speech production. Motor and sensory systems deal with different physical properties (i.e., muscle contraction and air vibration) that must be integrated at the brain level. Does the brain operate in a common space or in separate spaces to integrate motor and sensory information? Given the fast temporal rates that characterize speech production and perception, a fast neural mechanism is necessary for sensorimotor integration. One candidate mechanism to underwrite fast temporal aspects is neural oscillations. Frequency specific power modulations have been associated with both motor and sensory processing. Previous studies show that power desynchronization in alpha and beta frequency bands - collectively referred to as mu rhythms - is observed during motor execution. Mu rhythms are generated not only during overt but also during covert motor execution. The fact that mu rhythms are generated in the absence of movement and its sensory consequences suggests that they reflect neural computations independent from movement outcome. Mu rhythms generation has been localized to the motor and sensory cortices.

Previous studies have grouped alpha and beta frequency bands together under the mu rhythm umbrella. However, this grouping may fail to recognize the multifaceted nature of both alpha and beta frequency bands. In this study, we investigate the extent to which alpha and beta frequencies perform different functional operations during speech production. To this end, we used MEG to assess alpha and beta frequency band segregation in the time-frequency and spatial domain. Participants read syllables either covertly or overtly. Time-frequency analyses show robust alpha and beta desynchronization at the time of covert and overt speech production. Cluster-based permutation analysis across subjects shows a segregation of alpha and beta frequency bands into two different time-frequency clusters. The two clusters differ in timing: the beta cluster (200-300 ms) precedes the alpha cluster (400-500 ms). MEG source reconstruction shows that the beta cluster is localized in motor areas while the alpha cluster is localized in temporal areas. The results suggest that beta is primarily involved in motor planning and execution while alpha is primarily involved in sensory processing.

COMBINED EEG AND PUPILLOMETRY DATA IN AN AUDITORY ODDBALL PARADIGM

Online version

- Global program
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- H - N
- O - Z

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Abstract

Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a neurodevelopmental disorder characterized by a variety of behavioral and cognitive attentional symptoms. As an underlying mechanism, correlative studies indicate different sensory selectivity in ASD which may result from aberrant activity of the locus-coeruleus norepinephrine (LC-NE) system. However, this ASD model requires experimental validation. Here, we present a study design along with collected data to investigate the link between LC-NE activity and sensory selectivity using an oddball paradigm. N = 76 subjects aged 12–19 years completed a passive two-tone auditory oddball task, including a manipulation of LC-NE activity, while electroencephalography (EEG) and pupillometry were recorded simultaneously.

Mismatch Negativity (MMN), associated with auditory change detection, and the P3 event-related potential (ERP), an index of contextual updating, both indicate sensory selectivity. Pupil dilation serves as a proxy of LC-NE activity. For the statistical analysis, ERP data will be matched with pupil data on a subject-level. To validate the oddball effect, which has already been analyzed in the pupil data, MMN and P3 amplitude will be assessed in a linear mixed model (LMM), respectively. Further analyses will include group-specific effects of the LC-NE manipulation as well as associations of MMN and P3 with pupil dilation. These data may provide insights into the neural underpinnings of different sensory processing in ASD.

SENSORIMOTOR BCI PERFORMANCE DEPENDS ON SIGNAL-TO-NOISE RATIO BUT NOT PHASE SYNCHRONIZATION OF THE MU RHYTHM: A MULTIVERSE ANALYSIS OF LONGITUDINAL DATA

Online version

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Abstract

Serving as a channel for communication with locked-in patients or control of prostheses, motor imagery-based brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) decode imaginary movements from the recorded activity of the user's brain. However, many individuals remain unable to control the BCI, and the underlying mechanisms for such BCI inefficiency are not clear yet. Resting-state signal-to-noise ratio (SNR) of the mu rhythm as well as phase synchronization (PS) of the mu rhythm between sensorimotor brain regions were previously shown to correlate with the user's BCI performance. However, these predictors of performance were primarily evaluated in a single BCI session, while the longitudinal aspect remains rather uninvestigated. In addition, different pipelines and measures for estimation of PS in source space are used in the literature, further hindering the replicability of the results. In order to systematically address these issues, we performed an extensive validation of the relationship between pre-stimulus SNR, PS,

and session-wise BCI performance. We used a publicly available dataset of 62 human participants performing up to 11 sessions of BCI training and examined 24 pipelines for source space analysis as well as three PS measures. We ran a multiverse analysis to investigate whether the observed effects were robust to the selection of the pipeline. Our results show that SNR had a between- and within-subject effect on BCI performance for the majority of the pipelines. In contrast, the effect of phase synchronization on BCI performance was less robust to the selection of the pipeline and became non-significant after controlling for SNR. Taken together, our results demonstrate that changes in neuronal connectivity within the sensorimotor system are not critical for learning to control a BCI, and interventions that increase the SNR of the mu rhythm might lead to improvements in the user's performance.

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OSCILLATORY WAVEFORM SHAPE AND TEMPORAL SPIKE CORRELATIONS DIFFER ACROSS BAT FRONTAL AND AUDITORY CORTEX

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Abstract

Neural oscillations serve various functions in the mammalian brain, and the shape of these oscillations in the cortex can provide insights into local brain processes, as well as abnormalities or changing states. However, little is known about how the shape of these waveforms differs across distant but functionally and anatomically connected cortical regions. This research leverages simultaneous recordings of local field potentials (LFPs)

in the auditory and frontal cortices of awake *Carollia perspicillata* bats to investigate differences in waveform shape across these cortical regions on a cycle-by-cycle basis. Our study reveals significant distinctions in waveform shape within the fronto-auditory circuit, even when examining rhythmic activities within similar frequency ranges, such as delta and gamma bands, during spontaneous brain activity.

Furthermore, we identify consistent differences in the variability of waveform shape across individual cycles in these areas. A theoretical model predicts that regions with more asymmetric waveform shapes would exhibit stronger correlations between spike-spike and spike-LFP interactions, a pattern observed in the data, where frontal cortex displays higher spike-spike and spike-LFP correlations. This model suggests a connection between differences in waveform shape and va-

riations in spike correlations across different cortical areas. In summary, these findings underscore that oscillatory activities in the frontal and auditory cortices exhibit distinct dynamics, which can be related to the diversity of functions and anatomical patterns within the fronto-auditory circuit.

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STOCHASTIC RESONANCE AS A POSSIBLE TOOL FOR CONTINUOUS READ-OUT OF VISUAL WORKING MEMORY REPRESENTATIONS WITH MEG

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Abstract

The sensory recruitment hypothesis posits that early visual cortex (EVC) is recruited by more anterior cortical regions for the retention of high-precision visual working memory (VWM) information. Support for sensory recruitment comes from the ability to decode mnemonic content from patterns of BOLD responses in EVC. However, electrophysiological measurements of neural activity (e.g., MEEG or multi-unit recordings) typically do not show sustained decoding over the VWM delay. We hypothesize that this discrepancy emerges because feedback from anterior regions only modulates synaptic thresholds, but not firing in EVC. Indeed, single-cell recordings in macaque cortex show that top-down feedback systematically affects local field potentials (LFP) without altering neural firing directly. These systematic modulations of LFP might drive the robust decoding from the BOLD response, which correlates more closely with the LFP than spiking, without leaving a robust trace in the MEEG signal. In this study, we aim to make these spike-silent synaptic feedback signals detectable from MEG data by exploiting stochastic resonance. Stochastic resonance posits that sub-

threshold information in a nonlinear system (e.g., spike-silent feedback in a neuron) can be made supra-threshold (e.g., translated to firing) by injecting a small "resonant" amount of noise. The right amount of noise pushes informative parts of the signal above threshold and elicits responses that are patterned by the current state of the system (e.g., maintained VWM contents). To test this, we asked participants (N=7) to remember orientation stimuli while noise images of varying intensity were shown over a 2s delay period. By continuously activating EVC during the delay, we expect to find a 'resonant' level of visual stimulation that provides sustained read-out of mnemonic information. In preliminary analyses, VWM representations were decoded from occipital MEG sensors during the delay, and we observed a (thus-far) non-significant trend towards better decoding of intermediate noise contrasts. With more participants in this ongoing study, we hope to use stochastic resonance to find further evidence of sensory recruitment, bridge the gap between MEEG and fMRI findings, and present a viable method to improve read out of VWM information using MEEG.

RESTING-STATE HEARTBEAT-EVOKED POTENTIAL AS A TRAIT IN ANXIETY

Online version

- Global program
- A - G
- H - N
- O - Z

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Abstract

Anxiety disorders are accompanied by alterations in the interoceptive system, making affected individuals more sensitive to their bodily sensations. The pathophysiological mechanisms underlying these alterations remain poorly understood. Previous research shows that heartbeat-evoked potentials, neural reactions to heartbeats, during tasks may be linked to interoceptive ability. In a registered report, we plan to study if heartbeat-evoked potentials at rest can explain inter-individual variability in anxiety symptoms, and thus serve as a trait-like measure. To this end, we will test if resting-state heartbeat-evoked potentials are positively associated with anxiety scores in the LIFE-Adult-Study dataset (Loeffler et al., 2015): a large, pre-collected sample of participants (>3000). We will use 20-minute resting electroencephalography and electrocardiography recordings and the Generalized Anxiety Disorder questionnaire. Furthermore, we will control for a broad range of physio- and psychological measures such as age, heart rate variability, BMI, blood pressure, and depression scores. Currently, the heartbeat-evoked potential field faces a challenge establishing robust effects due to the lack of standards in data processing procedures.

To address this problem and to reduce pipeline-related effects, we will register a multiverse of analysis pipelines that will differ in baseline, filtering, ICA, and statistical analysis settings. We will use the permutation approach, cross-validation, and GLM to illustrate how sensitive the result is to the choice of a pipeline. Given that the study of altered interoception in clinical populations is a promising prospective field, we expect that clinical practice could benefit from the conclusions regarding the trait properties of heartbeat-evoked potentials and from clear methodological recommendations on how to compute them.

CO-VARYING EYE MOVEMENTS AND POWER MODULATIONS OF ALPHA OSCILLATIONS DURING WORKING MEMORY: A PILOT STUDY

Online version

- Global program
- A - G
- H - N
- O - Z

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Abstract

A common assumption in Cognitive Neuroscience is that brain rhythms vary with task-specific cognitive demands and reflect the neural support of the cognitive operation performed. Power modulations of alpha oscillations are consistently related to working memory (WM). However, there is an inconsistency in the literature regarding the direction of this association between alpha power and WM load: some findings suggest an increase while others suggest a decrease. To shed light on this topic, a pilot study (N=10) was conducted using the Sternberg and N-back task. The study aimed to explore whether different gaze patterns during these tasks could predict variations in alpha power. The preliminary findings revealed that the relationship between alpha power and WM load varied depending on the variability of participants' oculomotor actions. Specifically, when participants exhibited higher variability in their eye movements, there was a stronger decrease in alpha power with increasing WM load and lower variability

was associated with a weaker decrease. These preliminary results suggest that variations in alpha power with WM load, and power modulations more generally, may primarily serve to support oculomotor control, rather than solely reflecting the cognitive demands of the task. Furthermore, the study identified several other noteworthy preliminary conclusions. There was a close relationship between gaze patterns and alpha power modulation during WM, indicating that eye movements and alpha oscillations are intricately linked. Higher WM load was associated with a stronger reduction in alpha power and increased gaze variability. The modulation of posterior alpha power with WM load displayed significant interindividual variability. These findings will be used as the basis for a larger study (N=90) which will provide valuable insights into the role of oculomotor actions in the dynamics of alpha power during working memory tasks.

NEURAL SIGNATURES OF CONTINGENCY AWARENESS

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Abstract

The recognition of the conditioned-unconditioned stimulus (CS-US) association in human fear conditioning is referred to as contingency awareness. A common view is that such simple forms of associative learning are independent of

awareness. We challenge this view in an experimental design where only a half of the participants learned the association between CS and US. In this preregistered study (<https://osf.io/vywwq7>), we recorded

electroencephalography (EEG) from a sample of 78 participants. During the semantic compound conditioning experiment, the participants were presented with words (drawn from two semantic categories) paired with tactile stimulation followed by presentation of either neutral sound (CS- condition) or highly unpleasant loud noise (CS+ condition). Presentation of the unpleasant or neutral event in the end of the sequence depended on the word+vibration side compound (e.g., animals -> left hand vibration -> sound, animals -> right hand vibration -> noise, clothes -> right hand vibration -> sound, clothes -> left hand vibration -> noise). The participants were only instructed to listen carefully. Based on structured interviews, the participants were divided into an aware (N=48) and an unaware (N=30) group. A series of questionnaires were administered to explore potential predictors of contingency awareness. Only the aware group showed signs of learning as expressed in larger stimulus preceding negativity – a slow ERP component preceding emotionally charged

events – developing shortly before the US in the CS+ as compared to CS- condition. No such learning was evident in the unaware group. In terms of oscillatory brain activity, in the aware group, we found stronger alpha-beta suppression in response to the vibration and stronger alpha suppression before the vibration, as well as a weaker theta response to the US (loud noise), altogether possibly indicating heightened attention to the cue and violation/confirmation of expectation. The personality tests showed that probability to become aware of the contingencies was not significantly related to elevated anxiety, neuroticism, higher intolerance of uncertainty or harm avoidance. These findings support the notion that associative learning, as reflected in cortical measures, cannot occur without contingency awareness.

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CONSIDERATION OF ESTIMATION WINDOW LENGTH DURING OVERLAP CORRECTION OF EEG DATA

Online version

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Abstract

Regression Event-Related-Potentials (ERPs) with overlap correction (also referred to as linear deconvolution or temporal response functions) are becoming more popular for the analysis of Electroencephalography (EEG) data. In a nutshell, the continuous EEG is modelled as a mixture of overlapping ERPs instead of modelling time-locked data (e.g. by taking the average over multiple trials). Whereby it is assumed that each EEG sample can be modelled by the summation of the ERPs of the overlapping events. In practice,

we define a linear model incorporating all relevant information about each of the events, resulting in one design matrix per event type. Next, we define estimation windows (EW) around all event onsets, and "time-expand" our design-matrices around each event onset, resulting in a much taller and wider design-matrix. In the classical averaging analysis, we also make use of EWs - but critically, the actual EW length does not influence the estimate at other time-points. In striking contrast, choosing

the correct EWs for deconvolution analysis is crucial; long EWs might capture all relevant event-related activity but might introduce artifacts due to overfitting. Short EWs on the other hand might not overfit, but also might not capture all (overlapping) activity, and thereby introduce bias. Indeed, the question of choosing EWs is one of the most common questions we get with collaborators or at EEG workshops. Using a systematic simulation approach, we show that longer rather than shorter time windows should be preferred for typical EEG designs. We further provide an interactive app to visualize various design parameters: <http://estimationwindow.ccn2023.s-ccs.de>. Lastly, we explored the use of differing EWs on

several different empirical datasets. Here we show that the effect differing EWs have on the results seems to be heavily dependent on the dataset in question. Currently, we assume that this dependency stems from an interaction between the amount of overlap and noise present in the data, although more research is needed to confirm this assumption. While we saw changes in long-lasting activity when using longer EWs (likely an overfit to noise) we still advise using rather too long than too short EWs to capture all activity of interest.

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NEUROPHYSIOLOGICAL CORRELATES OF MOVEMENT KINEMATICS IN PARKINSON'S DISEASE PATIENTS USING PARALLEL SUBTHALAMIC LOCAL FIELD POTENTIALS AND ELECTROCORTICOGRAPHY RECORDINGS

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Abstract

Subthalamic deep brain stimulation (DBS) is a neurosurgical treatment that uses implanted electrodes and electrical stimulation to treat patients with Parkinson's disease (PD) or other movement disorders. The subthalamic nucleus (STN) is part of the basal ganglia and STN-DBS is known to cause behavioral alterations and clinical symptom alleviation, but the precise interactions of behavioral states during stimulation and consequent neural circuit effects remain unknown. Animal experiments with optogenetic stimulation have inspired the hypothesis that the effects of basal ganglia neurostimulation may depend on the behavioral and neural state at the time the stimulation is applied. To translate this concept to the human domain, we developed a speed-triggered stimulation paradigm, that allows the selective

stimulation of relatively slow vs. fast movements (300 ms, 130 Hz). We find a significant difference in the average speed between the conditions, with the overall speed being higher in the block in which fast movements were stimulated compared to the block in which slow movements were targeted (20 PD participants, OFF dopaminergic medication). The size of the stimulation-induced behavioral effect, however, varies strongly between patients. Therefore, we aim to elucidate whether invasively recorded neurophysiological states measured by bilateral STN local field potentials (LFP) and motor cortex electrocorticography (ECoG) may be predictive of the stimulation effect. As a first step, we will compute a series of features such as the oscillatory power and bursts from LFP and ECoG

recordings using the py_neuromodulation toolbox and correlate them with the patient's movement kinematics such as speed and deceleration. In the next step, we will relate the extracted features to the change in peak speed caused by adaptive STN-DBS. Our study may pave the way for the development of brain-state adaptive DBS for the treatment of PD and other brain disorders.

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MEMORY FORMATION IN HEALTHY AGING: UNVEILING THE IMPACT OF PRE-STIMULUS ACTIVITY ON POST-STIMULUS ALPHA DESYNCHRONISATION

Online version

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Abstract

Aging is often associated with cognitive decline and memory impairment. However, the neural mechanisms underlying memory formation and the factors contributing to impaired memory are still unknown. Previous research has primarily focused on memory formation through remembered versus forgotten comparisons, lacking the ability to capture the incremental nature of learning. Moreover, investigations have primarily examined event-related desynchronisation (ERD) of alpha power, neglecting the potential influence of ongoing, pre-stimulus alpha activity. To address these gaps, we employed a sequence learning paradigm, in which subjects learn a fixed sequence of visual stimuli over repeated observations. Critically, it allowed us to track the pre- and post-stimulus alpha power modulations during the incremental process of learning. Behavioral results revealed that young subjects learned significantly faster than older subjects, in line with expected age-related cognitive decline. Neu-

rophysiological data showed that pre-stimulus alpha increased with sequence knowledge. Crucially, mediation analysis revealed that alpha ERD was mediated by pre-stimulus activity. Specifically, successful learning was characterized by low pre-stimulus alpha and small ERD, whereas non-learning was characterized by high pre-stimulus alpha and large ERD. Interestingly, older subjects showed lower pre-stimulus alpha power and weaker modulations of alpha power during the task, suggesting potential age-related alterations in inhibitory mechanisms and lower capacity for information processing compared to their younger counterparts. These findings shed light on the age-related differences in memory formation and provide insights into ongoing and stimulus-related alpha power dynamics during learning. Further exploration of these mechanisms may contribute to the development of targeted interventions to enhance memory performance in older adults.

MOTOR IMAGERY OF LINKED MOVEMENTS ENHANCES MOTOR ADAPTATION

Online version

- Global program
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Abstract

Most movements in daily life do not occur in isolation but are embedded within a sequence. Linked movements like this have been shown to influence the execution of prior and following motor actions and can even facilitate adaptation during reaches through opposing force-fields. We investigated whether the facilitative effect of linked movements could also be achieved with kinesthetic motor imagery of prior movements. Additionally, we aimed to identify neuronal correlates of motor imagery predicting such motor learning. Movement kinematics (exoskeleton robot, Kinarm Lab) and EEG (64 electrodes) of 60 participants were recorded to investigate direction-specific adaptation during a reach of the right arm in an interference force-field paradigm. We compared performance of three experimental groups: 1) no prior movement (visual static cue) 2) active prior

movement, 3) motor imagined prior movement. In line with previous research, we showed that active prior movements facilitate adaptation to opposing force-fields, while visual static cues do not. Moreover, we found that motor imagery of prior movements can induce motor adaptation as well. In addition, our initial results indicate that post-imagery synchronization of alpha and beta oscillations can serve as an indicator of successful motor adaptation. Altogether our results go beyond a simple demonstration that motor imagery resembles performance of an actual movement in the brain. We show that the neuronal processes, underlying motor imagery of parts of a motor sequence, can be related to motor adaptation. This suggests that imagining a linked movement can be used to enhance motor performance of real movements.

GRADED CLUSTERED REACTIVATION DURING DECLARATIVE MEMORY RETRIEVAL: EVIDENCE FROM MEG RECORDINGS

Online version

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Abstract

Declarative memory storage and retrieval has been extensively researched. In animal models it has been established that retrieval involves reinstatement of previously encoded neuronal activity, however to what extent these findings translate to humans is not yet clear. How does the brain retrieve multi-item memories from storage? Two separate mechanisms have been proposed by previous study results: Individual items can be replayed in step-wise, temporally spaced-out succession (sequential replay) or alternatively, can be reactivated simultaneously (clustered reactivation). In our study, we investigated the presence of these mechanisms during cued retrieval with the help of magnetoencephalographic recordings (MEG). In the experiment, participants first

learned associations between ten images embedded in a directed graph network until they achieved 80% accuracy, followed by a 10-minute consolidation period. Using brain decoding, we examined evidence for clustered reactivation of learned material during a subsequent cued retrieval. During this testing session, we find evidence for graded clustered reactivation after cue onset, with reactivation strength of items decreasing with increasing graph distance. This ordering of reactivation was present only during successful retrieval and not during retrieval failure. Our results provide evidence that retrieval is supported by clustered reactivation, suggesting a mechanism for search within abstract cognitive maps.

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RIGHT LATERALIZATION OF THE STOPPING NETWORK: NEUROPHYSIOLOGICAL FINDINGS

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Abstract

Introduction: In Parkinson's disease (PD), abnormal beta oscillatory activity (13-35 Hz) across the cortico-basal-ganglia (BG) circuit is associated with motor symptoms. The Subthalamic Nucleus (STN) plays a pivotal role as a target for deep brain stimulation (DBS), and is also a central component within the so-called stopping network alongside the presupplementary motor area (pre-SMA) and the inferior frontal gyrus (IFG). It has been proposed that modulation of this right lateralized network could underline the alleviation of akine-

tic symptoms in PD. Thus, we hypothesized that pathological oscillatory circuit synchronization in the beta range of the stopping network may be associated with PD pathophysiology. To address this hypothesis, we leverage combined magnetoencephalography (MEG) and invasive subthalamic local field potential (LFP) recordings to investigate the lateralization of beta synchrony and assess the impact of dopaminergic medication in the stopping network of PD patients undergoing deep brain stimulation.

Material & Methods: In this study, we analyzed combined MEG and STN-LFP rest recordings in 34 participants from three centers. These recordings were obtained during periods of withdrawal of dopaminergic medication and following administration of L-dopa. We computed power spectra from source extracted MEG from bilateral pre-SMA and IFG as well as STN-LFP using Multitaper spectral estimations. Spectral parameterization was used to model the periodic beta power. We quantified cortico-basal-ganglia coupling using imaginary coherence - a frequency specific measure of functional connectivity. **Results:** Our findings reveal that in the medication-off state, there is a frequency specific increase in synchronization within the right hemisphere's stopping network, accompanied by a frequency shift following medication administration. Interestingly, no concomi-

tant change in oscillatory power in the beta frequency is observed. The administration of dopaminergic medication led to an increase in low-frequency activity within the theta/alpha range and a decrease in beta-frequency activity within the STN. **Discussion:** Our findings provide evidence for distinct interhemispheric differences in spectral communication patterns within the stopping network, with higher beta connectivity between preSMA, right IFG and STN in the right hemisphere. Our study may inspire promising implications for the potential development of circuit based adaptive stimulation strategies.

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INVESTIGATING RESTING-STATE EEG CORRELATES OF SUSTAINED ATTENTION IN HEALTHY AGEING: A CROSS-SECTIONAL BASELINE STUDY

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Abstract

Rationale: Older age is often associated with complex neuronal changes detectable by electroencephalography (EEG). Studies highlight age-related shifts in alpha oscillatory dynamics and its relationship with attentional processes. Furthermore, aperiodic neuronal activity shows age-related changes and have been shown to have implications in cognition. Though recent research has highlighted differences in peak alpha characteristics after adjusting for aperiodic activity, the interplay between Individual Alpha Peak Frequency (IAF), aperiodic activity, age and sustained attention in older adults has yet to be examined. **Materials and Methods:** This cross-sectional analysis used baseline data from the Lifestyle Intervention Study for Dementia Risk Reduction (LEISURE). Using the spectral parameterization (specpa-

ram) algorithm, we aimed to explore age-related changes in several resting-state EEG biomarkers (IAF, aperiodic offset, and exponent) and their impact on sustained attention, as measured by the CANTAB Rapid Visual Information Processing task (RVP) in healthy adults aged 50 and over (n=96, mean age=65.39, sd=8.44, female=80.2%). Hierarchical linear regression analyses were conducted, with age, gender, and education entered as covariates at Step 1, and the relevant EEG parameter at Step 2. **Results and Conclusions:** Notably, individuals with higher IAF exhibited an increased number of false alarms in the RVP task, suggesting that as IAF rises, there's a concurrent increase in attentional lapses and diminished cognitive alertness in sustained attention. Older individuals showed

a flatter aperiodic exponent and a lower offset. Despite these age-related changes, there was no link between aperiodic activity and sustained attention. No significant relationship between IAF and age was detected. Our results highlight the complex interplay between IAF, aperiodic activity, and sustained attention in older adults and demonstrate that multiple electrophysiological features, as well as their interplay, should be considered for the comprehensive assessment of association between age, neuronal activity, and cognitive performance.

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MODES OF INFORMATION PROCESSING DURING KNOWLEDGE ACQUISITION USING THE INTERNET

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Abstract

Introduction: In the modern information age, the internet is an unparalleled tool for acquiring knowledge. However, recent studies indicate that metacognitive judgements are biased towards overconfidence when people solve information problems using the internet (Pieschl, 2021; Ward, 2021). Moreover, confidence in false knowledge is observed following online searches (von Hoyer, 2021). Drawing from dual-process frameworks (e.g., Thompson, 2009), distinctions between analytic and heuristic processing may illuminate these metacognitive biases. Analytic processing, or deliberate reasoning, is vital for accurate mental models. Conversely, heuristic processing relies on intuitive heuristics or "cues", such as fluency and availability (Koriat, 1997). Integrating cognitive load theory and self-regulated learning theory, the Effort Monitoring and Regulation (EMR) framework offers additional theoretical insight (de Bruin & van Merriënboer, 2017). EMR emphasizes the impact of cognitive load on metacognitive processing capacities. From these frameworks, we derive our research questions: (1) How do time constraints on the explanatory knowledge task influence problem-solving with the internet? (2) How do these modes of processing relate to me-

tacognitive bias? **Method:** In this within-subjects experiment, participants first undertake two tasks: Raven's Progressive Matrices (RPM), which measures abstract reasoning, and a Rapid Evaluation Task (RET), wherein participants quickly judge the validity of short statements. They then answer explanatory knowledge questions using the internet under three different time constraints: 2, 5, and 15 minutes. Before and after answering an explanatory knowledge question, participants provide metacognitive judgments and judgments about intrinsic, extraneous, and germane cognitive load. Two blind raters independently evaluate the written answers using a standardized rubric to derive performance (Mattes & Pieschl, 2021). **Analysis:** EEG recordings during tasks serve as the primary dataset. Two distinct machine learning classifiers are trained using the RPM and RET data. These classifiers determine participants' dominant processing modes during online searches. The classification scores for the three time constraint conditions act as independent variables in a regression model with the absolute confidence bias (difference between metacognitive judgments and performance) as the dependent variable.

OPTIMIZATION OF M/EEG SPATIAL FILTERS FOR EXTRACTION OF ROI TIME SERIES BASED ON THE CROSS-TALK FUNCTION

Online version

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Abstract

One of the major challenges for the recovery of EEG/MEG sources and the interpretation of the obtained data is the field spread. In order to take this effect into account, source space analysis is widely used for the estimation of activity in the regions of interest (ROIs) as well as interactions between them. Time courses of activity in ROIs are typically obtained in two steps: (1) inverse modeling followed by (2) aggregation of time courses of activity for source dipoles (sources) within the ROI. For both steps, multiple methods exist, and so far there is no clear favorite among them in the literature. Yet, the choice of methods affects the results of the subsequent analyses, for example, when estimating functional connectivity. In the current study, we introduce two criteria for assessing the spatial origin of the extracted ROI time series. On the one hand, the contribution of sources within the ROI to the extracted signal should be as high as possible compared to sources outside the ROI. On the other hand, the contribution of sources

within the ROI should satisfy the requirements of the analysis, for example, homogeneity. For both criteria, we develop analytic expressions based on the cross-talk function (CTF; Hauk et al., NeuroImage, 2011), which reflects the contribution of all source dipoles to the extracted signal. We then optimize a linear combination of these criteria so that their relative importance can be fine-tuned according to the demands of the analysis. An optimal spatial filter for the extraction of ROI time series is derived from a generalized eigenvalue problem. The proposed method is benchmarked against several combinations of widely used methods for inverse modeling (eLORETA, LCMV) and aggregation of sources within the ROI (averaging, SVD, centroid). The results show that optimization improves the extraction of ROI time series by flexibly controlling contributions of sources to the extracted signal. Importantly, the improvement is not homogenous and is especially effective for ROIs that are closer to the surface of the skull.

BLINDLY SEPARATED SPONTANEOUS OSCILLATIONS PREDICT CORTICOSPINAL EXCITABILITY

Online version

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Abstract

The effects of Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation (TMS) on the motor network are highly variable due to the ongoing neural activity. Often regarded as noise, this variability of TMS responses provides a way of probing dynamic brain states related to corticospinal excitability. Electroencephalography (EEG) is the most temporally precise way to non-invasively access neural activity during TMS – unfortunately, at the cost of anatomical precision, especially regarding network activity. We employed a blind source separation (BSS) technique called analytic Common Spatial Patterns (aCSP), combined with machine-learning, to derive correlates of corticospinal excitability from pre-TMS EEG signals. The signal components were obtained individually, without any prior anatomical assumptions or restrictions regarding target cortical regions, and represented network-level oscillatory activity. High corticospinal

excitability was predicted by cortical activity within the β frequency band, located in the left central-parietal region, adjacent to the stimulated area, and frontal regions, and suggesting a travelling wave-like phenomenon. Low corticospinal excitability was also predicted by cortical activity within the β -band, this time localised in the parieto-occipital and medial frontal regions, hinting at communication between them. Both predictive components represented slow-scale dynamics, as they were temporally stationary within over 1 s before the TMS pulse. Overall, we established a data-driven approach to uncovering network-level oscillatory activity that modulates TMS effects. This approach requires no anatomical priors, while being physiologically interpretable, and can be employed in both exploratory investigation and brain-state-dependent stimulation.

SPATIO-TEMPORAL GENERAL ADDITIVE MIXED MODELS (GAMMS) FOR WHOLE BRAIN MEG ANALYSIS?

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Abstract

We collected MEG and behavioral data from 19 subjects performing an auditory pitch control task, in which slow continuous and fast intermittent pitch alterations had to be compensated with a button. We

identified compensating as well as paradoxical “following” responses to fast pitch alterations in which the finger appears to follow the externally induced pitch movement.

We want to test whether intrinsic neural processes at the time of disturbance are predictive of response class. Due to a low number of following responses we seek to partially pool information across participants. Standard mixed linear models are not readily applicable to MEG data due to poor inter-subject alignment of the neurophysiological correlates in the spatial (i.e. sensor) and temporal domains. While projecting individual sensor data to a standard source space or to virtual common sensors (by tSSS) improves spatial inter-subject alignment, it assumes a common anatomical-functional mapping and suffers from the underspecification of inverse mapping. Multiset Canonical Correlation Analysis performs favorably but is agnostic of the spatial structure and relies on temporal similarity of neural processes. Hidden Markov Models, temporal de-convolution and task-agnostic state segmentation weaken temporal alignment constraints but currently only work on the subject level, which hinders convergence on common patterns, while statistical inference on aggregate measures ignores within-subject variance. Multi-task learning and transfer-learning

are valid alternatives, but their "black box" nature limits the interpretability of resulting brain maps. We want to test the feasibility of generalized additive mixed models with per-subject Markov Random Field smooths of sensor location to account for inter-subject variability while retaining gross spatial structure. Handling time and frequency as smooth factors increases statistical sensitivity compared to mass univariate methods. If successful, all available data is integrated in one fully parametric but flexible model that affords comprehensive post-hoc analyses and maintains the interpretability of linear regression. Compared to a decoding model, an encoding model yields more interpretable brain maps. We anticipate computational challenges due to the large data set and the many model parameters, and have questions regarding model specification. We first model MEG activity during the motor responses, as we expect a higher effect size during this period.

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THE UNFOLD.JL REGRESSION-ERP ECOSYSTEM: WHAT'S NEW AND WHY BOTHER

Online version

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Abstract

Overlapping event responses, (non-)linear effects and confounds, outliers, item effects - all pretty common features limiting the application of ERPs in naturalistic paradigms (e.g. ET+EEG, VR+EEG, MoBi) but also classical paradigms (evidence Integration, language, even oddball tasks). The Unfold.jl ecosystem offers tools based on regression ERPs to account for each

of these issues. The tools currently consist of five packages: 1) Unfold.jl implements the model fitting based on the popular wilkinson~formula+syntax. It is feature-par with matlab-unfold. In addition it offers speed-improvements (up to 100x on GPUs) and extensions for outlier-robust fits, back-2back regression, and mixed models.

2. UnfoldMakie.jl offers a one-stop-shop for all (r)ERP plotting needs, with an in-development extension to interactively explore complex models. It outclasses e.g. eeglab by a speed factor of >20. 3. UnfoldBIDS.jl speeds up your workflow, making use of the BIDS structure and helps out on the second level. 4. UnfoldSim.jl scratches the itch to not trust new methods, but rather first test them on simulated data. 5. UnfoldDecode.jl provides tools to perform overlap-corrected decoding analyses (as recently proposed by Gal

Vishne, Carmel Auerbach-Asch and Leon Deouell). Most tools are interoperable, that is, you can easily call them from Python or R. Furthermore, all tools have documentation and tutorials to the best of our abilities, but more collaborators and more feedback is greatly appreciated.

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INFLUENCE OF COGNITIVE LOAD ON MOTOR PERFORMANCE AND SUBTHALAMIC BETA ACTIVITY IN PARKINSON'S DISEASE PATIENTS

Arian Memarpouri^{1,2}, **Jeroen G.V. Habets, MD PhD**², **Arko Ghosh, PhD**¹, **Andrea A. Kühn, MD**^{2,3,4,5}

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Abstract

Parkinson's disease (PD) is characterized by cardinal motor symptoms and non-motor symptoms, like cognitive impairments. Together, they can severely impact the patient's quality of life, and therapies for combating these symptoms include dopaminergic medication and deep brain stimulation (DBS). To better understand how PD therapies can improve the symptoms of patients in everyday life, recent studies revealed a dual-task effect in PD, meaning a concurrent cognitive task can reduce manual dexterity. However, this decline is less significant when DBS stimulation is active compared to when it's off. These behavioral results show a positive effect of DBS on dual-task performance, but the effect of a dual-task on adaptive DBS biomarkers, such as beta oscillations in the subthalamic nucleus (STN), still must be established. In our study, we will use a cognitive task, a motor task, and a dual task to investigate the effect of cognitive load on motor performance and subthalamic beta activity. The motor task is a custom-designed exergame where patients can move their hands in a virtual game environment, and cognitive performance is evaluated using the backward digit span task. For the dual task, patients will perform both

tasks simultaneously. We aim to recruit 20 PD patients who have previously undergone DBS surgery, and the tasks will be performed by all patients in the DBS on and off states. Moreover, we will record local field potentials in the STN through sensing-enabled DBS electrodes while the patients perform each task. This experiment will have a within-subject factorial design, allowing for comparisons of individual performance metrics across both DBS 'on' and 'off' states. We will use repeated measures ANOVA to compare manual dexterity, cognitive performance, and STN beta activities across the dual-task and single-task conditions within the distinct DBS states. On the behavioral level, we aim to replicate previous findings of a significant worsening of motor performance during the dual-task condition. Furthermore, we expect beta band activity in the STN to mirror the dual-task effect. Specifically, higher beta activity is associated with a greater decline in motor performance during the dual-task. By investigating the neural interplay between motor and cognitive symptoms, we can advance future adaptive DBS therapies that will improve patients' quality of life.

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[Local plenary lectures](#)[Link to live capture](#)

FROM DOLPHINS TO SLEEP WALKERS. SLEEP AS A GLOBAL AND LOCAL PHENOMENON

Lino Nobili¹

¹ *University of Genoa, IRCCS G. Gaslini Institute, Child Neuropsychiatry Unit, Italy*

[Local symposia](#)[Link to live capture](#)

INFANT EEG

Chair : Ermanno Quadrelli, University of Milano-Bicocca,
Department of Psychology, Milano, Italy

EEG TO STUDY TYPICAL AND ATYPICAL DEVELOPMENT: ISSUES AND PRACTICES

Chiara Cantiani¹

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Abstract

EEG is one of the primary experimental techniques allowing researchers to advance the understanding of early typical and atypical brain development. Despite its importance in getting meaningful

information and in driving theoretical advances, this methodology is rapidly evolving and presents unique challenges when applied to the study of infant brains.

In this introductory talk, I will present an overview of the main challenges regarding (1) paradigm selection, (2) EEG data acquisition, and (3) EEG/ERP data processing/analyses. Most of the open points will be addressed by the specific talks and in the hands-on included in the session. Hopefully, the session will result in a fruitful discussion with the experts in the field of developmental EEG in order to highlight good data collection and processing practices to maintain and increase the integrity of the field.

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THE DEVELOPMENTAL ORIGINS OF EMBEDDED NEURAL OSCILLATIONS FOR SPEECH AND LANGUAGE PROCESSING: THE ROLE OF PRENATAL AND EARLY POSTNATAL EXPERIENCE

Judit Gervain¹

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Abstract

Hearing is operational from the 24-28th week of gestation, so fetuses are immersed in a rich auditory environment and encounter, among other sounds, spoken language for the first time. However, the speech signal is low-pass filtered by maternal tissues and the intrauterine environment, suppressing individual sounds, but preserving prosody, i.e. the rhythm and melody of speech. Once they are born, infants get exposed to the full-band speech signal. The talk will report a series of EEG studies with newborns and young infants, investigating what fetuses and young infants learn from the prenatal, low-pass filtered and postnatal full band speech signal. A first study investigates whether newborns and 6-month-old infants track the envelope of speech, a signal that is sufficient for adults to understand speech in silence, and if yes, whether there are differences in speech enve-

lope tracking ability at birth and later. A second study assesses whether the hierarchy of embedded neural oscillations known to underlie speech processing in adults (e.g. Giraud & Poeppel 2012) is already present at birth, and if yes, whether it is already shaped by prenatal experience. The results suggest that the oscillatory hierarchy is indeed operational from birth, is shaped by prenatal experience with speech and shows developmental changes between birth and 6 months. A third study establishes a neural signature of learning from the native speech input by assessing how neural activation, in particular its long-range temporal dynamics, change after exposure to speech in the native language. The talk will end by discussing the theoretical implications of these mechanisms for early speech perception and later language development.

FREQUENCY-TAGGING: A POWERFUL METHOD TO INVESTIGATE NEUROCOGNITIVE DEVELOPMENT WITH EEG

M. Buiatti¹

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Abstract

Measuring stimulus-related neural activity with electroencephalography (EEG) in developmental populations is a challenging task: compared to adults, da-

tasets are much shorter due to the infants' limited attentional span and much noisier due to uncontrollable movements.

Frequency-tagging is an experimental design that minimizes these constraints by presenting the (potentially multiple) relevant features of the stimuli in a continuous oscillatory stream and by computing distinct feature-related responses at the frequency of feature occurrence, which yield a much higher signal-to-noise ratio than traditional event-related designs. The purpose of this talk is to provide indications on the optimal use of frequency-tagging in developmental EEG studies. Throughout the review of key studies on infants and newborns, I will stress that the methodological challenge of frequency-tagging in development lays in the simultaneous extreme

of short data and low tag frequencies, the latter required both to investigate higher-level cognition and to match the maturation limits of the youngest subjects. I will discuss the efficiency of standard amplitude and phase measures, as well as a novel one, when tackling this limit.

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A DEVELOPMENTAL APPROACH TO EEG CORTICAL SOURCE ANALYSIS

S. Conte¹

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Abstract

Cortical source reconstruction of electroencephalographic (EEG) signals can be an informative tool for the analysis of brain activity. The aim of source reconstruction is to identify the cortical generators (sources) of the EEG signal recorded on the scalp. The quality of the source reconstruction relies on the accuracy of the solutions to the forward problem, and consequently the inverse problem. An accurate forward solution is obtained when an appropriate imaging modality (i.e., structural magnetic resonance imaging, MRI) is used to describe the head geometry, precise electrode locations are identified with 3D maps of the sensor positions on the scalp, and realistic conductivity values are determined for each tissue type of the head model. Together these parameters

contribute to the definition of realistic head models and can improve the accuracy with which the generators of the neural activity are localized. In the current presentation I will be describing the main steps of the pipeline for source localization of ERP responses, with reference to the adjustments necessary when applying this procedure to pediatric populations. Alternative approaches will be discussed with respect to the construction of the head model and electrode maps. I will conclude with an overview of the advantages and limitations of the procedure compared with alternative neuroimaging techniques.

EEG-TMS

Link to live capture

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Chair : Chiara Mazzi, University of Verona, Department of Neurosciences, Biomedicine and Movement Sciences, Verona, Italy

COMPARISON OF DIFFERENT TMS-EEG CLEANING PIPELINES: ADVANTAGES, ISSUES AND CHALLENGES

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Abstract

Transcranial magnetic stimulation jointly delivered with electroencephalographic recordings (TMS-EEG) has revealed as a powerful tool for investigating cortical mechanisms and network perturbation. However, a plethora of artefacts contaminate TMS-EEG signals. How to remove artefacts from TMS-EEG recordings?

These artefacts can be removed with relative impact on neural activity using ICA but recently more suitable ad-hoc pipelines revealed their efficacy for separating artefactual noise from neural activity. We will show the characteristics of the artefacts and different possible approaches to remove them effectively.

Moreover, we recently tested three of the most well known TMS-EEG cleaning pipelines as AR-

TIST, TESA and SOUND. We used non-simulated sensory evoked potentials (SEPs) and TMS-EEG data respectively as ground-truth and artifactual signal, from which we extract typical TMS-related artifacts. Our analyses show that, despite the ICA-based artifactual components extraction method would bias ICA-based cleaning pipelines (such as ARTIST and TESA), SOUND still returns the preprocessed signal that correlates best with the ground-truth signal. This work informs researchers on which is the most reliable cleaning pipeline for TMS-EEG data: an essential step to define a "standard" in TMS-EEG data preprocessing, which would allow for more comparable results across research groups.

EFFECTIVE AND FUNCTIONAL CONNECTIVITY ANALYSIS OF TMS-EEG DATA

Alberto Pisoni ¹

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Abstract

TMS-EEG co-registration system allows assessing the cortical excitability level of the stimulated brain region and of brain sites that are connected to it. Through the analysis of the spread of the neural signal, indeed, TMS-EEG can reconstruct how and

when different cortical sites are communicating. This measure has been related to effective connectivity, since the perturbing stimulus is delivered through a TMS pulse, thus indicating where the signal is coming from.

Furthermore, the degree of communication between regions of the cortex starting from the stimulation of a specific region, can differentiate between degrees of consciousness induced by physiologic changes, as during sleep, or pathological conditions, as in disorders of consciousness, as well as external modulations, as in pharmacological anesthesia. Nevertheless, more subtle changes induced by neurophysiologic activations due to cognitive processing may be difficult to capture with such measure. Critically, brain states and cognitive processing have been linked to specific patterns of brain oscillatory activity, analyzed both in the time frequency domain as increases or decreases of power in specific EEG frequency bands, or using functional connectivity measures: when the features shared by two regions on their rhythmic activity are stable over time and trials, a certain degree of communication between the two cortical sites is supposed. There are, however, several different functional connectivity measures, each one with its strengths and weaknesses, and in the TMS-EEG literature, very few examples of the application of these indicators are present. One of the most critical aspects

of functional connectivity analyses is the problem of ghost connections or of separating two connections which are near in space. Furthermore, the TMS pulse introduces a strong amount of information in a very specific cortical site, which usually is the one in which researchers are interested into, thus increasing the possibility of highlighting fake connections between the TMS hotspot and neighboring regions due to signal spread. In this presentation, I will show through real data examples, how different acquisition and preprocessing steps of TMS-EEG recordings can influence functional connectivity results, and how different connectivity measures behave with this type of data, with a suggestion of which could be the best suited approach for computing functional connectivity with this technique. Finally, I will report how functional connectivity can be useful in TMS-EEG experiment to track changes induced by external modulations as well as by cognitive processing.

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Local talks

SOURCE RECONSTRUCTION IN M/EEG

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Abstract

In several applications it is either necessary or at least useful to localize, in time and space, the neural generators of the measured M/EEG data. To this aim it is necessary to perform an analysis step often referred to as source reconstruction. In this talk, we will provide a brief overview of the field, focusing on the following aspects:

1. Source reconstruction is technically not possible, as the data do not contain enough information to fully recover their exact generators; we should rather call this step source guessing (or estimation, if we

want to be statistically correct).

2. Due to point 1. above, it is preferable to have a probability distribution, rather than a single guess, as a solution of the problem; this is what Bayesian methods do.

3. When accurate localization is needed, an accurate forward model should be used in combination with a recent inverse method; recent inverse methods tend to outperform older ones, although they are not much used yet [Pascarella et al., NeuroImage 2023].

Posters

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INFANTS' NEURAL PROCESSING OF EMOTIONAL FACES IS AFFECTED BY OSTRACISM

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Abstract

Humans can extract multiple behavioral and biological information from processing others' facial expressions (Leppänen et al., 2007). This ability has been shown to appear at early stages of development (Rayson et al., 2017) and to play a fundamental role in social communication for infants (Kobiella et al., 2008). Many studies have investigated the neural correlates of face processing in infancy (e.g., Leppänen et al., 2007; Kobiella et al., 2008; Quadrelli et al., 2019); however, little is known about whether and how this processing can be affected by social interactions during infancy. The aim of this study is to explore whether being included or ostracized during a triadic playful social interaction (i.e., a ball-tossing game) can influence 13- to 14-month-old infants' behavioral reactivity during the game and the subsequent neural processing of emotional faces. Therefore, we implemented a live version of the Cyberball Game (Williams & Sommer, 1997; Williams et al., 2000) in which infants participated being either included or excluded while playing with two experimenters. The Cyberball phase was videorecorded to assess whether infants' behavior was affected by being ostracized as compared to included. Following the participation in the ball-tossing game, event-related potentials (ERPs) of 38 infants (N = 19 excluded) were measured while they observed

faces displaying dynamic expressions of anger, fear, and happiness. Results exploring behavioral reactions revealed that ostracism influenced ostracized infants' negative emotionality and involvement behaviors during the ball-tossing game. Furthermore, analysis on ERP data were conducted via ANOVAs to assess whether the condition in which the infant played the game and the emotional expressions seen had an impact on components' amplitude and latency. Results revealed a faster P1 to happy faces in the ostracism as compared to the inclusion condition. In addition, in the inclusion condition fearful faces elicited faster responses compared to happy expressions, while no significant differences emerged in the ostracism condition. However, no significant results were found for Nc component, considered as an index of the allocation of infants' attentional resources (i.e., Dennis et al., 2009) and for the N290 and P400 components (i.e., linked to face processing, and considered the precursors of adults' N170, de Haan et al., 2003). Current findings demonstrate that ostracism has a direct impact on infants' behavior and influences the way in which they process emotional faces at the neural level, thus suggesting possible negative cascading effects of ostracism episodes on infants' affective and cognitive development.

IMPACT OF TASK-IRRELEVANT EMOTIONAL STIMULI ON VISUAL SEARCH

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Abstract

Attention allows to prioritize relevant information from the environment, while filtering out irrelevant information. Research has revealed that attention can be involuntarily captured by task-irrelevant stimuli (distractors) that are salient for their physical features (e.g., color) or for emotional valence (e.g., negative), leading to impaired performance in visual search. Previous research has shown the possibility of improving our ability to ignore physically salient stimuli through repeated exposure. In view of this learning-dependent mechanism, questions remain about how emotionally salient distractors affect attentional mechanisms and especially whether their distracting power can similarly be reduced through experience. To investigate the attentional capture effect of these two different types of salient distractors, this study introduces a novel experimental design. Participants performed a visual search task involving squares, as in prior studies, and picture stimuli

with either negative or neutral valence, as a novel addition. Four stimuli were presented simultaneously in the search display, and participants were asked to find the target stimulus which differed from the others in terms of outline shape. Results showed better performance on distractor-absent trials compared to distractor-present trials. Additionally, emotional valence had a strong modulation effect on RTs, resulting in higher distractor cost in negative distractor-present trials compared to neutral distractor and distractor-absent trials. Despite performance improvement across blocks, negative distractors consistently resulted in higher error rates and longer target detection times. In conclusion, repeated exposure to salient stimuli reduced interference, but negative distractors consistently exert a notably greater impact on performance compared to other salient stimuli.

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SYNCHRONIZING WITH THE RHYTHM: INFANT NEURAL ENTRAINMENT TO MUSICAL AND SPEECH STIMULI

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Abstract

Neural entrainment is defined as the process whereby brain activity, and more specifically neuronal oscillations measured by electroencephalography (EEG), can synchronize with external (exogenous) stimulus rhythms. Low-frequency (< 6 Hz) neural entrainment has been observed for abstract stimulus properties such as the rhythms of musical beats and linguistic constituents (Nozaradan et al., 2011). Recent theories suggest that individual differences in this phenomenon could be one factor leading to atypical development trajectory of language ac-

quisition (Goswami, 2011). However, despite the importance that neural oscillations have assumed in the last years in the field of auditory neuroscience and speech perception, in human infants the oscillatory brain rhythms and their synchronization with complex auditory exogenous rhythms have been relatively unexplored. The present study aimed to further investigate infant neural entrainment to rhythmic patterns, and specifically to complex non-speech (musical) and speech rhythmic stimuli.

Specifically, we performed developmental analyses to explore potential similarities and differences between infants' and adults' ability to entrain to the stimuli and we compared infants from general population with a subsample of infants at higher risk of developing language impairment, i.e. infants at familiar risk (FH+). 36 8-month-old infants (26 from general population and 10 FH+) and 10 adults have been so far included in the study. Their EEG signals were recorded while they passively listened to non-speech and speech rhythmic stimuli modulated at different rates. The temporal envelope of three rhythm patterns was extracted using a Hilbert function implemented in MATLAB and the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) was applied to compute the spectrum of acoustic energy. FFT was applied to the averaged EEG using Letswave7 (Mouraux & Lannetti, 2008). Neural entrainment to the incoming rhythms was measured in the form of peaks emerging from the EEG spectrum at frequencies corresponding to the rhythm

envelope. Analyses of the EEG spectrum revealed clear responses above the noise floor at frequencies corresponding to the rhythm envelope, suggesting that – similarly to adults – infants at 8 months of age were capable of entraining to the incoming complex auditory rhythms. Preliminary results suggest that FH+ infants showed early anomalies in neural synchronization of both music and speech stimuli. Overall, we showed that measures of neural synchronization to complex auditory stimuli are a powerful tool to characterize rhythm perception/synchronization in early (a)typical development. Furthermore, such measures seem appropriate for the investigation of the effect of early music/rhythmic training in infancy (e.g., Dondena et al., 2021).

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ACTING JOINTLY IS NOT JUST ACTING SIDE-BY-SIDE: AN EEG HYPER-SCANNING STUDY

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Abstract

Anyone who has ever walked, cooked, or crafted with a friend is in a position to know that acting jointly is not just acting side-by-side. Yet scientific studies on joint action routinely contrast joint with solo action—thereby failing to isolate what is distinctive, among social phenomena, of acting jointly. The present study aims to fill this gap. We used EEG hyper-scanning to investigate whether there are markers of action planning and execution specific to joint action. If so, they should be different when agents plan and execute similar movements in parallel but merely individually. Twenty dyads had to move either one object (Joint-Action Condition) or two objects (Parallel-Action Condition) to a target using a joystick. The tasks were carefully constructed to make coordination challenging in both condi-

tions. We measured two event-related potentials (e.g. CNV and MRP)—as well as alpha-mu rhythm suppression in sensorimotor cortices during motor preparation and execution. We also planned to conduct analyses of inter-brain synchrony. Data hint at reduced CNV and MRP in the Joint- compared to Parallel Action Conditions. Reaction times were also shorter during Joint compared to Parallel Action. This suggests that coordination and mutual adaptation are less demanding in terms of self and other representation and monitoring when agents pursue a collective goal. Our study reveals EEG markers of planning and execution that distinguish merely acting in parallel (when this demands monitoring and coordinating another's action) from genuinely joint action.

TEMPORAL DYNAMICS OF SIZE CONSTANCY FOR PERCEPTION AND ACTION WITH REAL OBJECTS AT REAL DISTANCES

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Abstract

As we watch a train depart from a platform at a railway station, the size of its image on the retina gets smaller as it moves further away from us. Although the train is shrinking on our retina, we perceive it as exactly the same size, but just moving further from us. This perceptual rescaling of size to counteract the natural shrinkage of an object's retinal image with increasing distance is known as size constancy. Size constancy is critical not only to our perceptual experience, but also to our successful interactions with the physical and social world. Yet, our understanding of when and where the complex integration between size and distance information takes place remains unknown. Here, we recorded for the first time event-related potentials (ERPs) in conjunction with kinematics while participants were asked to either manually estimate the perceived size of an object (perceptual task) or to pick it up (grasping task). Small and big disks were placed at near and far distances, respectively, in order to subtend the same visual angle on the retina. Participants

were asked to maintain their gaze steadily on a fixation point throughout the experiment. Meanwhile EEG was recorded from 64 scalp electrodes and their hand was tracked with a motion capture system. We focused on the first positive-going visual evoked component peaking at approximately 90 ms after stimulus onset. In the posterior cluster, we found earlier latencies and greater amplitudes in response to bigger than smaller disks, regardless of the task. We also found a later effect of the task, around 130 ms, in a central cluster of electrodes, whereby the P2 mean amplitude was greater in the manual estimation task compared to the grasping. In line with the ERP results, reaction times were faster and mean grip apertures were larger for the bigger objects. These findings demonstrate that size constancy for real objects placed at different distances occurs at the earliest cortical stages and that early visual processing does not change as a function of task demand.

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BASELINE EEG IN THE FIRST YEAR OF LIFE: INSIGHTS INTO THE DEVELOPMENT OF AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDER AND LANGUAGE IMPAIRMENTS

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Abstract

Early identification of neurodevelopmental disorders is critical to ensure a prompt and effective intervention, thus improving the later outcome. Autism spectrum disorder (ASD) and language learning impairment (LLI) are among the most common neurodevelopmental disorders, and they share overlapping

symptoms. A number of studies reported an altered spontaneous brain activity in infants at higher likelihood (HL) of developing ASD or LLI (e.g. Benasich et al., 2008; Tierney et al., 2012), thus supporting the hypothesis that an atypical brain development might precede clinical symptoms.

The majority of these studies focused only on the analysis of EEG spectral power. However, other EEG derived measures should be investigated for a better understanding of the neural dynamics. Moreover, no previous works have used baseline EEG to investigate early brain development in both HL-ASD and HL-LLI infants altogether. This study aims to: 1) characterize neural activity in 6- and 12-month-old HL-ASD and HL-LLI infants, compared to typically developing (TD) infants, by analyzing EEG spectral power and complexity measures; 2) investigate if the measures associated with risk status are also linked with the later ASD or LLI diagnosis. We recorded 4 minutes of baseline EEG in 302 infants (147 TD, 87 HL-ASD, 68 HL-LLI) at 6 (T6) and 12 (T12) months of age using 60-electrode caps (Geodesic EEG System). We computed: Power Spectral Density (PSD), Detrended Fluctuation Analyses (DFA) and Multiscale Entropy (MSE) focusing on frontal scalp regions. Significant differences between groups were successively tested in subgroups of TD subjects without a diagnosis (N=84) and subjects dia-

gnosed with ASD (N=20) or LLI (N=18). We found risk status for ASD to be associated with reduced power and lower complexity (i.e. decreased long-range temporal correlations (LRTC)) in the low-frequency bands.

Whereas, risk status for LLI resulted to be associated with increased power and increased complexity (i.e. increased LRTC) in the high-frequency bands. No differences between groups emerged in relation to MSE, which significantly changed only between T6 and T12. Interestingly, later diagnosis shared similar associations, thus supporting the potential role of EEG derived measures as a biomarker useful for understanding pathophysiology and classifying diagnostic outcomes. Connectivity analysis are ongoing for an exhaustive characterization of brain dynamics and for the identification of the most relevant biomarkers.

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UNDERSTANDING HUMAN SPATIAL NAVIGATION SKILLS: AN EEG STUDY IN IMMERSIVE VIRTUAL REALITY

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Abstract

Spatial navigation is a complex cognitive process based on multiple senses which denotes the capacity to plan and execute free and goal-directed paths, thus representing an essential ability in daily-life. In this context, EEG alpha and theta frequency bands constitute the most studied oscillations since they have repeatedly been shown to correlate with encoding and retrieval of spatial information (e.g. Bischof et al., 2003) and with sensory, motor, and memory functions, respectively (e.g. Plank et al., 2010). Here, we plan to record EEG signal during a spatial task performed in immersive virtual reality (IVR) in adolescents to investigate the cortical correlates of active spatial navigation. Exploring navigation skills in adoles-

cents is relevant since this is the age when efficient spatial processing is ensured by the fact that allocentric and egocentric strategies operate in parallel (Ruggiero et al., 2016). Moreover, to the best of our knowledge, no previous studies have used EEG in combination with IVR in pediatric population. Twenty healthy youths (age range: 13-18 years) will perform a spatial navigation task in a IVR environment wearing a Oculus Quest and a 32-channel-EEG cap (AntNeuro). The experimental procedure is made of two phases: a training and a test phase. In the training phase (19 trials) the participant navigates through a 5 way maze in a playground trying to learn where a reward is located.

During the test phase (8 trials) he has to use the allocentric or egocentric strategy to find the reward. For the EEG data analysis, a trigger will be manually applied at the beginning of each trial and every time the participant takes a new path from the maze centre. The latter will be used to extract event-related epochs in which theta and alpha band power modulations will be analyzed. Since alpha and theta waves are directly related to the storage and retrieval of spatial information for navigation, we expect that theta and alpha activity will be enhanced during the decision-making phase on which path to take. Epochs derived from the test trials will be

analyzed separately according to the used strategy (allocentric or egocentric) in order to investigate if the cortical activity is influenced by the adopted strategy. In a second phase, the study will be extended to subjects with cerebral palsy (CP) whose spatial navigation abilities are impaired (Biffi et al., 2020). This will shed light to the neural mechanism underlying navigation problems in patients with CP.

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AN INTEGRATED EEG AND EYE-TRACKING APPROACH FOR THE STUDY OF AUDIOVISUAL SENSORY PROCESSING IN INFANTS AT ELEVATED LIKELIHOOD OF BEING AUTISTIC

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Abstract

Background: Autism Spectrum Disorder (ASD) is a heterogeneous condition characterized by atypical social communication and repetitive patterns of behaviour, with recent Italian prevalence estimates of one in 77. The heterogeneity of autism is expressed in individual variation not only in the severity of core symptoms but also in cognitive, language and behavioral skills, which show different developmental trajectories. Moreover, there is a strong interest in identifying reliable behavioral and brain-based predictors, which may constitute useful tools for early detection of at-risk cases. In particular, autistic individuals perform poorly during conditions that require integration across multiple sensory modalities such as audiovisual (AV) sensory integration and process differently social and non-social stimuli compared to neurotypical (NT) counterparts. However, the study of potential interaction between sensory and social processing in the first years of life is still scarce and no study examined early social and sensory markers in infant siblings of autistic children (EL-ASD) using integrated experimental

techniques. Objectives: We report a new research protocol that integrates electroencephalographic (EEG) and eye-tracking (pupillometry) measures (1) to characterize AV sensory processing in social and non-social conditions in EL-ASD compared to NT children, and (2) to investigate the association between early social and non-social sensory skills and the clinical outcome measures.

Methods and Analyses: The study includes EL-ASD and NT toddlers recruited at 18 months and a follow-up evaluation is collected at 24 months. At both time-points all children are assessed with an experimental protocol including behavioral and neurophysiological measures. The integrated EEG-eyetracking task focuses on AV sensory processing in social (face saying "wow" in infant-directed speech) and non-social (spinning top toy) conditions. Presented videos are presented both in synchronous and asynchronous modalities (1000 ms delay audio presentation). Thus, four conditions are considered (SOC/SYNCH, SOC/ASYNCH, NONSOC/SYNCH, NONSOC/ASYNCH).

EEG signal is recorded by EGI High-Density EEG 128-channel system and pupil parameters are recorded using a Tobii ProSpectrum 300 Hz system. In addition, complete information about clinical measures is collected for all children at 18 and 24 months. Data collection is ongoing and preliminary results in 18-month-old EL-ASD and NT children will be presented looking at EEG power and connectivity and at pupil dilation dynamics.

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THE ROLE OF APERIODIC COMPONENT IN DISCRIMINATING ALTERED EEG ACTIVITY IN A POPULATION OF STROKE PATIENTS

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Abstract

Background: One of the most common analysis techniques for EEG/MEG signal relies on the estimation of the frequency spectrum, which decomposes the raw signal into putative component oscillations with specific frequencies and expresses the amount of energy associated with each oscillation. Albeit already known since decades, in the recent years literature has witnessed a renewed interest in the so-called "aperiodic component" of the power spectrum. Indeed, beyond oscillations, EEG spectrum also features non-oscillatory activity or broadband 1/f noise, which lacks a predominant temporal frequency and is characterized by an exponent (the slope negativity) and an offset (indicating broadband power shift). Beside methodological implications in interpreting results on frequency bands, there is a growing interest on the potential clinical relevance of aperiodic component of the spectrum: recent studies examined changes in these parameters in various pathologies, from neurodegenerative diseases to stroke and schizophrenia (for a recent review see Pani et al., 2022). Despite this interest, very few have investigated its possible relationship with epilepsy, in particular in symptomatic epilepsy after stroke. Materials and Methods: We analyzed a 19 channel EEG dataset from a group of stroke patients recorded during a resting state paradigm; 19 of them presented EEG with epileptiform activity,

even though some of them (N=6) didn't have any clinical seizure after the stroke onset; the other group (N=26) have no epileptic history nor altered EEG. Using spectral parametrization (specparam, Donoghue et al., 2020) we extracted from each frequency spectrum of each patient the exponent and the offset of the aperiodic component; our goal was to investigate if aperiodic activity could differentiate these two populations, being a potential factor that could help discriminating pathological from non-pathological bioelectric cerebral activity.

Results: Both measures significantly differed between the two groups, being more negative in those patients which presented EEG with no epileptic activity. We also investigated if any of them was correlated with three different clinical scales, indicating stroke severity (NIHSS1, NIHSS2 and mRS) but we found no significant relationship. Conclusion: We found some evidence that stroke patients with altered EEG compared to stroke patients with normal EEG activity show difference in aperiodic activity. This effect may be driven by increases in the local excitation/inhibition ratio. These results could pave the way on the use of aperiodic component as biomarker for the development of epileptic EEG activity in stroke patients.

EXPLORING THE NEUROPHYSIOLOGICAL EFFECTS OF A VISUOMOTOR PAIRED ASSOCIATIVE STIMULATION PROTOCOL: A TMS-EEG STUDY

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Abstract

The mirror-Paired Associative Stimulation (m-PAS) is a cross-modal version of the PAS protocol that can induce new ipsilateral motor resonance responses through the repeated association of transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS) over the right primary motor cortex (M1) paired with the visual presentation of right-hand – i.e., ipsilateral to TMS – index finger movements. Here, we exploited TMS with electroencephalography (TMS-EEG) to clarify the global cortical dynamics underlying its aftereffects. Twenty-five healthy participants underwent the m-PAS protocol. Before and after each m-PAS session, TMS-evoked potential (TEPs) and Motor Evoked Potentials (MEPs) were concurrently recorded during the observation of both contralateral (left) and ipsilateral (right) index-finger movements (or static hands). MEP

analysis showed that the m-PAS induced new ipsilateral motor resonance responses, indexed by atypical facilitation of cortico-spinal excitability by the view of ipsilateral hand movements. Moreover, motor resonance was significantly reduced during the observation of contralateral hand movements. Preliminary TMS-EEG analysis showed amplitude modulations of mid-latency M1 TEP components at sensorimotor sites during the action observation task after the mPAS administration. Connectivity analysis will be carried out to evaluate pre-post differences in inter-areal communication patterns. Taken together, the m-PAS protocol effectively reshaped visuomotor representations. This modulation is detectable both at a peripheral (i.e., MEPs) and at a cortical level (i.e., TEPs).

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VISUAL RULE LEARNING ADVANTAGE IN PREVERBAL INFANTS OVER ADULTS: EVIDENCE FROM NEURAL ENTRAINMENT

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Abstract

Detecting and generalizing repetition-based abstract patterns in continuous streams of information (i.e., Rule Learning, RL) is a key cognitive ability available early in development. The classic approach to investigating infants' RL skills relies on habituation procedures measuring looking times that do not allow the identification of subtle differences in the processing of visual patterns and for comparing the functioning of RL skills across different age groups. To overcome this issue, we investigated visual RL with a new approach by capturing changes in neural entrainment to struc-

tures embedded in the input. Thirty-three adults and 31 9-month-old infants were exposed to 2 minutes of sequences of shapes organized into ABA triplets. Each shape was presented at a fixed rate of 6 Hz so that the triplet structure corresponded to a frequency of 2 Hz. The results from Z-scores of the signal-to-noise ratio at the stimulation frequencies (6 Hz and 2 Hz) revealed that the signal was significantly higher than noise already in the first 20 seconds of stimulation (Z-scores > 2.33, Bonferroni corrected), revealing a clear EEG response time-locked to the item

frequency (6 Hz) and the frequency of the embedded triplet (2 Hz). Moreover, infants showed a greater EEG response time at 6 and 2 Hz than adults ($p < .001$), suggesting an RL advantage in infants over adults. When comparing the time course of learning, the results showed different learning patterns between adults and infants. Adults showed an increase, while infants showed a decrease in EEG response to 6 Hz ($p < .007$).

Contrary, there are no differences in the EEG response to 2 Hz across time between groups ($p > .127$). These results suggest that neural entrainment is a promising tool for exploring how infants' and adults' brains track regularities and structures in the input.

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CENTRAL AND PERIPHERAL CORRELATES OF NEGATIVE EXPECTATIONS: TOWARD A NEW MODEL TO EXPLAIN FUNCTIONAL NEUROLOGICAL DISORDERS

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Abstract

Background: Functional neurological disorders (FND) are characterized by one or more symptoms usually of a motor or sensory nature, such as limb weakness, tremor, numbness and dissociative crises, which are incompatible with organic damage or the diseases that typically cause them. Anxiety and stress are considered important factors in the etiopathogenesis of FND. Several studies, in fact, show how the physiological correlates of anxiety and stress are altered in these patients. Through learning phenomena, patients would come to form negative expectations about the nature of sensory and bodily stimuli. Negative expectations, in turn, could fuel physiological anxiety and stress responses in an anticipatory manner. This study aims at developing a deeper understanding of the neurocognitive mechanisms underlying negative expectations in functional neurological disorders.

Methods: To this end, electroencephalogram and electrodermal activity (skin conductance responses, SCR) were preliminarily recorded in a group of 10 healthy adults who completed a Pavlovian threat-conditioning task that included an acquisition and an extinction phase. Two Landolt rings with different orientation were presented, one was reinforced with an extremely annoying but not painful short electrical stimulation (CS+) during the acquisition phase, while the other was never rein-

forced (CS-). We also collected subjective ratings of CSs valence and CS-shock contingency awareness to confirm the successfulness of the conditioning procedure. To get a complete picture of any individual differences in conditioned physiological response, we also assessed the role of personality traits through standardized questionnaires.

Results: Here we present preliminary results for subjective ratings and SCR. CSs valence and contingency were coherently recognized by the participants, validating the acquisition and extinction of the threat-conditioning. SCR data provided an additional confirmation of successful conditioning, with greater responses for the CS+ than the CS- during the acquisition phase; the difference between responses to the two stimuli quickly ran out during the extinction phase.

Conclusions: These preliminary results confirmed that it is possible to successfully induce threat-learning and negative expectations throughout this specific paradigm, associated with its psychophysiological correlates. The results of this first preliminary phase conducted on healthy adults will be compared with a group of FND undergoing the same paradigm to tackle the question of the role of negative expectations in the pathophysiology of the disorder.

THE ROLE OF CURRENT DIRECTION AND PULSE WAVEFORM ON THE MODULATION OF AN EARLY TMS-EVOKED POTENTIAL COMPONENT

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Abstract

The combination of transcranial magnetic stimulation with electroencephalography (TMS-EEG) allows to measure TMS-evoked potentials (TEPs) as indices of effective connectivity – i.e., the causal influence of a cortical area over a distant connected area. The development of TEP-derived markers of effective connectivity can be exploited to explore connectivity alterations in psychiatric and neurological conditions. To this aim, a significant challenge is understanding how stimulation parameters, such as the direction of induced current in the brain tissue and the waveform of TMS pulses, impact TEPs. Our study addresses this issue by utilizing an early TEP component (i.e., M1-P15) as an operational model to investigate the role of TMS parameters in the recording of early TEP components, supposed to reflect cortico-cortical connectivity. Indeed, the M1-P15 likely reflects cortico-cortical inhibition in motor areas through the corpus callosum. We conducted a single-session TMS-EEG experiment with 28 healthy participants, manipulating the induced current direction (posterior-anterior, anterior-posterior, latero-medial) and the TMS pulse waveform (monophasic, biphasic) across six experimental blocks. As dependent variables, we measured amplitude and latency of M1-P15. Additionally, we assessed the reliability of M1-P15 across the different conditions using the intraclass correlation coefficient (ICC). Our results revealed the pivotal role of TMS parameters in evoking the M1-P15, im-

pacting its amplitude, latency, and reliability. Specifically, M1-P15 exhibited the highest amplitude when TMS induced an anterior-posterior current direction with a monophasic waveform compared to other conditions. M1-P15 latency was longer for anterior-posterior current direction compared to posterior-anterior and latero-medial for both monophasic and biphasic waveforms. Finally, the reliability of M1-P15 was poor when stimulation parameters were altered from the ones applied in the original work of our research group on this cortico-cortical TEP component. This further suggests the necessity for controlling these factors to obtain consistent single-subject measurements. Overall, our study underscores the critical importance of considering TMS parameters when recording early cortico-cortical TEP responses. Our findings indicate that modifications in TMS parameters can significantly influence the spatiotemporal characteristics and reliability of early TEP components. This highlights the need for careful attention to stimulation parameters when using TMS-EEG to develop connectivity biomarkers based on TEPs.

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BRAIN CONNECTIVITY AND ELECTROCORTICAL SIGNALS RELATED TO ERROR PROCESSING: A COMBINED TMS-EEG-IMMERSIVE VIRTUAL REALITY STUDY

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Abstract

The ability to detect errors in goal-directed actions is quintessential in daily life interactions since, due to their dynamic nature, they often require flexible and adaptable behavior. Error-related negativity (ERN) and error-positivity (Pe) are the two main event-related components linked to error processing, along with fronto-medial Theta band (FM θ ; 4-8 Hz) synchronization. ERN is characterized by a negative deflection along the fronto-medial region with a peak around 50-100 milliseconds (ms) after error execution, followed by the Pe, which is mainly related to error awareness and is expressed by a positive peak located around centro-parietal regions. The anterior cingulate cortex (ACC), which plays a crucial role in performance monitoring, has been suggested as the main source of the above-mentioned electrocortical signatures. Notably, previous studies have shown that the observation of errors committed by an embodied virtual avatar (i.e., seen from a first person perspective - 1 PP) has led to the occurrence of ERN, Pe and FM θ synchronization (Pavone et al. 2016). In order for embodiment to take place in an immersive virtual reality environment (IVR), an individual has to control (Sense of Agency - SoA) and perceive (Sense of Ownership SoO) a virtual body as if it were their own. Interestingly, when an erroneous action is performed by an avatar, individuals seem to experience a transiently feeling of disembodiment with the virtual body (i.e., a reduction in SoO and SoA) which may derive from a potential interaction between the error

monitoring network and brain regions involved in Agency and Ownership (specifically frontal and parietal cortices). In the present project we aim at investigating the dynamic interplay between these networks by administering single-pulse Transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS) over ACC in combination with simultaneous electroencephalography (EEG) recording. ACC activity will be indirectly elicited by stimulating the anatomically connected left dorsolateral prefrontal cortex (dlPFC). 34 healthy participants (two groups: experimental, sham) will engage in an IVR task which requires the observation from a first- or third PP of an avatar performing successful or erroneous reach-to-grasp actions. Effective connectivity changes between ACC (stimulation target area) and remote brain sites will be examined by analyzing TMS-evoked potentials (TEPs) amplitude and changes in FM θ spectral power in the different experimental conditions. Further analyses will focus on the link between ERN, Pe, FM θ modulation and participants' self-reports concerning SoO and SoA, in order to better understand how these electrophysiological markers of error processing relate to behavior.

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FAMILIAR RHYTHMIC STRUCTURES FACILITATE PREDICTIONS ABOUT UPCOMING STIMULI IN THE NEWBORN BRAIN

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Abstract

Neural oscillations are a key neural mechanism in speech perception and language processing in adults (Giraud & Poeppel 2012; Peelle, Gross, & Davis, 2013). However, their role in language processing during early human development is far less well understood. Newborns already show remarkable speech perception abilities. For example, they are able to discriminate languages based on their rhythm behaviorally (Nazzi, Bertoncini, & Mehler, 1998; Ramus et al. 2000). The neural correlates of this ability have also been recently identified: newborns' brain activity differentiates sentences in the native language (French) and a rhythmically similar unfamiliar language (Spanish) from sentences in a rhythmically different unknown language (English) (Ortiz, Guevara, Gervain, 2023). Interestingly, in this study newborns' brain activity increased during the experiment (Ortiz et al., 2023). What causes this increase remains unexplained in this study. The brain has been shown to form predictions about upcoming events (Auksztulewicz et al., 2018; Morillon & Schroeder, 2015). Hence, as speech perception arises from the dynamic sampling of acoustic information at multiple time scales (Morillon & Schroeder 2015), the ability to predict upcoming events may facilitate the encoding of linguistic stimuli (Kujala et al 2023). We thus hypothesize that the increased brain activity observed as sentence presentation unfolded might represent predictions about the rhythmic structure of linguistic stimuli. Consequently, the repeated presentation of the same stimulus may lead to a progressively faster enco-

ding of its characteristics. Indeed, such predictions have been shown to speed up processing of quasi-rhythmic stimuli in adults, resulting in increasingly early response onsets for repeated stimuli termed "precession" (Teng et al., 2020). To test whether this occurs in the newborn brain, we are applying phase precession analysis to the data of Ortiz et al. (2023). After extracting the peak frequency across EEG frequency bands in the first and last sentences presented, we calculate the cross-correlation between the two signals and extract the maximum phase lags for each peak. If no phase precession is present, phases will proceed in 2π steps. Otherwise, if phases are accelerated, slopes will be steeper and the delay would be greater than 2π (Teng, Larrouy-Maestri, & Poeppel, 2021). We expect to find greater phase precession for the native language and the rhythmically similar unfamiliar language than for the rhythmically different unfamiliar language. This could index the presence of specific predictions regarding the rhythmic structure of speech that guide its encoding, further strengthening the role that rhythm plays in language acquisition already from birth.

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IDENTIFICATION OF VERY EARLY COMPONENTS FOR TMS-EVOKED POTENTIALS

A. Stango¹, G. Guidali, A. Zazio, D. Lucarelli, E. Marcantoni, G. Barchiesi, M. Bortoletto

¹ IRCCS Istituto Centro San Giovanni di Dio Fatebenefratelli, Italy

Abstract

Transcranial Magnetic Stimulation coupled with Electroencephalography (TMS-EEG) has emerged as a pioneering approach, providing unprecedented insights into neural signal recording. Current studies employing TMS-EEG coregistration report the generation of TMS-evoked potentials (TEPs) from about 15 ms after the TMS pulse. It is agreed that these TEP components, including the early ones around 15 ms, are generated by secondary activations of distant areas. The advancement of systems for recording TMS-EEG data has brought a better recovery of EEG signals after the TMS pulse. With amplifiers capable of reaching a sampling rate of over 5K Hz it has become possible to reduce the duration of the magnetic pulse artifact to less than 3 ms. This has opened up new perspectives in the analysis of TMS-EEG data, leading to the discovery of early TEP components possibly reflecting the evoked response from the directly stimulated area. In a recently published preprint, the presence of immediate components (2ms after the TMS pulse) has been acknowledged, suggesting that they are cortical responses. Here, we conducted a study to explore the existence of very early components, occurring between 3 ms and 10 ms after the TMS pulse, targeting the motor hand representation in pre-central gyrus (M1). Furthermore, we aimed to test the impact of muscle artifacts on detecting these components. In this analysis, we use the data from a previous study conducted in our laboratory. The study included 28 healthy participants who underwent a single-session TMS-EEG experiment in

which we varied the current direction of biphasic stimulation, including anterior-posterior-posterior-anterior (AP-PA) and posterior-anterior-anterior-posterior (PA-AP). The EEG signals were recorded at a sampling rate of 9600 Hz, allowing us to estimate the duration of the stimulation artifact to be ~2.5 ms. In this preliminary analysis, we considered only the anterior-posterior-posterior-anterior (AP-PA) direction and obtained average TEPs after minimal signal preprocessing. Next, we divided the subjects into two groups: one where no muscular artifact was detected (noMA), and one with muscular artifacts (wiMA). A very early component, i-TEP, was identified within an interval approximately from 3 ms to 8 ms, similar to the one identified in the preprint study. This component is characterized by a series of peaks, three in most of the cases. These peaks are more prominent on the electrodes close to the stimulation site, with amplitude around 30-40 μ V. Interestingly, the i-TEP was evident with similar features in both groups, noMA and wiMA. In the following studies, we will discuss if this component can be considered a cortical response.

- Global program
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THE NEURAL CORRELATES OF WORD ORDER IN PRE-LEXICAL INFANTS: A FREQUENCY-TAGGING APPROACH

M.Turconi¹, J. Gervain

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Abstract

Infants learn their native language quickly and effortlessly and follow the same developmental path regardless of culture. Although infants have an immature peripheral and central auditory system, they show exquisite speech perception abilities from birth. Indeed, the fetus' auditory system is functional by about 150 days after gestation. So, even before birth, they are exposed to the acoustic external environment, which is, however, muffled by the mother's body. According to the "bootstrapping hypothesis" (Morgan and Demuth 1996) infants are able to acquire abstract and structural properties of their language by detecting and using perceptually available surface cues present in the speech input. One of those properties seems to be word order: a pivotal basic element of language acquisition. Indeed, a series of behavioural studies have repeatedly demonstrated that young learners exhibit some knowledge of basic word order from their earliest multiword utterances (Brown 1973; Guasti 2002; Gervain et al. 2008; Bernard and Gervain 2012; de la Cruz et al. 2021). To understand how the surface cues of speech inputs are perceived, neuropsychological and brain imaging works have been conducted in recent years. Their results suggest that language acquisition involves neural commitment (Ahissar et al. 2001; Luo and Poeppel 2007; Buiatti et al. 2009; Ding et al. 2015; Chen et al. 2020): neural phase-locking to speech rhythm seems to track speech comprehension in a reliable way. Using a frequency-tagging approach we aimed to explore the neural mechanisms

underlying the perception of word order thanks to the surface cue of the relative position of functors and content words in pre-lexical infants. High-density EEG was recorded in infants of 6 to 8 months of age listening to a monotonous acoustic stream composed of two alternate basic units presented periodically at a specific temporal frequency that mimic the relative frequency of functors and content words in natural languages (aXbY, see Gervain et al. 2008). We hypothesize that the presentation of these structured units, composed of regularly concatenated syllables, would give rise to a peak of power at the frequencies of syllable occurrence. Consequently, if after some exposure, syllables are bound to adjacent syllables and ultimately grouped in quadrisyllabic words, we expected to record a peak of power at the frequency of two or four syllables.

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Local workshops & tutorials

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HANDS-ON SESAME: A MULTI-DIPOLE LOCALIZATION METHOD

Alessandro Viani¹, **Gianvittorio Luria**², **Annalisa Pascarella**³

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Abstract

SESAMEEG (<https://pybees.github.io/sesameeg/>) is a Python3 package providing the Bayesian multi-dipole localization method SESAME (SEquential Semi-Analytic Montecarlo Estimator) for the automatic estimation of brain source currents from MEEG data, either in the time domain and in the frequency domain.

The present tutorial will introduce and demonstrate the use of SESAMEEG. In particular, the session will

begin with a brief introduction about SESAME, with a focus on main inputs and outputs of the method. Then, we will show the application of SESAME to a sample dataset provide by the MNE-Python package and show how changes in input parameters may affect the reconstructed neural activity.

At the end of the session participants will have acquired the necessary skills to reconstruct the neural sources by using SESAMEEG.

PREPROCESSING WITH EEGLAB

Camillo Porcaro¹, **Caterina Piazza**²

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² Scientific Institute, I.R.C.C.S. "E.Medea", Bosisio Parini, Italy

Abstract

EEGLAB (Delorme & Makeig, 2004) is a Matlab toolbox for analyzing continuous and event-related EEG, MEG and other electrophysiological data. Over the last 19 years, it has become one of the most used environment for human EEG data processing, with contributions from the scientific community in terms of programming, plug-ins preparation, and especially use.

The present tutorial will introduce and demonstrate the use of the EEGLAB software environment and EEGLAB-linked tools for performing the preprocessing of EEG data, with detailed method expositions and practical exercises.

The session will begin with a brief introduction about neural basis and measurement of EEG signal. This will be followed by a detailed description of a preprocessing pipeline in EEGLAB. Each preprocessing step will be practically executed using a real dataset. Alternative methods of analysis will be presented using various EEGLAB tools. The final part of the tutorial will be devoted to the Independent Component Analysis (ICA), introduced both theoretically and practically.

At the end of the session participants will have acquired the skills necessary to process their EEG data.

EEG AND EYE-TRACKING INTEGRATION

Christoph Huber-Huber¹, Andrea Vitale²

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Abstract

In this hands-on session, we will process an EEG dataset with concurrently recorded eye-tracking data using the EEGLAB and EYE-EEG toolboxes in Matlab. The dataset was originally recorded to investigate the impact of active gaze behavior on early stages of visual processing. We start with a brief introduction to eye-tracking and eye-movement artifacts in the EEG. We will, then, analyze the data from a set of participants. We will give advice on synchronization, eye-tracker-supported ICA, and deconvolution methods (unfold toolbox).

In sum, our hands-on session will demonstrate how to work with coregistered EEG and eye-tracking data and it will highlight the importance of considering eye movements when working with EEG in general. There will be time for dealing with general questions and specific issues by the attendees. Eventually, we will provide suggestions and feedback to EEG and eye-tracking studies that have already been conducted or are being planned.

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ARTIFACT REMOVAL PIPELINES FOR HUMAN NEWBORN EEG DATA

Velu Prabhakar Kumaravel¹

¹ *University of Trento, Italy*

Abstract

In recent years, Electroencephalography (EEG) has become an important method for studying the brain's functions shortly after birth. However, working with EEG data from newborns is challenging because data tends to be much shorter due to their limited attentional span, and much noisier due to unpredictable movement artifacts. To the best of our knowledge, there are no specialized tools available for this specific population. As a result, most researchers studying infant development have to manually inspect and clean EEG data, a time-consuming and subjective process that raises concerns about the reliability of their findings.

To address this issue, we have introduced the Newborn EEG Artifact Removal (NEAR) pipeline. NEAR is designed explicitly for handling EEG data from human newborns and consists of two essential components:

1. A novel tool that identifies bad channels in the EEG data using the Local Outlier Factor (LOF), a robust

outlier detection algorithm.

2. A method for adapting the parameters of the Artifacts Subspace Reconstruction (ASR) algorithm (developed for cleaning EEG data from mobile adults) to remove artifacts from newborn EEG data.

In this tutorial and hands-on session, I will start by explaining the underlying principles of the NEAR pipeline. Then, we will work with a sample dataset from newborns and walk through the entire artifact cleaning process using the NEAR pipeline. Additionally, I will demonstrate how to fine-tune the user parameters to optimize NEAR for your specific datasets, both for newborn and infant EEG data.

Overall, this approach aims to streamline and enhance the processing of newborn EEG data, addressing the current challenges associated with manual preprocessing and improving the reliability and reproducibility of EEG-based research in the field of infant development.

REAL-TIME MONITORING OF TMS-EVOKED POTENTIALS TO IMPROVE DATA QUALITY

Silvia Casarotto^{1,2}

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² *IRCCS Fondazione Don Carlo Gnocchi Onlus, Milan, Italy*

Abstract

Neuronal responses to stimulation provide useful complementary information to spontaneous brain activity. When sensory pathways are impaired and/or subject's collaboration is unreliable, electroencephalography (EEG) combined with transcranial magnetic stimulation (TMS) represents an ideal tool to investigate brain's reactivity. However, the actual impact of TMS on cortical neurons is currently hard to predict based on a priori biophysical and anatomical knowledge alone. In addition, the nature of TMS brings about special kinds of artifacts, including electromagnetic pulse artifact, unwanted activation of scalp muscles, slow capacitive discharging of charges that accumulate at the electrode-gel-skin interface and spurious potentials evoked by the coil's click and vibration. Here, we describe a customized software tool labelled rt-TEP (real-time TEP), which interfaces with different EEG amplifiers and offers a series of informative visualization modes to assess the ma-

gnitude of the initial brain response to TMS as well as the overall quality of TMS-evoked potentials (TEPs) in real time.

rt-TEP represents a fundamental software complement to any TMS-compatible EEG system because it allows the experimenter to detect the occurrence of artifacts as well as to evaluate the amplitude of TEPs already during data collection. This real-time readout can be used to optimize TMS parameters (e.g., site, orientation, intensity) before data acquisition to obtain TEPs characterized by high signal-to-noise ratio.

Real-time optimization of TMS parameters to achieve a desired level of initial activation can facilitate the acquisition of reliable TEPs and can improve the reproducibility of data collection across laboratories.

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Ghent

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Local symposia

EEG Machine Learning for Science

This symposium was organized with the support of the Flemish government and of the doctoral schools of Social and Behavioural Sciences (SBS), Natural Sciences (NS), Life Sciences and Medicine (LSM) & Arts, Humanities and Law (AHL) of Ghent University.

Chair : Raquel London, Ghent University, Department of Experimental Psychology, Belgium
Roos A. Doekemeijer, Ghent University, Department of Experimental Psychology, Belgium
Sven Wientjes, Ghent University, Department of Experimental Psychology, Belgium

Symposium abstract

By allowing data-driven discoveries, machine learning can identify unexpected associations between brain processes and cognitive functions. It can integrate and analyze diverse data types such as EEG, behavior and model parameters.

BEYOND THE HIDDEN MARKOV MODEL: APPLICATIONS FOR DECODING AND PREDICTION OF BEHAVIOUR

Diego Vidaurre Henche¹

¹ Aarhus University, Department of Clinical Health, Center of Functionally Integrative Neuroscience, Denmark

Abstract

Brain activity is vastly multidimensional and complex. Not only across subjects, but also across experimental repetitions or trials, brain pattern show great variability that traditional methods are often limited to accommodate. As a way to find structure

within this complexity, thus enabling efforts to find meaningful associations to behaviour, the Hidden Markov Model (HMM) has emerged in the last years as a general family of models that can be used across data modalities.

In this talk, I will introduce the HMM in its most general form, and discuss two problems/solutions: (i) how the HMM can help us to describe the unique information that individual trials have above and beyond crude averages; and (ii) how we can use the individual subject HMMs to predict individual traits such as brain age or intelligence.

- Global program
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UNDERSTANDING COGNITION ONE STAGE AT A TIME: DISCOVERING COGNITIVE EVENTS ON SINGLE TRIALS

[Link to live capture](#)

Jelmer P. Borst¹

¹ *University of Groningen, Faculty of Science and Engineering, Bernoulli Institute, the Netherlands*

Abstract

Cognitive science has long investigated processing stages. Where the traditional methods of Donders and Sternberg were limited by behavioral measures, recent methods have used brain measures to track cognitive processing more directly. Here I will present one such a method, HMP, which is founded on two theories of EEG generation. Both the classical theory and the synchronized oscillation theory state that significant cognitive events cause multivariate voltage peaks that are added to the ongoing oscillations. The HMP method discovers such peaks, and thereby the onset of cognitive stages in EEG or MEG data using

hidden semi-Markov models. It integrates the information present across all trials of all participants, to ultimately identify multivariate peaks on single trials. I will first show that this method can identify processing stages in simple decision and memory tasks, and that it can track which cognitive stages are affected by experimental conditions. Next, I will show that we can measure the onsets of cognitive stages at the single-trial level, allowing for many new ways to analyze data: from more precise ERP-like components, to within-stage connectivity, to linking continuous predictors to stage durations across trials.

DYNAMIC REPRESENTATIONAL SIMILARITY ANALYSIS

[Link to live capture](#)

Ingmar E. J. de Vries^{1,2}

¹ *Donders Institute, Radboud University, Nijmegen, the Netherlands*; ² *Centre for Mind/Brain Sciences (CIMEC), University of Trento, Rovereto, Italy*

Abstract

In dynamic environments (e.g., traffic or sports), our brain is faced with a continuous stream of changing sensory input. Adaptive behavior requires our brain to predict unfolding external dynamics. While

theories assume such dynamic prediction, empirical evidence is limited to static snapshots and indirect consequences.

We developed a dynamic extension to representational similarity analysis (dRSA) that uses temporally variable models to capture neural representations of unfolding events across hierarchical levels (from perceptual to conceptual). This approach quantifies the match between a stimulus model at a given time-point and the neural representation at different (i.e., earlier, or later) time-points. We applied dRSA to source-reconstructed MEG data and demonstrate neural representations of observed (predictable) actions to be mostly predictive. Predictions encompass several timescales matching hierarchical levels of processing, such that high-level conceptual features are predicted earlier, while low-level perceptual features

are predicted closer to real-time. Additionally, we manipulated prior stimulus knowledge at two levels by either inversion (up-down) or temporal piecewise scrambling of action videos and observe a feature-specific reduction of predictive representations and increased unpredicted post-stimulus representations. To conclude, this new approach demonstrates the predictive nature of neural representations of naturalistic dynamic input and provides support for predictive coding theories of the brain.

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Posters

CONCEALED PERSONALLY FAMILIAR FACE DETECTION WITH EEG IN RAPID SERIAL VISUAL PRESENTATION

Ivory Y. Chena ¹, Sebastiaan Mathôt ¹, Robbert van der Mijn ¹, Aytaç Karabay ², Howard Bowman ^{3,4}, Elkan G. Akyürek ¹

¹ University of Groningen, Department of Experimental Psychology, the Netherlands ; ² New York University Abu Dhabi, Department of Psychology, United Arab Emirates ; ³ University of Birmingham, School of Psychology, UK ; ⁴ University of Kent, School of Computing, UK

Abstract

Rapid serial visual presentation (RSVP) has proven effective against countermeasures that classical concealed information tests (CIT) are vulnerable to. Here we investigated whether RSVP-based CIT in combination with EEG is effective for detecting concealed familiar faces, and we compared the sensitivities of univariate analyses and multivariate analyses (neural-network decoding). 29 participants searched for a target face in an RSVP task while a familiar face (one of their parents' faces) or one of two control faces also appeared in the stream. Using univariate cluster-based permutation tests of central midline electrodes, we were able to detect familiar face recognition in 17 parti-

cipants, yielding a detection rate of 58.6%. We also observed an increase in theta power in response to familiar faces, and were able to detect 14 participants out of 29 (detection rate of 48.3%) based on theta power. Neural network decoding was able to detect familiar faces at the group level, but with considerable variability between participants. Based on exploratory analyses, we suggest that neural-network decoding is promising but requires more data than univariate analyses. Taken together, our findings suggest that RSVP-based CIT is a potentially powerful tool when combined with an optimized EEG experimental paradigm and data-analysis procedure.

EFFECTS OF DIFFERENTIAL FEAR CONDITIONING ON THE PERCEPTION AND NEURAL PROCESSING OF RESPIRATORY STIMULATION

Valentina Jelinčić ¹, Ilse Van Diest ¹, Diana Torta ¹, Andreas von Leupoldt ¹

¹ KU Leuven, Faculty of Psychology and Educational Sciences, Research Group Health Psychology, Belgium

Abstract

Bodily symptoms are often exacerbated by anxiety, yet neural mechanisms underlying this increase are poorly understood. Fear conditioning (FC) entails forming an association between a neutral conditioned stimulus (CS) and an aversive unconditioned stimulus (US), and is considered an etiological model of anxiety. We investigated the effects of differential FC on the perception and neural processing of respiratory stimuli. We explored relationships with US expectancy (learning index). 52 participants received two inspiratory occlusions (S1 and S2) within one inspiration (duration=150ms, ISI=500ms), every 2-5 breaths while viewing a neutral female face (CS). Different faces served as threat and safety cues (CS+/CS-). The US

was a shrill scream following only CS+. We measured the peak N1 event-related potential responses to S1 and S2. Participants were intermittently asked to self-report the intensity and unpleasantness of occlusion pairs, as well as US expectancy. We observed significant increases in perceived unpleasantness and N1 amplitudes during CS+ relative to CS- trials. Higher US expectancy for CS- predicted increased N1 amplitudes during CS- trials. These results support the relevance of fearful states for respiratory processing, and demonstrate a link between the propensity for anxious responding and symptom perception. Replications in patients are necessary to judge clinical relevance.

- Global program
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EFFECT OF ADDED SUGAR ON RESPONSE INHIBITION: EVENT-RELATED POTENTIALS IN A GO/NOGO STUDY

Karolina Jocabalyte ¹, Rytis Stanikunas ¹

¹ Vilnius University, Institute of Psychology, Lithuania

Abstract

Added sugar usage has become an important public health issue nowadays. Therefore, the interest in studying the cognitive and emotional effects associated with sugar consumption has increased. The aim of the present study was to investigate how the intake of added sugar affects participants' response inhibition monitored during the performance of a computerized Go/NoGo task. Participants (20 subjects: 10 men and 10 women) performed the Go/NoGo task during which electroencephalogram (event-related potentials) and electrocardiogram were registered. There were two analogous blocks of tasks, separated by a break during which participants consumed an added sugar (25-50 grams) containing beverage and

filled in questionnaires: the Dietary Fat and Free Sugar – Short Questionnaire (DFS), the Yale Food Addiction Scale (YFAS 2.0), and the Barratt impulsiveness scale (BIS-11). Comparing the behavioral results before and after the added sugar consumption revealed no differences in computerized tasks' performance. No differences in reaction time or number of errors were associated with an intake of added sugar. However, the ERPs revealed significant differences in the P3 components. Specifically, the higher amplitude of NoGo-P3 after the added sugar consumption. This may reflect the need for more cognitive endeavors for successful inhibition of response impulses.

THE CARDIAC AND RESPIRATORY PHASES DETERMINE THE ONSET AND THE INTRACRANIAL GENERATORS OF THE NEURAL CORRELATES OF CONSCIOUSNESS

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¹ University of Fribourg, Switzerland

Abstract

We can investigate neural correlates of consciousness (NCC) by comparing the brain response to different perceptual outcomes of a visual threshold stimulus: when it is consciously perceived, both early sensory (P1), perceptual (VAN) and post-perceptual (LP) ERP components are stronger. Because the brain is inextricably linked with the body, cyclic variations of bodily signals can influence perceptual awareness. Baroreceptor activity (BRA) during the systolic cardiac phase interferes with sensory stimulus processing. BRA also increases during exhalation, which affects the detection of simple stimuli. To determine how the cardiac and respiratory phase affect awareness-related brain activity, we presented visual

stimuli at the discrimination threshold. We compared ERPs and their intracranial sources when subjects correctly identified the stimuli with and without awareness depending on the cardiac and respiratory phase. If a visual stimulus is presented when BRA is minimal (diastole and inhalation), the P1 is the earliest marker of awareness. While when BRA is stronger (systole and exhalation) the VAN is the earliest NCC. Statistics on the intracranial sources indicate that a visual stimulus reaches awareness differently if it is accompanied by BRA or not. Taken together, we show that bodily signals modulate the timing and the underlying mechanisms of awareness.

- Global program
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AUTOMATICALLY REJECT EEG ARTIFACTS BY DEFINING THE TIME WINDOW AND CHANNELS OF INTEREST. DON'T RELY SOLELY ON THE PEAK-TO-PEAK AMPLITUDE; ALSO CONSIDER THE MEAN AND THE SLOPE

Guillaume P. Pech ¹

¹ Université Libre de Bruxelles, Center for Research in Cognition and Neurosciences, Consciousness, Cognition and Computation lab, Belgium

Abstract

Removing artifacts at the epoch stage is one of the many problems that researchers face when using EEG. The literature varies from manual visual rejection to subjective or automatic thresholds rejection based on peak-to-peak amplitude. Here, a new approach is proposed that takes into account the final goal of the study, which is to extract ERPs in specific channels and time windows. Considering this final goal, we propose to focus only on the time and channels of interest to automatically

detect artifacts, as there is no justification to remove artifacts that precede or follow the event of interest. Moreover, instead of solely focusing on the peak-to-peak value, both the mean and the slope should also be considered in detecting these outliers, as they capture features of the signal. A Python code adapted to the MNE library is proposed to implement this approach.

EXPLORING THE ROLE OF SENSE OF OWNERSHIP IN DISHONEST BEHAVIOR: INSIGHTS FROM IMMERSIVE VIRTUAL REALITY AND ELECTROCORTICAL SIGNATURES

Giulio Piperno^{1,2,4}, M. Scattolin^{1,2}, S. Petkovic^{1,2}, R. Villa³, M. Panasiti^{1,2}, S. Aglioti^{1,2}

¹ Sapienza University of Rome, Department of Psychology, Italy ; ² Sapienza University of Rome, Italian Institute of Technology, Italy ; ³ University Medical Center Hamburg-Eppendorf, Department of Psychology, Germany ; ⁴ Ghent University, Department of Experimental Psychology, Belgium

Abstract

In a previous study, we found reduced Sense of Ownership (SoO) leads individuals to behave more dishonestly in their pursuit of high (versus low) rewards. This suggests that reductions in SoO may distance oneself from own immoral behavior, though the underlying neurocognitive mechanism remains unclear. In the current study, we ask participant (90 planned, 20 tested) to engage in a card game in which they have the possibility to increase their gains through deception. Participants control a virtual body presented from first-person perspective (1PP; high SoO) or third-person perspective (3PP; reduced SoO). To gain a deeper understanding of the underlying neurocognitive processes, we use EEG to measure

brain activity. Our goal is to determine whether the observed increase in dishonesty at lower SoO levels is associated with distinct perceptions of reward cues or, alternatively, emerges from differential neurocognitive mechanisms governing action implementation. To this end, we are focusing on the P300 following the presentation of reward cues and the readiness potential (RP) preceding decision-making. Our preliminary findings suggest both a greater RP difference between honest and dishonest decisions in the 1PP versus 3PP condition and an overall higher P300 cue-response in the 1PP compared to the 3PP condition.

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EXPECTATION EFFECTS ON REPETITION SUPPRESSION IN NOCICEPTION

Lisa-Marie G. Pohle¹, Ulrike Horn¹, Birgit Nierula¹, Falk Eippert¹

¹ Max Planck Institute for Human Cognitive and Brain Sciences, Germany

Abstract

Repetition suppression (RS), the reduced neural response to a repeated presentation of a stimulus, can be explained with a reduced prediction error for repetitions since they can be expected. However, evidence for this in the nociceptive domain remains inconclusive. To assess expectation effects on RS in nociception, we adapted an established paradigm from the auditory domain. Participants (N = 36) received short CO₂ laser stimuli (125 ms), which could be repeated after 1s or not. We explicitly varied the frequency of repetitions per block to render them expected or unexpected. EEG data was recorded and cleaned from eye movements and muscle artefacts via ICA and a spike detection tool, trials with remain-

ing artefacts were discarded. Time-frequency representations were obtained by fast-Fourier transformation. We observed a clear RS of the laser-evoked vertex potential (N₂P₂), which however was not modified by the induced expectations. Stimuli induced an oscillatory desynchronization in low frequency bands and characteristic gamma band oscillations (GBOs), the latter also showing RS. While our observation of RS not being modulated by expectations does not support prediction (error) explanations for RS in nociception, time-frequency representations suggest an expectation effect on GBOs. Proper statistical analysis of the data is still pending.

EFFECT OF IMPRISONMENT ON DECISION-MAKING : A LONGITUDINAL EEG STUDY ON CURRENT AND FORMER PRISONERS.

Victoria Rambaud ¹, I. Veeckman ², L. Favril ², T. Vander Beken ², E. Caspar ¹

¹ Ghent University, Department of Experimental Psychology, The Moral & Social Brain Lab, Belgium ; ² Ghent University, Department of Criminology, Criminal Law and Social Law, Institute for International Research on Criminal Policy, Belgium

Abstract

Statistical learning (SL) refers to the ability to extract regularities from the sensory environment, which typically occurs without explicit awareness. Behavioural research has long acknowledged the importance of SL in a wide range of cognitive domains such as language and visual perception. More recently, an EEG-based measure of SL has been introduced that quantifies the amount of neural entrainment (or phase locking) to the temporal structure created by patterns embedded in the sensory input relative to the presentation rate of the individual stimuli: an increase at the pattern rate and a decrease at the individual rate indi-

cates pattern learning. Whereas it provides a promising online and implicit way of measuring SL, it is still unknown what exactly is reflected in this measure. Does it merely reflect differentiation in the neural response to predictable and unpredictable stimuli, or is there more to it? In this EEG study, our aims are (1) to replicate the neural entrainment effect in a visual SL task and (2) to better understand what underlies this effect by combining spectral analysis with ERP analysis, neural decoding and simulations. I will present the study design, simulations and initial empirical results.

- Global program
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WHAT DRIVES THE NEURAL ENTRAINMENT EFFECT IN VISUAL STATISTICAL LEARNING

Liesa Ravijts ¹, Louisa Bogaerts ¹

¹ Ghent University, Department of Experimental Psychology, Belgium

Abstract

Statistical learning (SL) refers to the ability to extract regularities from the sensory environment, which typically occurs without explicit awareness. Behavioural research has long acknowledged the importance of SL in a wide range of cognitive domains such as language and visual perception. More recently, an EEG-based measure of SL has been introduced that quantifies the amount of neural entrainment (or phase locking) to the temporal structure created by patterns embedded in the sensory input relative to the presentation rate of the individual stimuli: an increase at the pattern rate and a decrease at the individual rate indicates

pattern learning. Whereas it provides a promising online and implicit way of measuring SL, it is still unknown what exactly is reflected in this measure. Does it merely reflect differentiation in the neural response to predictable and unpredictable stimuli, or is there more to it? In this EEG study, our aims are (1) to replicate the neural entrainment effect in a visual SL task and (2) to better understand what underlies this effect by combining spectral analysis with ERP analysis, neural decoding and simulations. I will present the study design, simulations and initial empirical results.

THE INTERPLAY OF SPONTANEOUS PUPIL SIZE FLUCTUATIONS AND ALPHA POWER IN DETECTION OF NEAR-THRESHOLD VISUAL STIMULI

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Abstract

Larger pupils are associated with improved performance in visual detection tasks, often attributed to changes in level of arousal as indexed by pupil size. However, changes in pupil size also affect the amount and focus of light on the retina, potentially influencing detection independently of arousal. The goal of our project was to gain a better understanding of how pupil size and neural activity (as measured with EEG) are related to each other and to performance in a visual detection task. This work is exploratory in nature, and thus, no specific hypotheses were formulated beforehand. We collected EEG and pupil data from 15 participants while they performed a task

consisting of detecting faint stimuli briefly flashed in peripheral vision. Stimulus parameters (contrast and spatial frequency) were adjusted with a staircase procedure to fix performance at 65% accuracy. Preliminary results show that larger pupils are linked to better detection performance, as we have shown before. Further, pupil size is positively correlated with power in the alpha band in the pre-stimulus period. However, alpha power itself is not significantly correlated with performance. We plan to continue with a decoding analysis and structural equation modeling to account for arousal as a latent variable.

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DISTINGUISHING ATTENTION IN DAILY MAP TASKS FROM UNIQUE EYE TRACKING AND EEG SIGNATURES

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Abstract

Cartographic maps are ubiquitous in space activities such as localization, navigation, and travel exploration. However, understanding how the attention interacts with maps remains a challenge. Research to date has focused on the overt aspects of map users' cognitive processes, using conventional empirical methods and eye tracking, but the covert aspects (e.g., brain activity) have been largely neglected. In this study, participants used Google Maps for four everyday tasks: global search, distance comparison, route following, and route planning. We recorded and analyzed user's attention-related visual (eye movement measures by eye tracking) and electrophysiological (fixation-evoked P3-ERP and task-induced alpha/theta ERD/ERS by scalp elec-

troencephalograms) responses. Results demonstrated efficient visual processing and expanded spatial exploration in global search and distance comparison tasks. Interestingly, more attentional resources were devoted to recognizing whether information matches or not in global search tasks, as shown by the larger P3 component for the map target. In contrast, route following and route planning tasks required intensified attention for information decoding and complicated cognitive processes, focusing predominantly on pertinent narrow map regions. Our findings highlight that the visual and electrophysiological signatures effectively capture the heterogeneity of user attention during different map tasks.

Local workshops & tutorials

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PREPROCESSING IN MNE

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MACHINE LEARNING FOR EEG

Raquel London¹

¹ Ghent University, Faculty of Psychology and Educational Sciences,
Department of Experimental Psychology, Belgium

MULTIVARIATE PATTERN ANALYSIS WITH HIDDEN SEMI-MARKOV MODELS

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Los Angeles

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Local symposia

MACHINE LEARNING AND EEG

SESSION 1: COMPUTATIONAL TOOLS AND PIPELINES FOR ML ANALYSIS

Chair : Richard Leahy, University of Southern California, CA, USA

TALK 1: MACHINE LEARNING AND THE BIDS EEG DATA FORMAT

Arnaud Delorme¹

¹ *University of California, San Diego, USA*

TALK 2: CREATING DEPLOYABLE WORKFLOWS FOR EEG SIGNAL PROCESSING AND ML/DL USING NEUROTYPE

Tim Mullen¹

¹ *Intheon Lab, San Diego, USA*

TALK 3: WORKLOAD ESTIMATION USING BRAIN- AND BIO- SIGNALS FOR ADAPTIVE TRAINING SYSTEM

Ivan Tashev¹

¹ *Microsoft Research, Redmond, USA*

TALK 4: AI/ML Enhances Dynamic Brain Imaging from EEG/MEG

Bin He¹

¹ *Carnegie Mellon University, USA*

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SESSION 2: SELF SUPERVISED LEARNING

Chair : Takfarinas Medani, University of Southern California, CA, USA

TALK 1: UNSUPERVISED MULTIVARIATE TIME-SERIES TRANSFORMERS FOR SEIZURE IDENTIFICATION ON EEG

Dominique Duncan¹

¹ University of Southern California, USA

TALK 2: NEURO-GPT: A FOUNDATION MODEL PRETRAINED ON LARGE-SCALE EEG DATA

Wenhui Cui¹

¹ University of Southern California, USA

SESSION 3: MACHINE LEARNING FOR BRAIN COMPUTER INTERFACES

Chair : Shrikanth Narayanan, University of Southern California, CA, USA

TALK 1: A HIGH PERFORMANCE NEUROPROSTHESIS FOR SPEECH DECODING AND AVATAR CONTROL

Alexander Silva¹

¹ University of California, San Francisco, USA

TALK 2: AI-POWERED NEXT-GENERATION NEUROTECHNOLOGIES

Maryam Shanechi¹

¹ University of Southern California, USA

TALK 3: RECONSTRUCTING PINK FLOYD FROM HUMAN AUDITORY CORTEX

Ludovic Bellier¹

¹ University of California, Berkeley, USA

SESSION 4: MACHINE LEARNING FOR NEUROLOGICAL DISORDERS

Chair : Kristina Lerman, University of Southern California, CA, USA

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TALK 1: MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS FOR ELECTROMAGNETIC BRAIN IMAGING IN DEMENTIA

Srikantan Nagarajan¹

¹ University of California, San Francisco, USA

TALK 2: GRAPH REPRESENTATION LEARNING OF MEG SIGNALS OPENS A WINDOW TO AGING TRAJECTORIES AND ALZHEIMER'S DISEASE

Dimitrios Pantazis¹

¹ Massachusetts Institute of Technology, USA

TALK 3: INTER-INDIVIDUAL DIFFERENCES IN NEUROPHYSIOLOGY VARY WITH AGE AND DISEASE

Jason da Silva Castanheira¹

¹ McGill University, Canada

Panel discussions

THE ROLE OF FOUNDATIONAL MODELS IN SPONTANEOUS AND EVENT-RELATED EEG

Chair : Shrikanth Narayanan, University of Southern California, CA, USA
Kristina Lerman, University of Southern California, CA, USA

Panelists

Alexander Silva, University of California, San Francisco, USA

Maryam Shanechi, University of Southern California, USA

Ludovic Bellier, University of California, Berkeley, USA

Srikantan Nagarajan, University of California, San Francisco, USA

Dimitrios Pantazis, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, USA

Arnaud Delorme, University of California, San Diego, USA

Ivan Tashev, Microsoft Research, Redmond, USA

Richard Leahy, University of Southern California, CA, USA

Local workshops & tutorials

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INTRODUCTION AND OVERVIEW OF BRAINSUITE

David Shattuck¹

¹ *University of California, Los Angeles, CA, USA*

BRAINSUITE TOOLS & DISCUSSION

Anand Joshi¹

¹ *University of Southern California, CA, USA*

INTRODUCTION TO EEG/MEG ANALYSIS

Richard Leahy¹

¹ *University of Southern California, CA, USA*

BRAINSTORM HANDS-ON TUTORIAL

Raymundo Cassani¹, **Takfarinas Medani**²

¹ *University of McGill, Canada*

² *University of Southern California, CA, USA*

More details for the workshop and the LA Garden can be found here:

<https://neuroimage.usc.edu/brainstorm/WorkshopLA2023>

Lyon

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Local symposia

BETTER SCIENCE

Link to live capture

Chair : Alexandra Corneyllie, CNRS, Lyon Neuroscience Research Center, France

OPEN SCIENCE: A DYNAMIC ECOSYSTEM

Gaëlle Leroux¹

¹ CNRS, Lyon Neuroscience Research Center, France

ECOLOGICAL EMERGENCY: WHAT LABS CAN('T) DO

Maximilien Chaumon¹

¹ CNRS, Institut du Cerveau et de la Moelle épinière, France

MEG OPM

Link to live capture

Chair : Denis Schwartz, INSERM, Lyon Neuroscience Research Center, France

OPPORTUNITIES FOR OPM NEUROSCIENCE

Gareth Barnes¹

¹ University College London, Imaging Neuroscience, United Kingdom

THE 4HE-OPM: FIRST NEUROSCIENCE APPLICATIONS

Tjerk Gutteling¹

¹ University of Birmingham, United Kingdom

INTERICTAL SPIKES WITH HELIUM OPM & INTRA-EEG

Christian Benar^{1,2}

¹ Aix-Marseille Université, Institut de Neurosciences des Systèmes, France

² INSERM, UMR_S 1106, 13005 Marseille, France

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ADVANCED CLINICS

Link to live capture

Chair : Olivier Bertrand, INSERM, Lyon Neuroscience Research Center, France

ADVANCED TOOLBOX FOR sEEG

Jean Philippe Lachaux¹

¹ INSERM, Lyon Neuroscience Research Center, France

DEEP LEARNING METH. FOR EPILEPTIC SPIKE DETECTION IN MEG

Pauline Mouchès¹

¹ INSERM, Lyon Neuroscience Research Center, France

BAYESIAN THEORIES OF PERCEPTION IN AUTISM

Francoise Lecaigard¹

¹ INSERM, Lyon Neuroscience Research Center, France

EEG METRICS TO ASSESS CONSCIOUSNESS DYNAMICS

Florent Gobert¹

¹ HCL, UCBLyon1, Lyon Neuroscience Research Center, France

COMAS (DECODING, MACHINE LEARNING)

Marzia De Lucia¹

¹ Laboratoire de Recherche en Neuroimagerie, University Hospital (CHUV) and University of Lausanne (UNIL), Switzerland

CAN BCI HELP CONSCIOUSNESS DISORDERS?

Perrine Séguin¹

¹ INSERM, Lyon Neuroscience Research Center, France

NEURAL COMMUNICATION

Link to live capture

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Chair : Mathilde Bonnefond, INSERM, Lyon Neuroscience Research Center, France

MODELING THE COMPLEXITY OF BRAIN OSCILLATIONS

Matteo Di Volo¹

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DO TRAVELLING WAVES REFLECT PREDICTIVE CODING PROCESSES?

Andrea Alamia¹

¹ Brain and Cognition Research Center (CerCo), Toulouse, France

NEURAL DYNAMICS AND CORTICAL HIERARCHY

Julien Vezoli¹

¹ Ernst Strüngmann Institute (ESI) for Neuroscience in Cooperation with the Max Planck Society, Frankfurt, Germany

NETWORK COMMUNICATION BASED ON NESTED RHYTHMS

Mathilde Bonnefond¹

¹ INSERM, Lyon Neuroscience Research Center, France

SATELLITE: SENSORIMOTOR BRAIN RHYTHMS: FOUNDATIONS AND APPLICATIONS

Chair : Jérémie Mattout, INSERM, Lyon Neuroscience Research Center, France

MOTOR IMAGERY

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SENSORIMOTOR OSCILLATIONS: RELATION TO EXCITABILITY & FUNCTIONAL SIGNIFICANCE

Vadim Nikulin¹

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ERD/ERS MODULATIONS IN BCI

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MOTOR IMAGERY-BASED BCIS FOR DECODING AND RESTORING THE BRAIN

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² Faculté de Médecine et des Sciences de la Santé, Université de Sherbrooke, Québec J1H 5N4, Canada

THE AVANCER TRIAL

Claudia Bigoni ¹

¹ Defitech Chair of Clinical Neuroengineering, Neuro-X Institute (INX) and Brain Mind Institute (BMI), Geneva, Switzerland

SOURCES & ROLES OF MOTOR CORTICAL LOW/HIGH BETA RHYTHMS

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BETA BURSTS: DETECTION AND FUNCTION

James Bonaiuto ¹

¹ Institut des Sciences Cognitives Marc Jeannerod, CNRS UMR 5229, Bron, France

DECODING BETA BURSTS FOR BCI

Sotiris Papadopoulos ¹

¹ Institut des Sciences Cognitives Marc Jeannerod, CNRS UMR 5229, Bron, France

Local workshops & tutorials

MNE-PYTHON

MNE INTRODUCTION

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MNE DECODING

Romain Quentin ¹, **Pauline Mouchès** ¹

¹ INSERM, Institut du Cerveau et de la Moelle épinière, France

Technical assistants

Alexandra Corneyllie¹, Samuel Garcia¹

¹ CNRS, Lyon Neuroscience Research Center, France

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Posters

THERE'S LIFE IN THAT OLD MEG YET: DEPTH ELECTRODE-LIKE LAMINAR SOURCE RECONSTRUCTION WITH HIGH PRECISION MEG.

Maciej J Szul^{1,2}, Suvadeep Maiti^{1,2}, Ishita Agarwal^{1,2}, Siqi Zhang^{1,2}, Gareth R Barnes³, Sven Bestmann⁴, James J Bonaiuto^{1,2}

¹ DANC Lab, ISC Marc Jeannerod, UMR 5229, Bron, France ; ² Université Claude Bernard Lyon 1, Lyon, France ;

³ Wellcome Department of Imaging Neuroscience, UCL Queen Square Institute of Neurology, London, UK ;

⁴ Sobell Department of Motor Neuroscience, UCL Queen Square Institute of Neurology, London, UK

Abstract

Simulations have shown that MEG is capable of localising brain signals with laminar precision, given high enough levels of data quality, and these levels are achievable with high precision, head-cast MEG. Previous laminar source reconstruction efforts used two surfaces, representing deep and superficial layers. One of these approaches used a sliding time window model comparison for temporally resolved laminar inference, limiting its applicability across experimental conditions, and limiting inference to whether activity is strongest in deep or superficial layers. Here we aimed to provide a more complete picture of neural dynamics across cortical layers. A depth electrode-like source space was created by generating 11 equidistant layers between the white matter and pial surfaces, with vertices matched across layers. We then applied the Empirical Bayesian Beamformer to visual and motor ERFs from high precision, head-cast MEG data. This yielded, for each pial surface vertex, 11 source time series at diffe-

rent laminar depths. We then applied two analyses to these series: a current source density (CSD) transform, revealing temporally dynamic current sources and sinks, and a relative power analysis, thought to be a marker of the boundary between deep and superficial layers. The boundaries of current source and sink patterns tightly corresponded to the estimated thickness of each cortical layer as estimated from the BigBrain histological atlas. Moreover, alpha/beta power was strongest in deep layers and gamma in superficial layers, and the crossover point of relative alpha/beta and gamma power was correlated with the estimated depth of layer IV from the BigBrain atlas. Multilaminar source localisation with high precision MEG is possible and extremely promising. Contrary to sparse sampling of intracranial electrodes, laminar MEG has the potential to non-invasively and globally test hypotheses about cortical layer dynamics.

BURSTING WITH POTENTIAL: HOW SENSORIMOTOR BETA BURSTS DEVELOP FROM INFANCY TO ADULTHOOD

Rayson, H^{1,2}, **Szul, MJ**^{1,2}, **El-Khoueiry, P**^{1,2}, **Debnath, R**³, **Gautier-Martins, M**^{1,2}, **Ferrari, PF**^{1,2}, **Fox, N**⁴, **Bonaiuto, JJ**^{1,2}

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Abstract

Beta activity is thought to play a critical role in sensorimotor processes, but little is known about how activity in this frequency band develops. Here, we investigated the developmental trajectory of sensorimotor beta activity from infancy to adulthood. We recorded electroencephalography (EEG) from 9-month-olds, 12-month-olds, and adults while they observed and executed grasping movements. We analysed 'beta burst' activity using a novel method that combines time-frequency decomposition and principal component analysis (PCA). We then examined the changes in burst rate and waveform motifs along the selected principal components. Our results reveal systematic changes in beta activity during action execution across development. We found a decrease in beta

burst rate during movement execution in all age groups, with the greatest decrease observed in adults. Additionally, we identified four principal components that defined waveform motifs that systematically changed throughout the trial. We found that bursts with waveform shapes closer to the median waveform were not rate-modulated, whereas those with waveform shapes further from the median were differentially rate-modulated. Interestingly, the decrease in the rate of certain burst motifs occurred earlier during movement and was more lateralized in adults than in infants, suggesting that the rate modulation of specific types of beta bursts becomes increasingly refined with age.

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MULTI-SCALE PARAMETERIZATION OF PERIODIC NEURAL ACTIVITY WITH LAGGED HILBERT COHERENCE

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Abstract

Background: Analysis of neural activity in various frequency bands is ubiquitous in systems and cognitive neuroscience. Recent analytical breakthroughs and theoretical developments rely on phase maintenance of oscillatory signals or a clean separation in power between aperiodic and periodic activity, without considering whether or not such assumptions are met. Lagged coherence, the coherence between a signal and itself

at increasing temporal delays, has been proposed as a way to quantify the rhythmicity, or periodicity, of a signal. However, current lagged coherence algorithms suffer from poor spectral accuracy and resolution, aliasing effects that become more pronounced at higher frequencies, and conflation with amplitude covariation, especially in frequency ranges in which the signal power is low.

Methods: We introduce a continuous lagged coherence metric, lagged Hilbert coherence, that addresses these shortcomings by using multiplication in the frequency domain for precise bandpass filtering, instantaneous analytic signals via the Hilbert transform, and thresholding using the amplitude covariation of surrogate data generated by an autoregressive model.

Results: We show that this version of lagged coherence yields vastly higher spectral accuracy and resolution than previous versions, and demonstrate how it can be used to 1) examine the

relationship between mean frequency-specific rhythmicity and response time, 2) improve parameterization of the aperiodic and periodic components of power spectral densities, and 3) detect the occurrence of transient oscillatory bursts.

Implications: Lagged Hilbert coherence thus offers a significant toolset advancement for complex neurophysiological spectral analysis.

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SENSORIMOTOR BETA BURST DEVELOPMENT IN HUMAN INFANTS: A LONGITUDINAL MRI, EEG, AND BEHAVIORAL STUDY

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Abstract

Cortical motor activity in the beta frequency range (13–30Hz) is a hallmark signature of both healthy and pathological movement, but functional relevance remains unclear. Recent studies show that instead of oscillations, beta activity occurs in discrete transient bursts. Computational models of beta burst generation suggest that they result from precisely timed inputs to motor cortical circuits, but it is unknown from which regions these inputs originate. In addition, it has been proposed that bursts of beta activity in the sensorimotor cortex represent the activation of local cortical representations of motor goals, but this has not yet been tested. A longitudinal, within-subject investigation into the maturation of brain connectivity, beta burst activity, and motor development across early life is now crucial to address both of these questions concerning generation mechanisms and function of beta bursts. In infants' first year of life, the brain goes through significant structural and functional transformations as essential sensorimotor and cognitive milestones are achieved,

making this developmental period especially important for probing questions about beta activity. Our current longitudinal project is thus employing a variety of methods to examine and compare changes in brain structure, neurophysiology, and reaching-grasping movements across the first 12 months. We are conducting assessments at 3, 6, and 12 months with a large cohort of infants. These include a collection of anatomical and diffusion magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) data, resting-state functional magnetic resonance imaging (fMRI) data, electroencephalography (EEG) during motor execution task and behavioral measures of motor skill. This will allow us to monitor the progression of sensorimotor skills, along with their underlying neural correlates, including the relationship between changes in white matter microstructure, sensorimotor beta activity, and reaching and grasping movements.

PURSUING A NOVEL METHODOLOGY FOR EXPLORING BRAIN-BEHAVIOR-ENVIRONMENT INTERACTIONS IN NATURALISTIC SITUATIONS

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Abstract

Assessing consciousness in patients with altered states of consciousness remains a complex task. Approximately one-third of these patients exhibit cognitive-motor dissociation that current tools struggle to characterize.

To tackle this challenge, we propose the use of synchronized multimodal tools to study the intricate interactions among the brain, body, and environment.

In the pursuit of developing new methodologies, we conducted a study with conscious participants, during which we recorded their behavioral, cerebral, and cardiac activities in various naturalistic situations.

To evaluate behavior, we employed computer vision to extract fine-grained elements and utilized classification algorithms and explicability methods to identify behavioral signatures specific to each situation.

We are now investigating brain activity in relation

to behavioral outcomes and the environment at multiple levels:

At the first level, we will examine the links between the environment and cerebral activity by analyzing differences in dwPLI connectivity and local oscillations based on different situations.

At the second level, we will explore the brain-body-environment loop by examining correlations between participant behavior, cardiac activity, and EEG activity in different situations.

At the third level, we plan to develop an advanced AI model for optimal fusion of heterogeneous data, allowing us to study the temporal aspect of these correlations.

This approach will enhance our understanding of variations and the coupling of these different modalities in ecological contexts, thereby paving the way for new advancements in the evaluation of patients with altered states of consciousness.

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MYONSET: A PYTHON PACKAGE TO DETECT EMG ONSET FOR ELECTROPHYSIOLOGICAL STUDIES

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Abstract

Among brain's functions, selecting and executing actions is certainly one of the most important. In this research domain, investigating electromyographic (EMG) activity of muscles involved in actions execution can be an easy way to collect more information on processes of interest. Yet, once EMG is recorded, one needs to process and analyze EMG data in addition to other collected data

(e.g., behavior, electrophysiological recordings, etc). Particularly, the detection of EMG bursts onsets is often a critical processing step. However, few tools are available to achieve it, and none was really suitable to use in typical experimental designs of experimental psychology such as reaction time tasks. To meet this need, we developed MYOnset, a Python

package designed to help such EMG recordings processing, with particular attention given to the step of EMG bursts onsets and offsets detection. MYOnset integrates tools for standard preprocessing of EMG recordings, like bipolar derivation and filtering. Regarding EMG onset detection, MYOnset proposes a two-steps method: first, an automatic detection of EMG bursts onsets and offsets, second, a step of visualization and manual correction of detected onsets and offsets. MYOnset integrates two algorithms combining different automatic detection methods. Further, MYOnset proposes a specific window for the visualization and manual correction step, which the most time-consuming step and for which no tool was

available. This window offers an adapted view for EMG signals and the associated markers, i.e., experimental triggers and EMG onsets and offsets automatically detected. Importantly, user can interact with onset and offset markers to adjust onsets/offsets positions, insert new onsets/offsets, and remove existing onsets/offsets.

MYOnset package is available on PyPI (<https://pypi.org/project/myonset/>) and GitHub (<https://github.com/lspieser/myonset>).

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SEEING SPEECH: DECODING THE TIMECOURSE OF CUED SPEECH PERCEPTION

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Abstract

Most alphabets are based on the visual coding of phonemes and syllables. However, other visual codes were developed for use by deaf people for conveying visually the sounds of speech. Cued Speech (CS) allows to specify syllables through a combination of lips configuration, hand location relative to the face, and hand shape (Cornett, 1967). Numerous studies now support the idea that Cued Speech represents a judicious choice for people choosing the oralist approach (learning a spoken rather than a sign language) for their child (Hage & Leybaert, 2005; Trezek, 2017). Indeed, the use of this communication system has been found to improve general linguistic abilities, and reading in particular, in a deaf community characterized by a low average level of literacy. By contrast, only a few studies have assessed the mechanisms of CS perception.

We are therefore using EEG to elucidate the time-course of the cerebral mechanisms of CS perception and, critically, identify the multiple codes

under which CS may be represented across the brain. Particular attention is devoted to comparing the cerebral mechanisms of cued speech perception with the cerebral mechanisms of reading.

For this end, we presented a set of 16 syllables, in the CS form (experiment 1) or in the written form (experiment 2) to deaf CS users, hearing CS users and hearing CS naïve participants. We plan to decode the 4 types of CS cues (hand position, hand shape, vocalic information from lip reading and consonant information from lip reading), and study how those elementary codes are combined into higher-level representations (decoding of vowel and consonant identity, assessment of the mutual independence of codes, etc). The same logic applies for the analysis of written syllables data. Moreover, in order to study the computation of representations independent from input format, we plan to use "cross-decoding" between the CS and written modalities.

PREDICTING THE CLINICAL UTILITY OF DEEP BRAIN STIMULATION ELECTRODE CONTACTS BASED ON THEIR ELECTROPHYSIOLOGICAL SIGNATURE

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Schnitzler, A ¹, Hirschmann, J ¹

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Abstract

Motivation

Deep brain stimulation (DBS) is a well-established therapy for movement disorders like Parkinson's disease (PD). It is as a crucial alternative when pharmacotherapy produces side effects or when symptoms resist drug treatment. Yet, finding optimal DBS parameters remains a complex task demanding substantial time and effort.

Aims

Our goal was to predict the DBS electrode contact yielding the best clinical outcome when used for therapeutic stimulation. Thereby, we hope to automate contact recommendations for DBS programming and to uncover relationships between symptoms and electrophysiological markers.

Methods

We used Extreme Gradient-Boosted tree learning on electrophysiological data from simultaneous magnetoencephalography and local field potential recordings from the subthalamic nucleus (STN) of 45 PD patients measured in resting state. STN power and STN-cortex coherence in various frequency bands were extracted to predict the

therapeutic window and side effect threshold for each electrode contact.

Results

Actual and predicted values were strongly correlated for therapeutic window ($r=0.76$, $p < 0.001$) and side effect threshold ($r=0.66$, $p < 0.001$). Our automated feature selection exhibited a preference for the low-beta and high-beta frequency bands, with a focus on frontal, parietal, and temporal areas contralateral to the STN. Comparing the cumulative hit rate between predicted and randomly shuffled contact rankings indicated that our approach would afford a significant time advantage if applied to DBS programming in practice ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion

This study demonstrates the feasibility of predicting the optimal DBS contact based on electrophysiological features. When used in conjunction with DBS systems equipped for brain activity recordings, our approach has the potential to save neurologists considerable time in DBS programming.

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GLOBAL MEASURES OF LOCALLY INDUCED TRAVELING WAVES USING M/EEG

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Abstract

Identifying and examining spatially localized, small scale brain dynamics using global metrics like magneto- or electro-encephalography (M/EEG) is notoriously difficult. Not only can the

chosen measurement method blur and distort intricate details, but factors like volume conduction and spectral aliasing in both the temporal and spatial domains can

potentially obscure genuine characteristics or, worse yet, introduce artifactual ones. In the (non-invasive) study of cortical traveling waves, i.e., oscillatory or transient changes in electromagnetic activity that propagate over portions of the cortex, there has been some debate about the authenticity of detected wave-like patterns. Such debate questions the feasibility of reliably observing and characterizing mesoscopic (i.e., intra-regional) traveling waves through extra-cranial recordings. To address this, we take advantage of the well-established retinotopic organization of the early visual cortex (V1). By employing calibrated visual stimulation, we induce a traveling wave with controlled characteristics in V1. Sub-

sequently, we investigate the reliability of recovering these properties from M/EEG simultaneous recordings.

We use a range of traveling wave analysis methods, including optical flow analysis and 2D

Fourier transforms and find that the approaches differ significantly in their ability to recover the parameters of the input wave. Together, our study demonstrates the need for careful consideration of the analysis methods when interested in fine spatio-temporal brain dynamics.

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EEG CORRELATES OF HUMAN-RHYTHM INTERACTION

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Abstract

In the metaverse, a clear trend exists towards creating a virtual world with seamless, intuitive interactions, facilitated by immersive and interactive environments. To maintain this immersion in any interaction, including those with music and rhythm, it is vital to capture the user's sensation and experience during their engagement. Beyond physical inputs like motion, brain activity and bio-synchronization can serve as a valuable tool for analyzing this overall user experience.

For instance, neural entrainment, the synchronization of neural oscillations to external rhythmic stimuli, offers a promising avenue to study and characterize these interactions. However, despite its significance in neuroscience, accurately quantifying entrainment non-invasively and precise interpretation of experience and sensation remains a challenging endeavor.

This poster presents a finger-tapping experiment designed to explore potential brain markers in relation to tapping synchronization and corresponding questionnaire responses. The aim

is to pinpoint biological indicators of a good human-rhythm interaction and, in doing so, to identify entrainment and user experience.

In our experiment, subjects synchronized or complemented their tapping to an auditory presented rhythm across multiple beat patterns. We assessed both spectral band activity and the low-frequency rhythm content of EEG activity, examining these aspects both locally over time and across the experiment. To distinguish sensorimotor and perceptual EEG activity, two spatial filters based on localizer trials are applied, enabling separate analysis of their responses.

The quality of the rhythm interaction is determined based on the physical performance, questionnaires and incorporates the theory of human embodiment within music interactions. Ultimately, the significance of this research lies in expanding the immersive nature of VR environments and sustaining this immersion during a music interaction.

DOES A SHIFT IN MENTAL TIME TRANSLATE INTO A SHIFT IN HIPPOCAMPAL DELTA OSCILLATIONS?

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Abstract

Through mental time travel (MTT), humans can explore past events or possible futures. One hypothesis is that humans build flexible temporal cognitive maps of the position of events in time (Gauthier & van Wassenhove, 2016a; 2016b). Spatial cognitive maps arise in the hippocampal-entorhinal circuit (Moser et al., 2015), where the sequence of neural assemblies on the phase of θ oscillations maps the animal's past, present and future positions (Dragoi & Buzsaki, 2006). Previous studies have shown the implication of the hippocampal-entorhinal system (Gauthier & van Wassenhove, 2016a; 2016b; Gauthier et al., 2019; Gauthier et al., 2020), and of δ oscillations for MTT (Prabhu & van Wassenhove, submitted). Yet, the computation of temporal distances remains to be characterized. In a novel paradigm, participants projected themselves to different times in the past or future. They were then shown historical events, and had to report as fast as possible whether the event had already happened,

or had yet to happen, with respect to their temporal position (Wagelmans & van Wassenhove, in prep.). The further away in time the participants imagined themselves to be, the slower their reaction times were. This behavioral shift grounds the hypothesis of a shift in the amplitude of evoked responses and the phase of δ oscillations. Herein, we adapted this task to MEG (N = 30). Data has been collected. We aim to show a gradient of evoked response amplitude: from the lowest amplitude for the greatest distance in the past, to the highest amplitude for the future. Then we will assess the inter-trial phase coherence of the δ oscillation for each distance. We aim to show that for larger distances in the past, the δ oscillation aligns on earlier phases; and for the future, the δ oscillation aligns to later phases. Thus, we will be able to map self position in time onto the δ oscillation phase. Finally, we will realign the MEG recordings and the aMRI to reconstruct the sources of neural activity.

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SIZING UP TIME: EEG DECODING OF DURATION PRODUCTION IN VIRTUAL ENVIRONMENTS OF VARYING SIZE

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Abstract

When, where, and how duration is encoded in the brain? This project aims at uncovering how the brain represents time and how this representation is influenced by environmental constraints. To this end, we manipulated environmental constraints in virtual reality (i.e., size of the room, height of the ceiling) and combined behavioural measures of duration perception and production with electrophysiological recordings to characterise the underlying neural activity. Behavioural results revealed that participants pro-

duced longer durations in large environments, as compared to smaller ones. We then used time-resolved multivariate decoding approaches, which consists in training classifiers at specific time points and testing them at every other time points to understand the dynamic neural code underlying these effects. By using electrophysiological measurements and decoding algorithms, we sought to identify the cerebral topography associated with time perception.

DOES THE FREQUENCY OF FEEDBACK DISPLAY IN ELECTROENCEPHALOGRAPHIC NEUROFEEDBACK PROTOCOLS MODIFY THE SPECTRAL POWER OF THE TARGET FREQUENCY-BANDS?

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Abstract

The present methodological study investigates whether the continuous modification of the visual feedback presentation in electroencephalographic neurofeedback (EEG-NF) protocols influences the spectral power of the frequency bands targeted in these protocols. The current EEG study reproduces classic EEG-NF conditions in healthy young adults without being a neurofeedback task (i.e., controlling one's own brain activity). Participants simply have to stare at a grey circle that appears in the center of a screen and changes size at a manipulated frequency rate. Contrary to an EEG-NF session, the circle size variations are not guided by the online measure of the EEG frequency bands power (as in most EEG-NF protocols), but randomly generated from the distribution of real EEG frequency-bands variations previously collected. Here, we investigate whether the frequency of stimulus modification can influence EEG bands power as if participants

were involved in an EEG-NF session. To this end, the grey circle size can vary at different frequencies: 1 Hz, 5 Hz, 10 Hz, or no-change (control). We use an open-friendly BCI tool to simultaneously record EEG data from Fz, Cz and Pz scalp positions. After data collection and pre-processing, we extract the spectral power of the most commonly used EEG frequency-bands in EEG-NF: theta (~4-8 Hz), alpha (~8-12 Hz), and beta (~12-30 Hz) bands. We hypothesize that the frequency at which visual information is modified could affect the frequency bands spectral power we are targeting. For instance, visual changes at 10Hz could artificially induce an increase in the power of the alpha band (but not the others). These methodological manipulations could thus provide essential information about neglected dimensions in EEG-NF protocols.

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NEURAL CORRELATES OF MOTOR MEMORY REACTIVATION: A MULTIMODAL NEUROIMAGING STUDY INVESTIGATING PHASE-DEPENDENT SLEEP OSCILLATION STIMULATION

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Abstract

Targeted memory reactivation (TMR) enhances memory consolidation during sleep. Based on evidence that brain excitability fluctuates with sleep slow oscillations (SO) phases, we hypothesized that the effect of TMR on consolidation depends on the stimulated phase of the SO. A sophisticated closed-loop TMR procedure was applied at two different SO phases (up vs. down) to test our hypothesis. 31 healthy participants performed an audio-motor sequence learning task (3 motor sequences learned) during which brain activity was recorded with fMRI. Training and retest on the task were separated by a night of sleep during which closed-loop auditory TMR was applied while brain activity was monitored with EEG. Results show that TMR time-locked to the SO-down phase resulted in performance deterioration as compared to up and no stimulation. EEG data revealed that up-stimulated SWs showed higher amplitude and greater sigma power at the SO peak. fMRI data indicate that, overnight increases in striatal activity were greater for the up- as compared to down- and not-reactivated conditions. These striatal increases were related to greater SO amplitude du-

ring the post-learning night and to greater gains in performance. Last, connectivity analyses indicate that the beneficial effect of up stimulation on motor performance was paralleled by more network segregation (i.e., a decrease in connectivity) in hippocampo-motor networks.

In the down- and not-reactivated conditions, hippocampal activity decreased overnight more than in the up-condition. The greater the hippocampal decrease, the poorer the gains in performance. Connectivity analyses show an overnight increase in striato-hippocampo-motor connectivity that was related to poorer performance and smaller sleep oscillations.

Our results suggest that CL-TMR induced phase-specific modulations of (i) motor performance, (ii) brain activity and connectivity and (iii) sleep oscillations characteristics that were all inter-related.

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OPTIMAL THETA-GAMMA COUPLING FOR BURSTING OSCILLATIONS

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Abstract

Coherent oscillations of neural activity are ubiquitous across brain spatial and temporal scales and have been associated with the formation of sensory or behavioral representations [1]. Refined experimental techniques report today a new complexity of this oscillatory activity, especially in the gamma (30-100 Hz) band. Indeed, the frequency of these oscillations shows a large variability through time [2], questioning the classical view of γ oscillations being separated into different frequency bands. Oscillations appear instead in bursts characterised by rapid, synchronous neu-

ronal firing. This is difficult to reconcile with often employed massive trial averages or with predictions from simplified computational models. In this work, I will present a new mechanisms for the emergence of bursting gamma oscillations, based on chaotic attractors in spiking networks of excitatory and inhibitory neurons. We also employ a neural mass model to reduce the dimensionality of the network, allowing us to discover a rich repertoire of dynamical phases, from bistable regimes to classical PING periodic oscillations to gamma bursts.

We then study the Phase Amplitude Coupling (PAC) of gamma oscillations with a theta forcing across the phase space of the model. We show that PAC is maximum at the edge of this new bursting gamma region. This demonstrates that chaotic oscillatory bursts are capable of boosting information transfer between different neural rhythms. Altogether, we present a theoretical framework to explore the mechanisms of theta-gamma PAC and their relation with the activation of neuronal ensembles.

[1] Wang, X. J. *Physiol Rev* 90, 1195-1268 (2010).
 [2] Douchamps, V., Di Volo, M., Torcini, A., Battaglia, D., & Goutagny, R. (2022). *bioRxiv*, 2022-10.

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HYBRID CNN-GCNN APPROACH FOR EPILEPTIC INTERICTAL SPIKE DETECTION IN MEG RECORDINGS

Thibaut Dejean¹, Pauline Mouches¹, Julien Jung¹, Romain Bouet¹, Romain Quentin¹

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Abstract

This poster introduces a novel hybrid Convolutional Neural Network-Graph Convolutional Neural Network (CNN-GCNN) approach for the precise detection of interictal spikes in epilepsy using Magnetoencephalography (MEG) recordings. While MEG has been historically instrumental in localizing interictal epileptic activities, manual identification and interpretation are often labor-intensive and require significant expertise. To bridge this gap, we propose a hybrid model that leverages the spatial relationships and localized features inherent in MEG data. The presented method consists of two main components: 1) a CNN architecture that initially extracts relevant spatial features from MEG waveforms, and 2) a GCNN structure that integrates these features, emphasizing the complex connectivity between sensors. This combination ensures that the model captures both the localized characteristics and overall network structure in the MEG recordings. The model was trained and validated using data from 95 patients, following a rigorous 10-fold cross-validation scheme. The preliminary

results demonstrate a promising mean F1-score of over 75% for a balanced dataset, with sensitivity and specificity rates of 76% and 80%, respectively. Further, a comparison of the hybrid CNN-GCNN model with other state of the art methods like FA-MED or EMSNET highlights its superiority in both efficiency and accuracy. This research's contributions lie not only in the introduction of a novel computational model but also in its potential to significantly enhance the efficiency, reliability, and cost-effectiveness of interictal spike detection in clinical MEG examinations. Future work will focus on spike form identification and clustering and a more extensive validation among a larger number of patients.

MEASURING COGNITIVE EFFORT: OBJECTIVE, SUBJECTIVE AND PHENOMENAL

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Abstract

Numerous markers of sympathetic activity track engagement in effortful mental tasks. How the phenomenal experience of cognitive effort is linked to arousal is less clear. We aim to clarify this by correlating self-reports of cognitive effort with the subjective reports and physiological indexes of arousal.

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DECODING MOTOR ADAPTATION FROM MEG DATA

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Abstract

Motor adaptation is a critical aspect of human motor control and has implications for stroke rehabilitation. However, the neural mechanisms underlying motor adaptation are not well understood. In this study, we investigated how the brain represents learning rate during motor adaptation using magnetoencephalography (MEG) in healthy participants performing center-out reaching movements with a joystick. We compared three computational models of motor adaptation with different learning rate mechanisms: constant, dynamic based on error variability, and dynamic based on error sign consistency. These models differ in how they account for the history of errors and their influence on the adaptation process. We decoded the model variables from MEG signals using source power comodulation (SPoC) coupled with back-to-back regression, a novel method

that allows us to disentangle partially correlated variables contributions and to select the most relevant brain regions and frequencies for decoding. We evaluated the decoding accuracy of the models across stable and random perturbation blocks, where participants had to adapt to a consistent or a random cursor feedback. Our results show that the model with dynamic learning rate based on error sign consistency has the highest decoding accuracy. Our study offers a novel method to compare motor adaptation models and thus elucidate neural mechanisms of motor adaptation. This work will improve the understanding of the role of error history in motor learning and may help to design optimal motor system-lesion rehabilitation strategies.

Montreal

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Local Talks

UNDERSTANDING AND MODULATING CONSCIOUSNESS IN THE HUMAN BRAIN: INSIGHTS FROM FUNCTIONAL CONNECTIVITY, CRITICALITY, AND COMPLEXITY

Catherine Duclos¹

¹ *University of Montreal, Canada*

ALTERNATIVE PERSPECTIVES ON PERSISTING CHALLENGES IN EEG (ARTIFACTS AND HAIR)

Helen J. Huang¹

¹ *University of Central Florida, USA*

CONNECTING BRAINS AND DISCIPLINES WITH HYPERSCANNING BIOFEEDBACK

Helen Suzanne Dikker¹

¹ *New York University, USA*

Panel discussions

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CRITICALITY, COMPLEXITY AND CONNECTIVITY: BASIC CONCEPTS AND APPLICATIONS TO CONSCIOUSNESS RESEARCH

Chair : Karim Jerbi, University of Montreal, Montréal, Canada
Charlotte Maschke, McGill University, Montréal, Canada

Panelists

JM Lina, École de Technologie Supérieure, Montréal, Canada

Catherine Duclos, University of Montreal, Montréal, Canada

Mohammad Yaghoubi, McGill University, Montréal, Canada

Jordan O'Byrne, University of Montreal, Montréal, Canada

Vanessa Hadid, McGill University, Montréal, Canada

MOBILEEEG AND REAL-TIME SIGNAL PROCESSING: NEUROFEEDBACK AND CREATIVE RESEARCH APPLICATIONS

Chair : Emily Coffey, Concordia University, Montréal, Canada
Yann Harel, University of Montreal, Montréal, Canada

Panelists

Nicolas Farrugia, IMT Atlantique, France

Helen J. Huang, University of Central Florida, USA

Suzanne Dikker, New York University, USA

Fabien Dal Maso, University of Montreal, Montréal, Canada

Antoine Bellemare Pépin, Concordia University, Montréal, Canada

RECENT TRENDS IN EEG HYPERSCANNING: FROM METHODS TO SOCIAL NEUROSCIENCE RESEARCH

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Chair : Sylvain Baillet, McGill University, Montréal, Canada
Lena Adel, McGill University, Montréal, Canada

Panelists

Guillaume Dumas, University of Montreal, Montréal, Canada

Caroline Palmer, McGill University, Montréal, Canada

Suzanne Dikker, New York University, USA

Lightning talks

MODULATION OF LOCOMOTION DYNAMICS USING PERSISTENT RHYTHMIC CUE SEQUENCES

Tou, Si Long (Jenny)¹; Chau, Tom

¹ *Univeristy of Toronto, Canada*

Abstract

The temporal intervals between successive movements during human locomotion tasks such as finger tapping exhibit non-uniform variations characterized by a structured pattern called "persistence". Deviation from this healthy pattern could lead to undesirable consequences, as a reduction in the persistence towards randomness in pathological gait is commonly observed. Coincidentally, persistence in EEG also change in the diseased brain compared to the health state.

In this study, we aim to investigate rhythmic cues simulated by a class of stationary Gaussian time series called fractional Gaussian noise, and their non-stationary integral fractional Brownian motion. The primary aim of this study is to establish the relationship between persistence levels of these rhythmic cues

and their effect of the persistence of finger tapping. The secondary aim is to identify EEG features that govern the persistence in human locomotion.

Thirty healthy adults aged 18 to 35 years will be recruited for one session of 1.5 hours. Participants tap their fingers to rhythmic cue sequences of a metronome or of 6 different persistence levels, quantified by their Hurst exponent. The rhythmic cue sequences, finger taps, and EEG brain waves are collected and analyzed.

Data collection is ongoing. Eight participants have completed the study. Preliminary data analysis has shown that the Hurst exponent of between-tap intervals is positively correlated with the Hurst exponent of rhythmic cues.

SHORT-TERM EFFECT OF MINDFULNESS MEDITATION ON EEG BCI PERFORMANCE IN A PEDIATRIC CONTEXT

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Abstract

Previous research has been shown benefits on the meditation in the pediatric context, such as calmness, focus and self-regulation. Children may experience difficulties maintaining focus using brain-computer interface (BCI). In this study, we investigated the short-term effects of mindfulness meditation on auditory-tactile P300-BCI performance in a pediatric context. Twelve able-bodied children aged 10 to 18 years were recruited for control (non-meditation) and study (meditation) sessions. Each session began with a 15-minute guided mindfulness segmented two blocks of 7.5 minutes into. After the mindfulness session, participants performed an auditory-tactile oddball task, while recording EEG data. P300 responses were elicited by presenting simultaneous audito-

ry and tactile stimuli from the same directional azimuth. A block comprised 10 runs, taking approximately 10 minutes to complete, and each data collection session consisted of 5 blocks, lasting approximately 2 hours. An average accuracy of $80.66\% \pm 11.68\%$ was achieved across participants without meditation, while five participants exhibited significantly improved accuracy following meditation training. Using time-frequency features and a Gaussian Naive Bayes classifier, meditative and rest states were differentiated with an accuracy of $83.94\% \pm 13.00\%$. A novel feature extraction method was introduced to detect P300 responses with variable latencies, providing valuable insights into the underlying cognitive processes.

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COGNITIVE LOADS MODERATE THE FACIAL EMOTION AND BODY POSTURE INTEGRATION. AN EVENT-RELATED POTENTIAL STUDY: PRELIMINARY RESULTS

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¹ *Université du Québec à Trois Rivières, Canada*

Abstract

We perceive emotions through several sensory channels (e.g., face, posture) interacting together, facilitating the emotional perception when they are congruent (similar across channels) compared to when they are incongruent (different). This contextual effect seems to be automatic, but studies call this into question. A process is automatic when it persists regardless of the availability of cognitive resources (efficiency), awareness and speed of processing (Moors & De Houwer.,2006). The aim of this study was to investigate the automaticity of the context effect at the cerebral le-

vel while manipulating efficiency. 27 participants (26+/-4.9 years) performed dual task involving a memory (of seven similar or different digits; cognitive load condition) and a recognition task (of the face or body emotion; focus condition) while cerebral and behavioural measures were recorded. GLMs show a main effect of cognitive load, focus and congruency for response time and congruency for accuracy ($p < 0.001$). Bayesian ANOVA shows substantial evidence of no interaction between congruence and cognitive load for behavioral measures ($BFs < 0.03$).

Massive univariate analyses on EEG data show greater P200 amplitude in the occipital and central regions when focus on facial emotion ($p < 0.05$), and during congruence ($p < 0.05$). Overall, these contextual effects appear to be processed automatically, in line with proposals suggesting the extracting rapidly emotional information from the environment.

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BASELINE BRAIN CRITICALITY PREDICTS PROPOFOL-INDUCED FUNCTIONAL CONNECTIVITY AND SIGNAL COMPLEXITY CHANGES IN DISORDERS OF CONSCIOUSNESS PATIENTS

Rosalie Girard Pepin¹, Guillermo Martinez Villar, Charles Gervais, Charlotte Maschke, Hanieh Bazregarzadeh, Stefanie Blain-Moraes, Catherine Duclos¹

¹ *Université de Montréal, Canada*

Abstract

Previous studies showed that GABA agonists could potentially have a therapeutic effect on the brain's functional properties in disorders of consciousness (DOC). We hypothesized that the brain's susceptibility to this effect would depend on its baseline critical state. Using high-density electroencephalography (hd-EEG), we assessed whether criticality (chaoticity, order parameter (OP), pair correlation function (PCF) and Lempel-Ziv complexity (LZC) prior to brief propofol anesthesia (Pre-Anesthesia) could forecast changes in brain functional connectivity metrics after propofol exposure DOC patients. We assessed changes in functional connectivity by comparing Pre-Anesthesia to Post-Anesthesia graph theoretical properties. Pre-Anesthesia chaoticity

was linked to changes in clustering ($r = -0.69$, $p = 0.008$) and small-worldness ($r = -0.684$, $p = 0.010$), while Pre-Anesthesia PCF and OP were related to changes in path length (r -values > 0.57 , p -values < 0.05), global efficiency (r -values > -0.56 , p -values < 0.05), and modularity (r -values > 0.60 , p -values > 0.05). LZC correlated with to its own propofol-induced variation ($r = -0.723$, $p = 0.005$). Results indicate that DOC patients with lower chaoticity and lower PCF may be more susceptible to showing beneficial brain functional changes following propofol exposure. These findings suggest that assessing baseline criticality using hd-EEG may help identify DOC patients whose brain network could functionally benefit from propofol exposure.

IMPACT OF AUDITORY STIMULATION ON SLEEP SPINDLES AND LEARNING PERFORMANCE

Jourde, Hugo R¹; Sita, Katerina; Eyqvelle, Zseyvfin; Brooks, Mary; Coffey Emily B.J.

¹ *Concordia University, Canada*

Abstract

Closed-loop auditory stimulation (CLAS) of slow-oscillations (SO) during sleep has previously been used to enhance memory consolidation. Sleep spindles, which are also implicated in memory processes, are considerably faster and more variable,

making them challenging to detect and manipulate similarly. In collaboration with engineers, we developed a new ML-based device, the Porti-loop, capable of real-time detection and stimulation of sleep spindles.

The present study aimed to compare the effects of spindle stimulation with SO stimulation on memory tasks in young adults. Eighty participants were randomly assigned to four conditions: SO stimulation, spindle stimulation, no stimulation, and wake. They performed cognitive tasks before and after sleep, and EEG activity was monitored during sleep. We were successful in efficiently modulating brain activity and report novel results concerning the electrophysiological impact of closed-loop auditory stimulation of sleep spin-

dles. By comparing their change in performance between before and after sleep, this study aims to characterize the impact of SO vs. spindle stimulation on memory and advance the field of CLAS in neuroscience, with potential implications for interventions in older adults with sleep issues.

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EEGNET: A NEW PLATFORM TO SHARE EEG DATA AND ADVANCED ANALYSIS PIPELINE.

Labelle, Corentin¹; Rogers, Christine; Fecteau Shirley; Bastien Célyne; Blanchette Isabelle; Evans Alan; Albouy Philippe

¹ *Université du Québec à Laval, Canada*

Abstract

In research, results need to be robust and generalizable to further have an impact on society. However, only a few tools have been created to help reproduce results from research studies. This problematic is at the heart of the open science movement, which promotes collaborative work and data sharing. The idea driving open science initiatives is to make research studies easily reproducible, notably by facilitating the reusability of existing datasets.

The EEGNet project aims to provide a platform for sharing and analyzing standardized electroencephalogram (EEG) data. As part of this project, we developed an EEG data analysis tool, based on the Brainstorm software. This user-friendly tool can be used to preprocess, process and perform statistical analysis of EEG data.

This new tool enables to easily perform complex analyses. More importantly, it allows to create shareable analysis pipeline and standardize EEG data in a shareable format, thereby facilitating the reproducibility of neuroscientific studies. This innovative method will be implemented on the EEGNet platform as an online analysis tool.

Altogether, the analytical tools of the EEGNet platform will facilitate, among other things, the study of states of consciousness (e.g., sleep, waking, coma), and will have the potential to contribute to the early detection of EEG abnormalities in children and adults suffering from psychiatric or neurological disorders.

VISUAL RHYTHMIC STIMULATIONS ENTRAIN FRONTO-PARIETAL THETA ACTIVITY AND IMPROVE WORKING MEMORY PERFORMANCE

Fontaine N. ¹, Simoneau K., Ginzburg J., Labelle C., Albouy P., Hoyer R.S.

¹ Université du Québec à Laval, Canada

Abstract

Working memory refers to the cognitive ability to hold and manipulate information and is supported by fronto-parietal functions. Brain oscillations reflect the rhythmic activity of neural networks. Recent results showed that fronto-parietal activity in the human brain can selectively be entrained by visual 3D shapes in rotation flickering at 5 Hz before each trial of an auditory working memory task (Albouy et al., 2022).

The present study investigates this finding can be generalized to other sensory modalities. We thus created a new visual working memory task, which was performed by 20 adults while their brain activity was recorded using EEG. Participants performed different blocks of the task with and without

visual rhythmic stimulation.

Preliminary results show that theta oscillation in the fronto-parietal network positively predicts behavioral performance during manipulation periods and increases brain theta oscillatory activity in the fronto-parietal network.

This study enlarges the basic understanding of working memory and supports the assumption that rhythmic sensory stimulation can be used to causally enhance working memory during task performance. The present results also highlight that the beneficial effects induced by this new brain stimulation technic can generalize across sensory modalities.

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TRACKING SPECTROTEMPORAL MODULATIONS OF NATURALISTIC STIMULI WITH IEEG

Cloutier-Debaque, Émilie ¹; Martineau, Laurence; Ginzburg, Jérémie; Lessard-Bonaventure, Paule; Zatorre, Robert; Albouy, Philippe

¹ Université du Québec à Laval, Canada

Abstract

Human beings have the ability to perceive and understand complex sounds such as music and language. However, scientific consensus has yet to be reached concerning the exact neural mechanisms that underly these processes. So far, studies have mostly employed artificial laboratory stimuli, which potentially limits the generalization of their findings to real-world contexts. We recorded the cerebral activity of seven patient implanted in intra-electroencephalography (iEEG) while they were listening to naturalistic stimuli, which was the first seven minutes of the audio of Harry Potter and the Philosopher's Stone. We

then decomposed the iEEG signal into frequency bands using a Hilbert transform and correlated the time-varying power of the brain signal with the spectrotemporal modulations of the audio. Results show that gamma frequency in primary auditory cortex regions can track both temporal and spectral modulations in seven subjects. We will next investigate the role of the other frequency bands, along with the functional differences in primary versus secondary regions. Finally, we will inquire about the possible lateralization of spectrotemporal modulations in auditory regions.

CHARACTERIZING APERIODIC BRAIN SIGNAL DYNAMICS

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¹ *McGill University, Canada*

Abstract

Brain signal dynamics contain both aperiodic and periodic components at multiple spatial and temporal scales. While the field has long-dismissed broadband aperiodic activity as "noise", mounting evidence suggests that aperiodic activity correlates with regional population spiking, neuronal timescales, and excitation-inhibition balance. Aperiodic spectral dynamics offer a non-invasive glimpse into the evolution of these features with respect to cognition and behaviour. We present SPRiNT as a new, open-source tool for separating dynamic brain signals into periodic and aperiodic

spectral components. SPRiNT is validated comprehensively on synthesized naturalistic time-series and empirical data, including M/EEG and intracranial rodent electrophysiology. Using SPRiNT, we demonstrate the added value of tracking aperiodic dynamics to understand the neurophysiology of demographic trends and behaviour. SPRiNT responds to growing neuroscientific interests in disambiguating dynamic periodic and aperiodic brain activity and advancing our understanding of broadband brain signals.

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CHANGES IN VISUAL PERCEPTION PREDICTED BY ALPHA POWER IN BINOCULAR RIVALRY WITH INTEROCULAR GROUPING

Eric Mokri¹, Jason da Silva Castanheira, Mathieu Landry, Janine D. Mendola

¹ *McGill University, Canada*

Abstract

Binocular rivalry (BR) is a bistable visual phenomenon where two incompatible images are simultaneously presented, one to each eye, and elicit perceptual alternations between image dominance and suppression. Remarkably, BR accommodates interocular grouping (IOG) so that if complementary portions of two globally coherent images are shown separately to each eye, subjects still perceive alternations and global patterns far more often than would be expected by chance. We found that alpha oscillations (8-13Hz) in the posterior cortex during rivalry viewing (n=25) was predictive of perceptual alternations. Alpha os-

cillations in this region are hypothesized to be inhibitory in nature, thus the decrease in alpha power preceding a switch in percept is thought as releasing the breaking mechanisms, and allows the new dominant percept to emerge. The decrease in alpha power was observed to differ both spatially and temporally across grouping demands, with markers of alpha change occurring earlier during IOG. We found further evidence that the mechanisms of alpha power fluctuations are happening prior to the dynamics of image dominance and suppression traced by frequency-tagging with MEG.

HEARING WITH HANDS: VIBROTACTILE STIMULATION GENERATES A FREQUENCY-FOLLOWING RESPONSE

Zatorre, Robert; Coffey, Emily; Sharp, Andréanne; Chauvette, Loonan;
Farrés Franch, Marcel; Carbajal Chavez, Ana ¹

¹ McGill University, Canada

Abstract

Auditory perception is the primary gateway for communication through language and music. However, other senses can support or alter this perception. The interactions between auditory and tactile perception remain understudied to date even though these two modalities are responsive to similar physical phenomena (i.e., vibrations). Prior studies have documented that the auditory cortex can respond to vibrotactile input. However, the nature of this neural response remains unclear; in particular, the degree to which periodicity encoding in the brain occurs in response to vibrotactile input.

The frequency-following response (FFR) is a non-invasive evoked brain response measured using electroencephalography that can be used to

study the fidelity of auditory feature encoding of complex sounds represented in the central auditory system. This study aimed to investigate if the FFR could be a useful tool to investigate the underlying mechanisms of tactile perception of sounds.

Results reveal that it is possible to measure a FFR using vibrotactile stimulation in the absence of auditory input. The tactile FFR exhibits different characteristics compared to unimodal auditory FFRs, including lower amplitude and no sensitivity to harmonics. Combined modality stimulation did not lead to amplitude summation. These findings modality interaction, opening up questions about the origins and pathways responsible for the phenomena.

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THE NEED FOR OPEN SOURCE PORTABLE EEG SYSTEMS: A CASE STUDY

Brooks, Mary ¹, El Chami, Randa, Jourde, Hugo, Coffey, Emily B.J.

¹ Concordial University, Canada

Abstract

The advent of new, portable EEG systems has enabled a variety of study designs that were previously impractical. Polysomnography (PSG), the gold standard in sleep research, involves individual and specific placement of electrodes on the scalp, which is not feasible for study participants to wear at home, especially for older adults. Although overnight studies in the lab are possible, they are resource-intensive and limited to a few nights of recording. We used Dreem headbands to study sleep variability in older adults over 14 nights and its relationship to next-day cognitive performance. While highlighting the value of wearable, user-friendly EEG devices that can be implemented at home,

we also encountered a major limitation of closed-source hardware: the company was bought out during our study, and we were no longer able to collect or access data with the devices we had purchased (except at exorbitant subscription fees). Our experience is a cautionary tale, but also motivates the community development of wearable, affordable and user-friendly EEG systems like the Portiloop (Valenchon et al., 2022), developed in our lab as an open science project. We will discuss plans to further extend the Portiloop's capacity such that we can ensure access to high quality, low cost tools for our research community.

Local workshops & tutorials

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GSP: GRAPH SIGNAL PROCESSING

Nicolas Farrugia¹

¹ *IMT Atlantique, France*

CONN2RES: REVERSE ENGINEERING THE CONNECTOME USING RESERVOIR COMPUTING

Bratislav Mistic¹, **Filip Milisav**¹

¹ *McGill University, Montréal, Canada*

THE PORTILOOP: A DEEP-LEARNING BASED REAL-TIME SYSTEM FOR CLOSED-LOOP BRAIN STIMULATION

Emily Coffey¹, **Giovanni Beltrame**²

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² *Polytechnique Montréal, Montréal, Canada*

GOOFI-PIPE: AN ACCESSIBLE AND MODALITY-AGNOSTIC BIOFEEDBACK FRAMEWORK FOR EXPLORATIVE EXPERIMENTS

Antoine Bellemare Pépin^{1,2}, **Philipp Thölke**¹,
Yann Harel¹, **François Lespinasse**^{1,2}

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² *Concordia University, Montreal, Canada*

HYPYP: HYPERSCANNING PYTHON PIPELINE

Guillaume Dumas¹

¹ *Université de Montréal, Montréal, Canada*

NONLINEAR ANALYSIS OF MUSICAL SYNCHRONY IN BRAIN AND BEHAVIOUR

Caroline Palmer¹

¹ *McGill University, Montréal, Canada*

MEASURING MUSICAL SYNCHRONY IN GROUP SETTINGS

Anna Zamm¹

¹ *Aarhus University, Denmark*

Nijmegen

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Local plenary lectures

FACING THE SMALL DATA REALITY

Michael Tangermann¹

¹ *Donders Institute, Radboud University, Nijmegen, The Netherlands*

Local symposium

RECENT ADVANCES IN OPM SYSTEMS AND RESEARCH

Chair : Denis Schwartz, INSERM, Lyon Neuroscience Research Center, France

RECENT DEVELOPMENTS IN OPMs

Arjan Hillebrand^{1,2,3}

¹ *Amsterdam UMC, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam, Department of Clinical Neurophysiology and MEG Center, Amsterdam, The Netherlands ;* ² *Amsterdam Neuroscience, Brain Imaging, Amsterdam, The Netherlands ;*

³ *Amsterdam Neuroscience, Systems and Network Neurosciences, Amsterdam, The Netherlands*

ADOPTING OPMs FOR COGNITIVE NEUROIMAGING

Robert Oostenveld¹

¹ *Donders Institute for Brain, Cognition and Behavior, Radboud University, Nijmegen, Netherlands*

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NATURALISTIC OPM-MEG: FROM NEURODEVELOPMENT TO HYPERSCANNING

Niall Holmes¹

¹ *Sir Peter Mansfield Imaging Centre, School of Physics and Astronomy, University of Nottingham, Nottingham, United Kingdom*

Local Talks

TOWARDS HIGH-SPEED NON-INVASIVE BCIs FOR COMMUNICATION AND CONTROL: USING EFFICIENT (DE)CODING AND SMALL DATASETS

Jordy Thielen¹

¹ *Donders Institute for Brain, Cognition and Behaviour, Radboud University, Nijmegen, The Netherlands*

HEART-TO-BRAIN INTERACTION (HBI) FACILITATES MOTOR IMAGERY PERFORMANCE: A NOVEL APPROACH TO NON-INVASIVE BCIS

Giuseppe Lai¹

¹ *Goldsmiths University of London, London, United Kingdom*

DEVELOPMENT OF IMPLANTABLE BCI TECHNOLOGY FOR COMMUNICATION & TRANSLATION TO CLINICAL APPLICATIONS

Nick Ramsey¹

¹ *Brain Center, University Medical Center Utrecht, Utrecht University, The Netherlands*

MOABB: BENCHMARK YOUR BCI ALGORITHMS ON A RICH COLLECTION OF MOTOR IMAGERY, ERP, SSVEP AND c-VEP DATASETS

Pierre Guetschel¹

¹ *Donders Institute, Radboud University, Nijmegen, The Netherlands*

PREDICTIVE NEURAL REPRESENTATIONS OF NATURALISTIC DYNAMIC INPUT

Ingmar de Vries¹

¹ *Donders Institute, Radboud University, Nijmegen, The Netherlands*

PREDICTING WHEN AND WHAT IN SPEECH

Sanne ten Oever¹

¹ *Maastricht University, Maastricht, The Netherlands*

ATTENTION CONTROL IN MULTISENSORY PERCEPTION

Kun Dong¹

¹ *Donders Institute for Brain, Cognition and Behaviour, Radboud University, Nijmegen, The Netherlands*

CORTICAL DYNAMICS UNDERSLYING THE INTERPLAY BETWEEN EXPRESS VISUOMOTOR RESPONSES AND POSTURAL CONTROL

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¹ *Department of Rehabilitation, Radboudumc, Nijmegen, The Netherlands*; ²*Donders Institute for Brain, Cognition and Behavior, Nijmegen, The Netherlands*

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Posters

TOWARDS ROBERT MOTOR ATTEMPT BCI CONTROL

Ivo de Jong¹

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DECODING THE ROLE OF PRIOR INFORMATION ON TEMPORAL DIMENSION OF BIOLOGICAL MOTION PERCEPTION THROUGH EEG AND TEMPORAL GENERALIZATION ANALYSIS

Hüseyin Orkun Elmas¹

¹ *Donders Institute, Radboud University, Nijmegen, The Netherlands*

'DO WORDS BURN IN A SECOND LANGUAGE?': PROCESSING LITERAL AND METAPHORICAL PAIN IN L2 DISCOURSE COMPREHENSION. AN ERP STUDY.

Andrea González-García Aldariz¹, Eva M. Moreno^{1,2}, Alice Foucart¹

¹ Universidad Antonio de Nebrija, Madrid, Spain ; ² Instituto Pluridisciplinar, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, Madrid, Spain

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UMM: UNSUPERVISED CLASSIFICATION OF ERPS WITH CONFIDENCE

Michael Tangermann¹, Jan Sosulski²

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THE ONLINE OPTIMIZATION OF BRAIN-COMPUTER INTERFACE STIMULUS PARAMETERS, A SIMULATUON

Chiara Thöni¹, Max Hinne¹, Michael Tangermann¹

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MODEL-BASED DYNAMIC STOPPING METHOD FOR (c-VEP) BCI

Sara Ahmadi¹, Peter Desain¹

¹ Donders Institute, Radboud University, Nijmegen, The Netherlands

EEG POTENTIALS EVOKED BY DEEP BRAIN STIMULATION IN PATIENTS WITH TREATMENT-RESISTANT DEPRESSION

Joana Pereira^{1,2}, Matthias Dold², Bastian Sajonz¹, Michael Tangermann², Volker Coenen¹

¹ Lab of Stereotaxy and Electrophysiology - University Medical Center Freiburg ; ² Donders Institute, Radboud University, Nijmegen, The Netherlands

DAREPLANE PLATFORM FOR CLOSED-LOOP DEEP BRAIN STIMULATION RESEARCH

**Matthias Dold², Joana Pereira^{1,2}, Bastian Sajonz¹, Volker Coenen¹, Marjolein Janssen³,
Michael Tangermann¹**

¹ Lab of Stereotaxy and Electrophysiology - University Medical Center Freiburg ; ² Donders Institute, Radboud University, Nijmegen, The Netherlands ; ³ School of Sports Studies, Fontys University of Applied Sciences, Eindhoven, The Netherlands, Department of Industrial Design, Eindhoven University of Technology, Eindhoven, The Netherlands

Local workshops & tutorials

FROM SPATIAL FILTERING TO TEMPORAL RESPONSE FUNCTIONS IN M/EEG DATA

Hugo Weissbart^{1,2}

¹ *Donders Centre for Cognitive Neuroimaging*

² *Max Planck Institute for Psycholinguistics*

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Local plenary lectures

NEUROPHYSIOLOGY OF LANGUAGE: BODY, EXPERIENCE AND DISEASE

Adolfo García ^{1,2,3,4}

¹ University of San Andrés, Center for Cognitive Neuroscience, Buenos Aires, Argentina ; ² Latin American Brain Health (BrainLat) Institute, Universidad Adolfo Ibáñez, Región Metropolitana, Chile ; ³ Global Brain Health Institute, University of California San Francisco, San Francisco, California, USA, Trinity College Dublin, Dublin, Ireland ; ⁴ Departamento de Lingüística y Literatura, Facultad de Humanidades, Universidad de Santiago de Chile, Estación Central, Santiago, Chile

Abstract

The neuroscience of language is a branch of cognitive neuroscience, a field aimed to understand the relationship between our mental experiences and our biology, with emphasis on the brain in the context of our bodies. We, human beings, have many mental abilities that can be studied scientifically. Many researchers are interested in unders-

tanding the neurobiological bases of memory, or the origin of emotions or attention, and so on. Trying to understand how language (the ability to produce and comprehend language, to acquire a native tongue, or to learn a foreign language) relates to the brain is the task of the neuroscience of language.

RELIABILITY AND CLINICAL SIGNIFICANCE IN EEG EXPERIMENTAL DESIGNS

José A. Biurrún Manresa^{1,2}

¹ Institute for Research and Development in Bioengineering and Bioinformatics (IBB), CONICET-UNER, Oro Verde, Argentina ; ² Center for Neuroplasticity and Pain (CNAP), Department of Health Science and Technology, Aalborg University, Aalborg, Denmark

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Abstract

Reliability is a topic in health science in which a critical appraisal of the magnitudes of the measurements is often left aside to favor a formulaic analysis. Furthermore, the relationship between clinical relevance and reliability of measurements is often overlooked.

Panel discussions

WOMEN LEADING IN NEUROSCIENCE (ROUNDTABLE)

Chair :

Victoria Peterson, Institute of Applied Mathematics of the Litoral, UNL-CONICET, Santa Fe, Argentina
Belén Moglia, Foundation Center for Nuclear and Molecular Medicine Entre Ríos, Argentina
Jesua Aizcorbe, Foundation Center for Nuclear and Molecular Medicine Entre Ríos, Argentina

Abstract

The roundtable discussion on the pivotal role of women in science, specifically in the field of neuroscience, illuminated the significance of their contributions and the challenges they face in this dynamic discipline. The session highlighted the remarkable strides made by female scientists, shedding light on their invaluable impact on the

advancement of neuroscience. Furthermore, the roundtable addressed systemic barriers and biases that impede the progress of women in neuroscience. Discussions revolved around strategies for overcoming these obstacles, including mentorship programs, advocacy for equal opportunities, and initiatives promoting work-life balance.

Posters

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QUANTIFYING CEREBRAL DYNAMICS IN PARKINSON'S: DEEP BRAIN STIMULATION EFFECTS EXPLORED

Lijandy Jiménez Armas¹, **Constantino Méndez Bértolo**², **Florencia Sanmartino**³, **Fernando López Sosa**², **Raúl Rashid López**⁴, **Raúl Espinosa Rosso**⁴, **Javier Gonzalez Rosa**³, **Diego M Mateos**^{1,5,6}

¹ Instituto de Matemática Aplicada del Litoral (IMAL-CONICET-UNL), 3000, Santa Fe, Argentina ; ² Department of Psychology, University of Cadiz, 11003 Cadiz, Spain ; ³ Institute of Research and Biomedical Innovation of Cadiz (INIBICA), 11009 Cadiz, Spain ; ⁴ Department of Neurology, Puerta del Mar University Hospital, 11009 Cadiz, Spain ; ⁵ Science and Technology Faculty, Autonomous University of Entre Ríos, Oro Verde, Argentina ; ⁶ Achucarro Basque Center for Neuroscience, Leioa, Bizkaia, Spain

Abstract

Parkinson's disease stands out as a prominent neurodegenerative disorder with profound impacts on both movement and muscular control, affecting a global community of over 6 million individuals. Among the array of available treatments, Deep Brain Stimulation (DBS), characterized by the implantation of cerebral electrodes, has emerged as a highly effective intervention. By delivering electrical pulses, DBS alleviates motor symptoms such as tremors and rigidity, thereby enhancing patients' overall quality of life. However, beneath its impressive efficacy, a pivotal question lingers: What precisely unfolds within the cerebral dynamics of a person with Parkinson's, and how does DBS modulate these dynamics? To unravel this intricate inquiry, our investigation delved into a meticulous analysis of high-density EEG records sourced from Parkinson's patients experiencing both active and inactive DBS, juxtaposed against a control group. Employing non-classical metrics coming from information theory, encompassing Entropy and Complexity, we ai-

med to uncover nuanced shifts in neural patterns and responses induced by DBS. Our results reveal significant differences in the power information quantifiers between control subjects and those with Parkinson's when DBS is turned off. However, these differences noticeably diminish when DBS is turned on. This suggests that brain dynamics are indeed impacted by Parkinson's disease, yet the implementation of DBS tends.

Local workshops & tutorials

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MNE-PYTHON INTRODUCTION

C. Brigitte Aguilar G.¹, Sofia A. Poux¹, Elizabeth L. Young¹

¹ National University of Entre Ríos, Engineering Faculty, Institute of Bioengineering and Bioinformatics Research and Development, Oro Verde, Entre Ríos, Argentina

ADVANCED EEG PROCESSING WITH MNE-PYTHON

C. Brigitte Aguilar G.¹, Christian A. Mista¹, Sofía A. Poux¹, Elizabeth L. Young¹

¹ National University of Entre Ríos, Engineering Faculty, Institute of Bioengineering and Bioinformatics Research and Development, Oro Verde, Entre Ríos, Argentina

Regensburg

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Local plenary lectures

EEG/ERP DECODING AND REPRESENTATIONAL SIMILARITY ANALYSIS

Steven J Luck¹

¹ *University of California, Davis; Center for Mind and Brain, USA*

USING RHYTHMIC VISUAL STIMULATION TO UNCOVER EARLY BRAIN DEVELOPMENT

Moritz Koester¹

¹ *University of Regensburg, Institute of Psychology, Chair of Developmental Cognitive Psychology, Germany*

INVESTIGATING THE TIME COURSE OF NEURAL REPRESENTATIONS USING EEG-RSA

Marius Zimmermann¹

¹ *University of Regensburg, Institute of Psychology, Chair of Cognitive Neuroscience, Germany*

Abstract

Previous studies using representational similarity analysis (RSA) on fMRI data demonstrated that activation patterns in the lateral occipito-temporal cortex (LOT) during action observation resemble how humans classify actions into semantic categories, suggesting that LOT contributes to accessing meaning of observed actions. In this project, we aim to investigate the temporal aspects of these neural representations using EEG-based RSA. Static images spanning

27 action categories of everyday actions (e.g. riding a bike, washing dishes, brushing hair) were shown to participants in a delayed matching task. Participants were asked to match stimuli on action features, i.e. action category, location and actor identity. Temporally specific neural representational dissimilarity matrices (RDMs) pertaining to neural representations of action categories were generated from EEG recordings using time-resolved MVPA.

These were correlated to independently generated behavioural RDMs pertaining to semantic action (dis)similarities, revealing a time course of neural semantic action representations, as well as other RDMs pertaining to similarity of movement type, body part, scenes and objects, and their respective neural representations. Preliminary results suggest that semantic organizing principles that were found in LOTC can be observed from approximately 150 ms post stimulus presentation onwards, whereas organizing principles related to body and move-

ment features can be observed from 100 ms following stimulus onset. These outcomes suggest that neural representations pertaining to kinematic action features precede those of semantic action features, capturing the computational steps that allow humans to understand observed actions.

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Local talks

INVESTIGATING NEURAL SIGNATURES OF STATISTICAL LEARNING AND LINKS WITH EPISODIC MEMORY ACROSS THE FIRST YEAR OF LIFE

Johannes Julius Mohn¹

¹ *Max Planck School of Cognition, Leipzig; Charité – Universitätsmedizin Berlin, Germany*

Abstract

Infants possess the ability to rapidly learn regularities in their sensory environments from repeated exposure, termed statistical learning. This ability is present early and may scaffold later emerging learning and memory abilities. However, longitudinal studies are lacking that chart the developmental trajectories of infant statistical learning, underlying brain processes, and individual differences therein. This lack is in part due to the challenges of assessing statistical learning and memory in preverbal infants using traditional behavioral paradigms. We are conducting a longitudinal EEG study of individual differences in infant

statistical learning and episodic memory. Our goal is to investigate the development of inter-individual differences in neural learning signatures and how they relate to emerging memory abilities in the first year of life.

PREPROCESSING INFANT EEG USING APICE (AUTOMATED PIPELINE FOR INFANTS CONTINUOUS EEG)

Ana Fló¹

¹ *University of Padova, Department of Developmental Psychology and Socialization, Italy*

Abstract

One of the main challenges when analysing infant EEG is that recordings are short and typically heavily contaminated with artefacts. Additionally, the signal features change along development and variability across participants is higher than in adult data. APICE (Fló et al. 2022) is a set of functions based on EEGLAB and written in MATLAB specifically developed to deal with these issues while keeping the pipeline fully automated. APICE provides multiple algorithms for motion artefact detection using adaptive thresholds. Adaptive thresholds make APICE suitable across age groups without requiring manual rejection or

substantial threshold adjustments for each protocol, resulting in better data recovery than other available pipelines. Moreover, APICE works on continuous data, making it suitable for different types of analysis. APICE also provides functions to define non-functional channels and data segments, correct localized artefacts, and apply ICA combined with iMARA to identify components associated with physiological artefacts. APICE is fully automated, flexible, and modular; thus, it can be easily combined with other toolboxes or pre-processing steps.

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INTRODUCING "BABYCLEAN": A SEMI-AUTOMATIC EEG PREPROCESSING PIPELINE

Peng Wang¹

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Abstract

"babyClean" is a semi-automatic EEG preprocessing pipeline designed based on the functions and toolboxes of EEGLAB, with flexible control manager scripts written in Matlab. It includes standard EEG preprocessing steps, such as re-referencing, automatic line removal, automatic rejection of bad channels and segments, as well as ICA-based automatic artifact rejection. The preprocessing workflow is divided into three parts: preprocessing for artifact rejection, ICA for artifact rejection, and new preprocessing after artifact removal. Each step can work independently

and is repeatable for fine-tuning parameters. We provide necessary information without overwhelming the user, assisting in their "decision-making" process. Additionally, we've integrated some "Tips and Tricks" from experienced EEG analysts into the pipeline to offer choices for different preprocessing step combinations. Advanced users have the flexibility to incorporate their own, more advanced workflows into the pipeline. Our design goal is to allow the pipeline to switch between full automation with standard threshold criteria and individual experience-based fine-tuning.

DISCOVER-EEG: AN OPEN, FULLY AUTOMATED EEG PIPELINE FOR BIOMARKER DISCOVERY IN CLINICAL NEUROSCIENCE

Cristina Gil Ávila¹

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Abstract

Biomarker discovery in neurological and psychiatric disorders critically depends on reproducible and transparent methods applied to large-scale datasets. Electroencephalography (EEG) is a promising tool for identifying biomarkers. However, recording, preprocessing and analysis of EEG data is time-consuming and mostly subjective. Therefore, we developed DISCOVER-EEG, an open and fully automated pipeline that enables easy and fast preprocessing, analysis and visualization of resting state EEG data. Data in the standard EEG-BIDS structure are automatically preprocessed and physiologically meaningful features of brain function (including oscillatory power, connecti-

vity and network characteristics) are extracted and visualized using two open-source and widely used Matlab toolboxes (EEGLab and FieldTrip). We exemplify the use of the pipeline for biomarker discovery in healthy ageing in the LEMON dataset, containing 212 healthy participants. We demonstrate its utility to speed up biomarker discovery in a clinical setting with a new dataset containing 74 patients with chronic pain. Thus, the DISCOVER-EEG pipeline facilitates the aggregation, reuse and analysis of large EEG datasets, promoting open and reproducible research on brain function.

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Local workshops & tutorials

INTRODUCTION TO FIELDTRIP

Marius Zimmermann¹

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REPRESENTATIONAL SIMILARITY ANALYSIS

RSA Theory

Zuzanna Kabulska¹

¹ *University of Regensburg, Institute of Psychology, Chair of Cognitive Neuroscience, Germany*

EEG-RSA in Matlab

Tonghe Zhuang¹

¹ *University of Regensburg, Institute of Psychology, Chair of Cognitive Neuroscience, Germany*

Santiago

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Flash talks

THE EFFECT OF EMOTIONAL SALIENCE ON ATTENTIONAL CAPTURE

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Abstract

Attentional capture is a phenomenon that has been studied for over 25 years. Two main positions have been proposed to explain this phenomenon, the bottom-up or stimulus-driven perspective and the top-down or goal-driven perspective. In 2020, Luck et al. suggested a middle ground between these opposing viewpoints, proposing that stimulus features capture attention, but if they are not part of the task, attention capture is inhibited and reoriented toward the individual's goal. These positions have mainly been based on non-emotional stimuli, overlooking the adaptive value and daily exposure of individuals to emotional stimuli. Therefore, the aim of this pilot study is to establish the effect of emotional salience on attentional

capture. Twelve subjects over 18 years old participated in the experimental sequence, where they had to respond to the location of a neutral facial expression in competition with a positive or negative expression. The pilot results indicate that participants take longer to respond to the target expression (neutral) when it is accompanied by a negative expression compared to when a positive expression is present. It is expected that the behavioral results will maintain the same trend, while at the electroencephalographic level, differences in the ERP N2pc and P300 are anticipated, which are associated with early selective attention and executive attention, respectively.

DO CEREBRAL AND SOMATIC PHYSIOLOGICAL MEASURES ALLOW US TO ANTICIPATE THE OCCURRENCE OF AN INSIGHT IN PROBLEM SOLVING?

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Abstract

Insight problem-solving is an intriguing phenomenon where a person suddenly finds the solution to a problem that is considered difficult. This experience is often accompanied by astonishment and an iaha! exclamation. Insight problem-solving has been investigated using performance measures, brain physiological measures such as EEG, fMRI, and a lesser grade heart rate variability, skin conductance, and eye movements. However, these studies haven't tackled the dynamic component that usually takes the form of nonlinear trajectories that traditional linear analysis ignores. Furthermore, studies have ignored the synchronization of brain and bodily signals exhibited in crucial moments that could anticipate insight.

In this issue, the Recurrence Quantification Analysis (RQA) has resulted very informative. RQA is a multidimensional statistical analysis used to

discover repetitive patterns (referred to as recurrences) in a time series. Based on these patterns, RQA can capturing the dynamics of problem solving, like stability, predictability, and uncertainty of the signals. For example, a recent article studied the dynamic components of pupil diameter fluctuations by means of a RQA. This analysis could anticipate who later solved an insight task (and who won't), even 1 minute before the task finished (Vásquez et al., 2023). One could use RQA in physiological time series to specify moments where these signals synchronize and so characterize trajectories and anticipate insight moments. A more profound comprehension of how physiological measures are deployed (brain and bodily) and synchronized could allow us to formulate a predictive model based on physiological measures.

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I CAN BEAT YOU: HEART-BEAT EVOKED POTENTIALS DURING SOCIAL INTERACTIONS

Aitana Grasso-Cladera ^{1,2}, Josefina Mattoli-Sánchez ¹, Francisco J. Parada ¹

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Abstract

Cognition can be understood as an embodied and environmentally scaffolded phenomenon. Hence, cognitive processes should be studied addressing their relationship with the agents' entire biology and their environments. In this sense, several hypotheses have been developed in order to explain the pathways and characteristics of the inter-system relations within the nervous system (e.g., gut-

brain or heart-brain axes). Cardiac activity, especially the Heart-beat Evoked Potential (HEP), has been used as a biomarker for heart-brain communication through the vagus nerve. HEP has been widely explored regarding interoceptive abilities and clinical populations (e.g., depression, anxiety).

However, it has never been explicitly used to study social interactions, even when interactive behaviors have an evolutionary role, are one of the most common behaviors among social species, and might impact health-disease processes. Here, we explored and compared HEP on a social interaction paradigm with three levels: from no interaction (i.e., hand-gesture identification task) to simulated social interaction (beliefs about an opponent; intentional stance) by playing a computerized version of the "Rock-Paper-Scissors" (RPS) game. While participants were playing, brain and cardiac activity were collected by electroencephalography (EEG) and electrocardiography (ECG), respectively. Results show significant differences

in HEP amplitude when comparing the gesture identification and simulated interaction conditions. Also, there were differences in HEP amplitude when comparing participants regarding their beliefs about the opponent. These exploratory results show the coupling of cardiac and brain activity regarding social cognition, setting the ground to continue exploring brain-body dynamics during social interaction. Future work will focus on parametrically modulating HEP amplitude in tasks with different social constraints.

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RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ANXIETY AND HABITUATION: AN EXPLORATORY STUDY

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Abstract

Habituation is a fundamental learning process involving the reduction of response to repetitive stimuli. Some authors have explored the connection between habituation and anxiety, as habituation could serve as a biomarker for assessing individuals with various anxiety-related symptoms. Existing literature is somewhat ambiguous, with some studies finding a relationship while others do not. To contribute to clarifying this ambiguity, we conducted a two-session experiment. In Session 1, we aimed to investigate short-term or intra-session habituation, and in Session 2, we sought to explore the extent to which habituation is retained. Additionally, we administered a psychometric battery to a sample of 62 participants. The habituation response we examined was the blink reflex. A Pearson correlation analysis revealed negative correlations ranging from moderate to weak between habituation in the first session and scores on the anxiety subscale ($r = -.32$,

$p = .013$), stress subscale ($r = -.273$, $p = .035$), and the total sum of the DASS-21 scale ($r = -.267$, $p = .039$), but not for the depression subscale ($r = -.12$, $p = .362$). One-way ANOVA analyses found an effect of anxiety on reactivity in the first habituation session $F(4,55) = 5.36$, $p = .001$, and on the retention of habituation $F(4,22) = 2.82$, $p = .049$. Stress showed an effect on the first session's habituation $F(4,55) = 2.61$, $p = .045$, reactivity in the first session $F(4,55) = 4.03$, $p = .006$, and the retention of habituation $F(3,23) = 4.79$, $p = .01$. Finally, depression had effects on the retention of habituation $F(4,22) = 10.67$, $p < .001$. Other variables did not show significant effects on the remaining indicators. These results suggest that there might be a relationship between states of anxiety and long-term habituation, although the possibility of these findings being due to differences in sensitization cannot be ruled out.

BEYOND THE "MONA LISA SMILE" EFFECT : BEHAVIORAL AND NEUROELECTROPHYSIO- LOGICAL EVIDENCE FOR THE INFLUENCE OF CONTEXT ON EMOTIONAL RECOGNITION

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Abstract

"The Mona Lisa" by Leonardo da Vinci has been studied extensively due to its enigmatic smile and the multiple interpretations it has elicited. Despite our ability to recognize faces, fully understanding the emotion conveyed requires considering context (Barret, 2017). This study focuses on analyzing emotional recognition in facial expressions and contextual images, including visual and auditory perception in more ecological contexts. Two levels of complexity will be addressed: behavioral and electrophysiological. The findings will provide theoretical information on the role of facial expression in emotional recognition in na-

tural contextual situations, thus, to understand the expression of another, taking the Mona Lisa as an icon, the context in which a facial expression is situated is necessary (Russell, 1996; de Gelder, 2008). They will also contribute to empirical knowledge of emotional processing at the brain level, comparing both levels of complexity with behavior. These results could influence the future development of emotional recognition instruments or programs from infancy to adulthood that will allow strengthening aspects of emotional regulation that to date have been diminished in society.

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LONG-RANGE TEMPORAL CORRELATIONS IN BRAIN-HEART OF SEPTIC PATIENTS WITH DELIRIUM

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Abstract

Sepsis is an organic dysfunction, which has a complication called delirium, understood as an acute cognitive disorder that affects attention, cognition, level of consciousness, circadian rhythm, and psychomotor activity. These changes can be studied from the theory of criticality, which postulates that systems requiring the existence of long-range temporal correlations (LRTC). These indicators of neural self-organization have been studied in cognitive and mental health disor-

ders. Furthermore, a bidirectional communication between the central and autonomic nervous systems is recognized, impacting cognition and body control. LRTC dynamics in heart rate variability (HRV) have been investigated. However, there is still no knowledge of the LRTC dynamics of septic patients with delirium. Our aim is to analyze the LRTC dynamics of cardiac and brain signals in septic patients with delirium during the resting state.

Prospective observational cohort study was implemented, recruited 21 patients with renal, abdominal, or respiratory sepsis, in the emergency room or ICU. The study includes the recording of brain (EEG) and heart (ECG) activity between 0-3 days (M1) and between 4-6 days (M2) at resting state. An analysis of the LRTC change will be performed with the "Detrended fluctuation Analysis (DFA) technique in the different frequency bands of EEG and ECG, first within-subject and then

between subjects with symptoms of delirium versus without delirium. The contributions of research are: i) to detect physiological markers that are easy to apply and use, ii) understand the changes at the brain and heart during the presence of delirium symptoms.

- Global program
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PATTERN RECOGNITION USING FUNCTIONAL GEOSTATISTICS AND DEEP LEARNING TECHNIQUES ON EEG DATA

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Abstract

The present work aims to classify the thought of the five Spanish vowels measured by electroencephalograms (EEG) of 21 electrodes around the Broca's area of the brain of 23 individuals. This was addressed by the framework of spatial functional data, considering each EEG a continuous curve in L2 and performing functional kriging, se-

veral images were constructed to apply classification techniques of machine and deep learning. Finally, both classification routines on average achieve more than 91% precision for each individual, considering that each individual should have its own classification mechanism.

Workshops

ON THE ROLE OF BEHAVIOR IN COGNITIVE ELECTROPHYSIOLOGY

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Abstract

This workshop, titled "On the Role of Behavior in Cognitive Electrophysiology," offers a comprehensive exploration into the integration of behavioral analysis with electrophysiological data, using MATLAB as the primary analytical tool. Aimed at researchers, clinicians, and students in the fields of cognitive science, neuroscience, and psychology, the workshop provides hands-on experience

in processing, analyzing, and interpreting the interplay between behavior and brain activity. Participants will be introduced to MATLAB's environment and toolbox suite tailored for electrophysiological data analysis. The workshop will cover the basics of importing behavioral datasets and will use MATLAB for extracting features such as reaction times.

Using real-world datasets, attendees will learn to visualize behavioral data.

Participants will gain a solid foundation in the principles of the significance of behavioral context in interpreting neural data, and the robust analysis capabilities of MATLAB. By the end of the workshop, attendees will have the skills to

implement a behavioral perspective in their electrophysiological research, leading to richer, more nuanced insights into cognitive processes.

- Global program
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INTRODUCTION TO TIME SERIES ANALYSIS USING THE EEGLAB TOOLBOX: A HANDS-ON TUTORIAL

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Abstract

Time series analysis is an essential component in the evaluation of electrophysiological data, offering insights into the dynamic nature of the brain's electrical activity. "Introduction to Time Series Analysis using the EEGLAB Toolbox: A Hands-On Tutorial" is a workshop designed to equip participants with the foundational skills required to perform time series analysis on electroencephalography (EEG) data using EEGLAB, an open-source MATLAB toolbox.

This workshop is tailored for beginners, including students, researchers, and clinicians interested in EEG data analysis. The tutorial will commence with an overview of time series data principles and the basics of EEG data structure. Participants will be guided through the process of importing

EEG datasets into MATLAB and the utilization of EEGLAB for preprocessing steps such as filtering, artifact rejection, and channel interpolation.

The interactive session will provide hands-on experience with EEGLAB scripting for automating analyses and replicating results. Participants will use real sample data.

By the end of the workshop, attendees will be proficient in using EEGLAB for time series analysis and will understand how to apply these techniques to their own research questions. This tutorial will empower participants with the analytical tools necessary for advancing research in cognitive neuroscience, neuroengineering, and other fields that utilize time series data from EEG recordings.

Talca

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[Local plenary lectures](#)[Link to live capture](#)

STUDYING EEG/iEEG SIGNALS DURING PERCEPTION AND PREDICTION

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Abstract

Large-scale neural interactions are crucial for the communication of perceptual and predictive information. These neural interactions encode distinct aspects of information processing such as transmission and integration. While transmission refers to the relay of information, information integration refers to the non-linear transformation of inputs into outputs through recurrent neural dynamics. In this talk, I will discuss how information theory combined with EEG, ECoG, and computational modelling can help us uncover information integration patterns critical for perception and prediction. In particular, I will focus on how

information theoretical metrics (non-linear) outperform traditional spectral metrics (linear) in distinguishing perceptual contents during internally driven perception (i.e., auditory and visual bistability), and externally driven perception (i.e., olfaction). Finally, in a predictive processing task, I will show how information theoretical metrics further distinguish the specific content of the information processing across the brain, i.e., whether neural interactions encode redundant or synergistic information about prediction errors. This talk suits everyone interested in brain dynamics in the context of EEG/MEG/ECoG data.

PRINCIPLES OF EEG METHODS FOR MEASURING STATES OF CONSCIOUSNESS

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Abstract

Uncovering the neural mechanisms that allow conscious access to information is a major challenge of neuroscience. An incomplete list of still open questions include, What are the necessary brain computational properties to permit access to a stream of conscious contents? What is the relationship between conscious perception, self-awareness, and multisensory processing of bodily signals? How these processes change when the brain transitions to an 'unconscious' state (like sleep, anesthesia or pathological conditions)? Can we externally trigger state-of-consciousness (SOC) transitions using stimulation? In this presentation, I will present my work focus on these

relevant scientific and clinical questions. I will present our latest developments including different pre-clinical and clinical experimental models (brain-injuries and/or anesthesia), neuroimaging methods (EEG, fMRI or brain/body interactions) and stimulation techniques (tES, auditory/somatosensory/visual stimulation).

Overall I will try to demonstrate that the integration of multimodal neural information provides critical information to characterize the state-of-consciousness in physiological and pathological conditions and might help to predict novel optimal therapeutic strategies.

- Global program
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Local talks

USING EEG TO STUDY BISTABLE PERCEPTUAL PHENOMENA

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Abstract

Multistable and bistable phenomena are special conditions in which the same perceptual stimulus can produce alternatively two or more stable perceptual states. The dynamics of these alternating states have been studied both as a phenomenon per se and used as a methodology to understand the emergence of perceptual awareness or other cognitive processes. In this presentation, different

measures of electroencephalographic (EEG) brain activity registering during multistable phenomena will be discussed through examples of diverse studies, highlighting the advantages and contributions of each method and analysis to understand the perceptual phenomena and, ultimately, perceptual awareness.

Local workshops & tutorials

CHALLENGES IN EEG STUDIES WITH MICROSTATES

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Abstract

Brain mapping (genotype–phenotype) generated by EEG is used in a wide range of studies focused on illnesses that affect the brain. Dietrich Lehmann and his work team were pioneers in the EEG microstates field (Lehmann, Ozaki, & Pal, 1987). This area has made great contributions to studies of the brain of different nature, such as disorders caused by cognitive distortions or neurological diseases. Currently, there is a high amount of studies available on neurological disorders with microstates. Brain microstates are semi stable periods that have been located in the topography of each Global Field Power (GFP) peak. In other words, it is the topographic difference in the scalp potential fields, which show changes in the global network activity of the area to be assessed. This topographic difference is analyzed in milliseconds. Thus, microstates are a new niche to be explored within the category of "Computer aided diagnosis using

EEG signals".

The objective of this tutorial is to propose a deep learning method for the exploration and automatic extraction of the main features of the brain electrophysiological signal for the study of EEG, which is obtained after the processing of brain micro-states. Brain microstates will be processed by a trajectory of successive random steps in time, this means that they will be treated by a random walk process, built in accordance to previous studies. Moreover, we will show how a deep learning method is employed for the exploration and automatic extraction of the main features of the random walk, which is known as Convolutional Neural Network (CNN).

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Tehran

- Global program
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Local talks

FRONTOTEMPORAL COORDINATION MODIFIES CORE OBJECT RECOGNITION IN OCCLUDED FACE DECODING

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Abstract

Object recognition under challenging real-world conditions, such as partial occlusion, remains an open question in cognitive neuroscience. While numerous studies have shown the significance of feedforward computations of visual information in accomplishing core object recognition tasks, the neural mechanisms and temporal dynamics of object recognition under occlusion remain poorly understood. Although researchers have investigated frontal feedback and connections and their impact on object recognition, they have not yet fully explored the neural mechanisms and temporal dynamics of these processes or the specific information sent within these feedback connections. To address these gaps, we recorded high-density electroencephalography (EEG) data from human participants viewing images of faces with various occlusions. We dissociated the processing of occlusion and occluded face stimuli and examined

the spatiotemporal dynamics of representations extracted from EEG data. Our findings reveal that frontal feedback drives the late processing stage of occluded face recognition, leading to improved accuracy in identifying faces. Additionally, we found increased synchronized activity between the frontal and temporal areas during occluded stimuli processing compared to intact faces, highlighting the critical role of frontotemporal coordination in occluded face processing during challenging real-world conditions. Furthermore, comparing human EEG with the recorded macaque IT cortex confirmed the contribution of the frontal cortex in the late stage of occluded face processing. However, we observed that the deep computational model failed to capture this feedback mechanism, highlighting the need for model expansion to accurately simulate frontal feedback in occluded face processing.

Local workshops & tutorials

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INTRODUCTION TO EEGLAB

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EYE TRACKING AND EEG INTEGRATION

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INTRODUCTION TO FIELDTRIP

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INTRODUCTION TO MNE-PYTHON

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